

INTERVIEW REPORT

BOLZANO, TRENTO, VORARLBERG AND TYROL

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INTRODUCTION: REPORT STRUCTURE

This report presents the results that emerged from the interviews conducted in the second phase of our empirical analysis (**Stage B**) in the project “Climate change integration in the multilevel governance of Italy and Austria”, financed by the Autonomous Province of Bolzano (Research Südtirol 2019).

The interviewees were selected based on the inputs provided by the project consortium and the results of the document collection (stage A of the data collection). The guiding criterion for mapping stakeholders was to achieve a balanced representation of the sectors covered in the project (transport, energy and water, and spatial planning) whilst capturing an institutional as well a non-institutional perspective.

Each interview lasted approximately 1 hour and was based on the general interview guideline developed by Niccolò Bertuzzi on the basis of the collective inputs received from partners and the research questions of the project. Interviews were conducted in the period June-September 2021 by Niccolò Bertuzzi (Autonomous Province of Trento), Giada Giacomini (Autonomous Province of Bolzano) and Alice Meier (Länder of Tyrol and Vorarlberg). The interviews were conducted either in Italian or German via Zoom, recorded and stored in secure archives according to the privacy rules of each University/Research center involved. This report contains a summary of those interviews. It is written in a descriptive way and aims to highlight the main elements related to the policy sectors and dimensions considered in the project. There was a specific agreement with interviewees that authors should avoid direct quotations from the interviews, unless asking for specific permissions.

Sections 1, 2, 3 and 4 of this document describe the broad results that emerged from our interviews, divided per sub-state territory. Each section is organized as follows: first, we highlight specific sectoral aspects that emerged throughout the interviews: we point out the main documents produced (available in our share folder, Stage A), and then give a narrative overview of themes that emerged during the interviews. These narratives also refer to single respondents; however, anonymization is guaranteed by the use of specific identification codes that are presented in dedicated tables before each single sub-state report. We then provide a cross-sectoral elaboration of the interview results, organized according to the project’s theorized dimensions of climate-change integration (coordination, leadership, participation, information, funding¹). Each heading is divided according to the indicators suggested by Part III chapter contributors. Finally, we give a brief evaluation of the cross-cutting tendencies emerging at the single sub-state levels, and recap on cross-cutting tendencies about obstacles and positive factors favouring climate change integration in sectoral policies across the different sub-state regional cases. The same structure is followed for all the sub-state cases: Bolzano, Trento, Tyrol, and Vorarlberg. However, some minimal differences in the organizations of subparagraphs is present, due to the specific findings emerged in each sub-state case.

Please note that documents mentioned in the report can be found in the cross-cutting folder or in the respective sectoral folders in our shared project folder (under “*data gathering*”). Kindly also note that the following considerations are non-exhaustive and need to be complemented and integrated with the findings of the document collection, *i.e.* the output of the first phase of our data collection (**Stage A**), as well as with your expertise in the respective fields.

¹ With regard to the funding dimension, chapter authors independently conducted one selected expert interview per sub-state territory. This data is an addition to questions posed to all respondents in other interviews and contained in the general guideline. In these reports you find some partial information on the funding dimension, but more structured contributions will be circulated by the authors of this chapter.

1. BOLZANO

Expert-Interviews data in the Autonomous Province of Bolzano (IT):

Number of conducted interviews: 12 Institutional/Administration: 8 Civil Society: 2 Technical expertise: 2

BOLZANO INTERVIEWS - INTERVIEWEE PROFILES

INTERVIEW-CODE (extended)	Interview code (short in text)	TYPE
IntBZ1_Administration_spatial planning	IntBZ_01	Institutional
IntBZ2_Political_cross-cutting	IntBZ_02	Institutional
IntBZ3_Technical expert_cross-cutting	IntBZ_03	Technical expert
IntBZ4_Civil society_cross-cutting	IntBZ_04	Civil society
IntBZ5_Administration_transport	IntBZ_05	Institutional
IntBZ_6_Administration_water	IntBZ_06	Institutional
IntBZ7_Administration_spatial planning	IntBZ_07	Institutional
Int_BZ8_Administration_energy	IntBZ_08	Institutional
Int_BZ9_Administration_cross-cutting	IntBZ_09	Institutional
IntBZ10_Administration_spatial planning	IntBZ_10	Institutional
IntBZ11_Civil society_cross-cutting	IntBZ_11	Civil society
IntBZ12_Administration_energy	IntBZ_12	Institutional

Glossary used in this report:

Name	Description	Website
CasaClima	The CasaClima Agency is a centre of excellence for energy-efficient and sustainable construction and renovation that is widely recognized throughout Italy and now increasingly also on an international level. CasaClima has been founded in 2002 and has created a wide range of quality seals for building products and building certifications that describe sustainable construction in a more holistic approach. Examples include the Nature sustainability seal for residential buildings, Welcome and Hotel in the tourism sector, Wine for wineries, Work&Life for office buildings and School for schools and	https://www.agenziacasaclima.it/it/home-1.html

	<p>kindergartens. In 2014, CasaClima was expanded to become the Energy Agency South Tyrol - CasaClima, a public body of the Autonomous Province of Bolzano - South Tyrol. Since then, the fields of action and competences of the Agency have constantly expanded and new initiatives have been started, such as the programs KlimaGemeinde in the field of municipal climate protection or KlimaFactory for improving energy efficiency in companies.</p>	
Ökoinstitut	<p>Private agency that deals with development of projects and concepts in the fields of environmental education, mobility, climate protection, soft tourism, sustainable lifestyles and sustainable economy for public and private customers.</p>	<p>https://www.oekoinstitut.it/en/</p>
<i>Patto per il Futuro dell'Alto Adige</i>	<p>The “Pact for the Future of South Tyrol” is an independent alliance of citizens that strives to ensure that the transformation of our society towards a future of solidarity, sustainability and crisis-proof is achieved through a participatory path.</p>	<p>https://zukunfts-pakt-pattofuturo.org/it/patto-per-il-futuro-dellalto-adige/</p>
<i>Giunta Provinciale</i>	<p>The provincial government (<i>Giunta</i>) is one of the organs of government of the province. The <i>Giunta</i> is composed of the president of the province and a number of councillors, established by the provincial statute, which must not be more than a quarter of the number of provincial councillors, counting for this purpose also the President, and not more than twelve.</p>	<p>https://www.provincia.bz.it/aprov/giunta-provinciale/default.asp</p>
<i>Assessore/Assessorato</i>	<p>The assessors are appointed by the president of the province among the citizens who meet the requirements of candidacy, eligibility and compatibility to the post of councillor. The assessors are also appointed outside the components of the provincial council but, however, since the office of assessor is incompatible with that of councillor, who was appointed assessor ceases from the post of councillor upon acceptance of the appointment. The President has, according to the law, the widest discretion in the appointment and dismissal of assessors; in practice, however, must take into account the indications of the political forces that support him and, in the case of coalition, weigh the presence in the joint of the same.</p>	<p>https://www.comune.bolzano.it/context.jsp?ID_LIN_K=773&page=5&area=305&id_context=29152</p>
<i>Agenzia provinciale per l'ambiente e la tutela del clima</i>	<p>The South Tyrolean Agency for the Environment and Climate Protection is South Tyrol's largest institution of experts in technical environmental protection, climate protection and resource</p>	<p>https://ambiente.provincia.bz.it/</p>

	<p>protection. The Autonomous Province of Bolzano has established its own environmental agency by provincial law no. 26 of 19 December 1995. Since 1 January 2019, by resolution of the Provincial Council of 18/12/2018, n. 1389, the Agency has assumed the name of "Provincial Agency for the Environment and Climate Protection". New denomination, but also new tasks and new organizational structure.</p>	
Inhouse society	<p>In-house companies are public companies incorporated in corporate form, typically public limited companies, <u>the capital of which is held in whole or in part, directly or indirectly, by a public body entrusting them with instrumental or production activities</u>. The establishment of such companies is one of the ways in which an entity can organize itself to provide internal management services (computer science, cleaning) or public services (for example, transport, energy, hygiene). The creation process can generally be summarised as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • creating an articulation of its organizational structure; • entrusting services by means of a public procedure; • by signing the articles of association of the company. 	n/a

1.1. SECTORAL OVERVIEW

1.1.1. TRANSPORT

Main initiatives and strategies mentioned during the interview:

- **Infrastructural measures:**
 - Val Venosta Railway
- **Strategies & best practices:**
 - Green Mobility Alto Adige (inhouse society)
 - Alto Adige Pedala
 - Bike cream challenge
 - [South Tyrol pass](#)

Overview

In the sector of transport, climate change has not been the direct driver of policies, however some instruments can be beneficial to mitigation. Such aspects emerged from the interviews to several stakeholders. The transport sector is very relevant when it comes to climate change, as one of the key strategies (also fostered by the new Glasgow Climate Plan) is the reduction of polluting emissions from transportation.

In fact, institutional interviewee (IntBZ_05) contended that regarding transportation, mitigation of climate change has not been directly included into strategies and policies, but it has been de facto

realized through the promotion of sustainable transportation which results in a decrease of polluting emissions. According to the same respondent (IntBZ_05), the objective of fighting against climate change has not been directly promoted in transportation governance. The Green Mobility initiative, which was instituted in 2012 [so it is quite “young” in relation to the start date considered in our project methodology, which is 2005] had the initial objective of promoting a better life quality for residents and tourists, together with the promotion of electric mobility. Regarding before-2005 strategies, there were few initiatives that is worth mentioning: the construction of the Val Venosta railway (with all the political debate that followed), which constituted a landmark case insofar it pushed the administration towards the realization of similar projects for the amelioration of the mobility in terms of creating alternatives to the use of cars.

However, the criteria for amelioration of the transport sector in the Autonomous Province of Bolzano has been more an **efficiency vector** rather than a pure environmental one. In order to gain this efficiency, the various administrative departments came together and instituted the **Green Mobility Alto Adige**, a society created by the Autonomous Province of Bolzano but coordinated by *STA - Strutture Trasporto Alto Adige SpA*. The Green Mobility initiative has brought together different actors, private and public, and took the lead in creating new green initiatives, such as the installation of charging stations for electric cars. In this way, Green Mobility has also sensibilized the providers of energy towards this new goal in changing the way people move in cities. Later on, Green Mobility has applied for funding both from public and private sources in order to realize the territorial spreading of charging stations. At the moment, the Autonomous Province of Bolzano is the first in Italy for what concerns the proportion of residents/cars charging stations (IntBZ_05).

Another important initiative for the mobility that has been mentioned is the **South Tyrol pass**: this initiative provided an integrated response to the necessity of moving around the province through the use of means of transportation alternative to cars (IntBZ_09).

1.1.2. SPATIAL PLANNING

Main sectoral initiatives and strategies mentioned during the interview:

- Provincial law 9/2018
- Presidential Decree n. 17/2020
- LEROP “Piano provinciale di sviluppo e coordinamento territoriale” 1995²
- Presidential decree n. 16/2020
- Deliberation 1130 September 2014³
- EUSALP
- [Sinfonia Smartcities project](#)
- Natura 2000
- Parco Nazionale dello Stelvio
- [Sustainability strategy](#)

Overview

As in the other sectors, institutional interviewee (IntBZ_01) observed that the Climate and Energy Plan of the province of Bolzano of 2011 is the main reference document. It was drawn up primarily

² See also <https://www.provincia.bz.it/natura-ambiente/natura-territorio/pianificazione/lerop-piano-sviluppo-coordinamento-territoriale.asp> last accessed September 2021. We are aware that this document is quite dated and that our research methodology includes documents from 2005 only, however administration still refer to it because it has not been produced a more recent plan.

³ Available at http://lexbrowser.provinz.bz.it/doc/it/200354%c2%a710/delibera_30_settembre_2014_n_1130/allegato.aspx.

by the competent division which is the *Agenzia per l'ambiente*. [However, in this and other interviews, we should be mindful that this strategy is the main cross-cutting document for Bolzano and not a sectoral policy]. The plan focuses on mitigation, it should also be stressed that it is somewhat lacking in terms of adaptation to climate change, which was perhaps not such a topical issue at the time when it was drafted and elaborated. But in general, IntBZ_01 reported about a general impression that administrations are doing a lot and very well also in terms of mitigation. Perhaps, there is room for improvements in terms of adaptation.

Institutional interviewee (IntBZ_07) has upheld, regarding to the climate plan, that it is appropriate to make a subdivision with regard to its objectives: 1) the **objective [of the reduction] of 1,5 tons of Co2 per capita** 2) the **mitigation of climate change issues**, which has always been a competence of the *Agenzia* because adaptation requires coordination with other departments, such as the Forestry. In the update of the Climate Plan [which is now in the public consultation phase] the department of the interviewee addressed the question on how it would manage the adaptation to climate change (which is also provided for by European and national law). The answer was precisely that the competent assessor as well as the competent structure must collaborate with other sectoral institutions such as forestry, water and other involved sectors (IntBZ_07).

It was evidenced that in sectoral planning tools, the topic of climate change is indirectly present. This is true for example for the law that concerns the spatial planning sector - **provincial law 9 of 2018** (the provincial law for the territory and the landscape). One of the main objectives listed in Article 2 of the law is to provide for certain measures which indirectly involve adaptation/mitigation to climate change and, in any case, the application of the **principle of land-saving**, the attempt to reduce as much as possible the impact on the soil and therefore to consider the territory and the soil as a resource. In this provincial law, the approach to climate change is de facto integrated. This approach takes its premises from the need to manage the territory by both avoiding natural hazards and consequently managing in a correct way the building sector.

It has been highlighted that in terms of spatial planning the “**famous Lerop**” of 1995 is still in force, so a very dated instrument. The institutional actor interviewed (IntBZ_01) affirmed that it is appropriate to provide a new instrument and the administration is beginning to do so through the preparation of the provincial strategic plan, as established by the provincial law 9 of 2018. The new provincial plan will serve as a coordination policy, because at the hierarchical level it is above all planning tools and, therefore, it serves as a reference for sub-regional and then at the municipal spatial planning level. In the new instrument, the administration will try to include a view to include the interlinkages to the climate plan.

Another strategy that has been mentioned (IntBZ_07) is **EUSALP**, the macroregional European strategy for the Alpine region, which as reported on its website, is “endorsed by the European Council, which may be supported by the European Structural and Investment Funds among others, to address common challenges faced by a defined geographical area relating to Member States and third countries located in the same geographical area which thereby benefit from strengthened cooperation contributing to achievement of economic, social and territorial cohesion.”⁴

The necessity of dealing with the reduction of GHGs emissions, and the need for putting into practice the above-mentioned initiatives, implied a **re-organization of the infrastructure for the transportation of energy**, ameliorating the travelling time of energy from the source to the buildings or other venues for private use. At the moment, in the Province of Bolzano there are 240km of high

⁴ From EUSALP website.

voltage infrastructure, and this has required an extensive modification of the spatial planning, for example in the areas of Brennero, Passo dello Stervio, Val Pusteria (IntBZ_09).⁵

Finally, regarding the update of the Climate Plan, it has been evidenced by a sectoral expert that an important element of novelty will be represented by a new temporal limit for **mitigation and adaptation measures, as they will have the year 2030 as time limit**, and not just the 2050 as per in the current Climate Plan (IntBZ_07).

1.1.3. ENERGY AND WATER

ENERGY

Main sectoral initiatives and strategies mentioned during the interviews:

- Bonus 110% (State level but with important repercussions in the province)
- Bonus “cubatura”
- CasaClima
- ComuneClima
- ScuolaClima [see also section “information”]
- Legge provinciale 9/2018
- SDGs
- Sustainability report
- [Sustainability strategy](#) (connected to the SDGs)

Overview

In the first part of the present research project we found that most of the climate-related policies and directive in the Bolzano Province are related to the energy sector. The interviews confirmed how crucial is the energy sector for climate change policy. **The energy sector is directly connected to the reduction of energy consumption in relation to climate change mitigation objectives.** Thus, it is a sector of utmost importance in the fight against climate change in the Autonomous Province of Bolzano, as demonstrated by the abundance of laws, policies and strategies evidenced in the Stage A of the research (desk research). In the last 15-20 years, climate change mitigation has being translated into a direct political and legal attention to energy policies, since over 80% of our greenhouse gas emissions are somehow attributable to the theme of energy (IntBZ_08). The main frame of reference for the energy policies is contained in the 2011 Climate Plan of the Bolzano Province. The mitigation strategy is based on three pillars/requirements: 1) the increase in renewable energy to 90% coverage of needs, 2) the reduction of emissions to 1.5 tons per annum, and 3) an increase in energy efficiency with a continuous power of up to 2200 W per annum (IntBZ_10).

Regarding adaptation and mitigation, an interviewee from civil society specified that, while sectoral initiatives initially started to focus on the sectoral adaptation to climate change, more recently mitigation efforts can be detected at the planning stage sectoral strategies such as the energy plan, climate plan, plans related to mobility, land development and landscape. However, climate change is not considered as one of the main topic, it is not considered as one of the system factors, but rather a variable (IntBZ_11).

From the interviews it emerged that since the 2000s the aim has been to promote the technology of **district heating fuelled by biomass**, fostered by the fact that there is a local production of woody biomass. At the same time, this approach shows some limitations today, because biomass is used

⁵ Not entirely sure of all this because the interviewee did not consent to recording the interview therefore I had to takes notes while he was talking.

locally. In the Autonomous Province of Bolzano there is a situation where in many municipalities there is no gas, and therefore people still use oil and fuel to heat up their houses. On the one hand, the objective is to improve the technology for the generation of thermal energy (easily adaptable in a mountain context), on the other hand, it is important to take into consideration the Sustainable Development Goals especially for what concerns the sustainable development (IntBZ_11).

The interviewees affirmed that there are fundamentally two priorities to be followed: according to the European regulations, the input of “**Energy efficiency first**” was to try at first to reduce energy consumption in all areas, in construction, transport, in production processes in the private sector, etc, and then at a later stage at the Provincial level the governance must try to decarbonize the remaining abovementioned energy requirements of the climate plan.

According to IntBZ_08, the construction sector is very important for the energy efficiency objectives or the overall reduction of the environmental footprint in the construction sector. The respondent asserted that it is well known that the largest building industry is the world’s highest energy and raw material consumer, and also the largest producer of waste and emissions (it accounts for about 40% of our total energy consumption) and is responsible for over a third of CO2 emissions (IntBZ_08).

IntBZ_12 clarified the **interlinkage between the Climate Plan and the Sustainability strategy**. The institutional actor affirmed that these two strategies are closely interrelated. Even though the sustainability strategy is a more recent concept since it was adopted a couple of years ago, it contains an important objective with relation to climate change [in fact, climate change is one of the 17 SDGs]. Thus, the Climate Plan works as an actualization and operationalization of the Sustainability Strategy: “this update of the climate plan is seen in the light of new developments within the province as part of the sustainability plan.” The interviewee also added that the Sustainability Strategy contains important trackers that help in pursuing the SDGs’ objectives. So there is also an ongoing work to make the sustainability methodologies and the climate plan methodologies consistent. As reported by the same interviewee, coordination between sustainability and the climate plan is therefore improving (IntBZ_12).

Regarding the energy sector, the initiative **CasaClima** (inhouse agency), with its method of energy efficiency certification for houses and buildings, is deemed crucial by many stakeholders interviewed when it comes to energy efficiency. In fact, the Initiative CasaClima has been nominated and their initiatives illustrated by many stakeholders who took part in the interviews (IntBZ_02; IntBZ_03; IntBZ_08; IntBZ_09).

In 2005 it was introduced in South Tyrol - obligatorily - a “Casaclima C” certification class as a minimum standard for all buildings and new buildings. Consequently, over time the emissions reduction objective has been improved in 2011 with the certification a “Casaclima B” and then to a “Casaclima A” in 2017. We know that a CasaClima-certified house consumes 10% less of the energy compared to the existing average building, and also covers a large part of its needs from renewable sources. This must be underlined because building in a sustainable way and upgrading the existing, are the most effective and cheapest measures to reduce our environmental impact (IntBZ_08).

In relation to CasaClima, the technical expert (IntBZ_03) evidenced that, when it comes to the implementation of energy efficiency measures established by CasaClima certification system, the **role of municipalities**, rather than the Province, it is crucial. The interviewee stressed that the initiative ComuneClima gives the possibility of ameliorating the energy efficiency to municipalities. The latter are responsible for the implementation of these policies. In fact, at the provincial level, national directives are normally transposed, but **on the territory the municipalities actually implement the measures in the field of climate protection** (IntBZ_03). Another important initiative

according to this stakeholder is constituted by the **national sustainability report**, designated by a national law that obliges companies of a certain size to write this report. There are also many private companies that are below this threshold but that compile the report voluntarily, but always according to the mandatory criteria to be able to compare with other companies in the sector and be up to the competition also at international level [businesses in Alto Adige ranked as some of the highest in Italy according to ASvis e Cerved [report](#)].

However, the stakeholder from civil society evidenced certain **critical aspects** in relation to CasaClima, and in general to the politics of energy efficiency represented by the national 110% Bonus, because in (IntBZ_11)'s view is not a systemic instrument but only an incentive directed mainly to wealthy categories of the population.⁶

Among the other initiatives related to this sector, the interviews highlighted the importance of the introduction (in 2012) of the **Bonus cubatura**: for residential buildings a bonus of 200 cubic meters, and on commercial residential areas a 20% of the building mass - in the case of a new building (climate-class A-nature) up to 15% of the cubic capacity. This instrument has been very successful in reducing emissions. This year will end the *bonus cubatura*, and decision-makers must decide in politics if they want to extend this initiative for another 2/3 years, and in the future, how we would like to present it to citizens (IntBZ_10).

WATER (management)

Main sectoral initiatives mentioned during the interview:

- Piano generale utilizzazione acque pubbliche/ General Plan for the Use of Public Water (Presidential decree June 2017)
- Nuovi canoni idrici (Legge 10 ottobre 2019)
- Delibere 857 e 848 Novembre 2020
- [National green certificates](#) (hydroelectric)

Overview

When it comes to the integration of climate change in the Province of Bolzano, water policies are strictly interrelated to the energy policies because of their connection in the **hydroelectric sector**. This sector is considered a source for renewable energy and therefore a key and an operational element of climate change mitigation. The information contained in this section comes mainly from IntBZ_06, since it is an institutional actor who works exclusively in the water sector.

(IntBZ_06) evidenced the fact that in the last 15 years or so, several legislative initiatives have been taken (by the *Ufficio Tutela Acque*, or with the contribution of the *Ufficio Gestione Risorse Idriche*). Such initiatives were mainly implemented in the publication of the general plan for the use of public water, the first draft of which came out in 2012, and actually entered into force with the **decree of the President of the Republic in June 2017**. The most important measure from the point of view of climate change mitigation (but understood as fighting the effects of climate change in particular) was

⁶ IntBZ_11 declared that “certainly it has been possible to intervene on many aspects, such as promoting a culture for the renovation of buildings linked to the concept of CasaClima. But the actual recovery and building transformation rate was only 2% a year, despite the system allows for direct incentives (and not tax credit), which should be an excellent incentive. And yet the renovation of buildings remains blocked at 2% if not less. Let’s say that the administration at the provincial level allows you to move more nimbly than what happens at the state level... Then a whole series of policies were made including the ‘cubatura bonus’ that allowed (in exchange for an energy recovery) to expand a cubatura of about 25%... but in my opinion, this is **‘energy recovery for the few and for the rich’**”.

the introduction (in 2019) of new **water charges**, thanks to **Law 10 of October 2019**, and to the **resolutions 857 and 848 of November 2020**, which give effect to the articles provided for by the aforementioned Law 10. These two resolutions are important because they define all the new water fees and, concerning the irrigation use - that is the main use in the Province - provide a set of **fee reductions for those users who apply sustainable practices**, such as saving water through the use of reservoirs rather than irrigation facilities that are less expensive.

Then, the entry into force of **national green certificates for the facilitation of the construction of new hydroelectric power stations** gave a certain impulse also in the Province, but it was not decided directly by local autonomy. Climate change certainly has an impact on the availability of water, so even with the granting of concessions should be taken into account the fact that in some cases there is a limited availability of water. For example, in the Province of Bolzano there are areas which are already recognized (at least in general) as less water-rich areas, and the general plan also provides for the definition of drought zone areas in the next period (IntBZ_03).

The planned measures, according to the interviewee, would be focussed on the introduction of **droughty zones**. The water management plans would be characterized for a more sustainable and forward-looking water management. This objective is already present in the General Plan for the Use of Public Water, in the regulatory part.⁷

1.2. DIMENSIONS OF INTEGRATION

1.2.1. COORDINATION (HORIZONTAL)

Common objectives and common strategy on climate-change integration

The respondents recognized that there are **shared objectives between departments in the fight against climate change**, and they highlighted the features of the climate-change strategy/sustainability strategy of Bolzano. However, there is a shared institutional concern with regard to the implementation of these shared objectives.

It was further highlighted that what makes the integration of climate-change in sectoral policies difficult is the **lack of the necessary structure in the administration**, which is not naturally set up to deal with such a large cross-cutting issue. This structural unpreparedness seems to be linked to the process-innovation that climate-change integration could concretely require, and to the fact, perceived as an anomaly, that the same political party has been governing in the past 50-60 years ago, influencing the public administration (IntBZ_02; IntBZ_04).

The existing coordination mechanisms and their viability

Several interviewed stakeholders perceive difficulties in the coordination between different offices of the public administration when it comes to the integration of climate change policies in administrative and legislative measures (see also last section of this report). According to the civil

⁷ The plan, in its Part III (art. 40, paragraph 2), provides for the identification by resolution of the provincial council of “areas characterized by drought or recurrent situations of water supply crisis. (...) For such territorial areas, it must however be elaborated within the terms that will be established with deliberation of the Provincial Council, from the competent provincial Authorities in collaboration with the concessionaires interested, a specific plan aimed at ensuring sustainable water use and achieving good quality status. The plans must be drawn up and implemented, taking into account water saving strategies, the use of alternative sources of supply and the use of reservoirs, as well as the requirement of a minimum viable outflow. The plans are approved by the Provincial Council.” [translated from Italian]

society stakeholder (IntBZ_11), the branch of the administration that deals with the risks related to climate change, does accomplish a horizontal coordination between public works and disaster risk reduction in the territory. For what regards planning, it can be realized in a coordinated manner among different departments, but as far as implementation is concerned, the governance model uses separate bodies to deal with climate change issues.

Even though it can present some obstacles, there is a certain amount of **coordination and dialogue among the different sectors of the public administration**. IntBZ_01 has confirmed that this is a common practice of Bolzano public administration, and such exchange of information is realized through **informal and formal practices**. It was stated that “it is common practice to collaborate between different departments and administrations” and it is driven by will and sensibility rather than legally established practices. For example, the institutional stakeholder of the spatial planning (IntBZ_01) affirmed that the spatial planning department is participating in an informal roundtable which was instituted with the *Agenzia per la tutela del clima* since this office is implementing a renewable energy sources plan (photovoltaic).

However, there are also formal means of coordination, such as the establishment of **commissions that are instituted by sectoral laws** (for example, *legge provinciale 17 del 2017*) with regard to the evaluation of plans and projects, where it is expected that the evaluation is both at planning and project level, which involves the cooperation of different offices. In addition, it was stated (IntBZ_01) that it is difficult to distinguish between environment, nature and landscape: what may be beneficial for the environment, can be very negative for the landscape or for nature itself in terms of biodiversity. So coordination between the *Agenzia per l’Ambiente* and provincial departments that deal with nature and landscape is fundamental, because there must be a point of union between these sustainability aspects in the broad sense. Again, in terms of formal coordination, the province (represented by other subdivisions) is an active part of the Alpine Convention, of the EUSALP projects etc.: here obviously the role of lead actor belongs to the *Agenzia per l’Ambiente*.

Other stakeholders, both institutional and from the civil society, have stressed **that horizontal coordination happens also at the level of municipalities**, and not only at the provincial level and that this form of horizontal coordination seems more efficient than the provincial one (for example, via the [Patto dei Sindaci](#) initiative) (IntBZ_02; IntBZ_06; IntBZ_11). IntBZ_12 clarified the role of municipalities and their coordination with the Provincial administration. IntBZ_12 affirmed that “Surely the municipalities are the first point of reference for citizens, often they are the ones that operationalize concrete actions. Municipalities are at the forefront in energy efficiency or in the attempt to develop renewable sources. We have meeting points with them especially with regard to public lighting because we have incentives ad hoc. We also coordinate with them for what regards district heating. I can say that **there is not a formal procedure** for which there is a continuous active exchange with the municipalities. The consortium of municipalities is always invited when there are events, new laws or whatever, and they must always express their opinion. This is done at the level of individual administrative measures. For example, on the new climate plan there will be a meeting with municipalities where they will give their contributions. The decision-making process is the same as for all other stakeholders in the sense that **in the end the final decision belongs to the provincial government** which is democratically elected”.

Horizontal coordination happens also between the public administration, **inhouse societies** and private actors. Some important private stakeholders, for example those that deal with tourism, are in contact with politics and administration. The technical expert interviewed (IntBZ_03) affirmed that the dialogue with private stakeholders is necessary when it comes to energy sustainability because of the relevant economic incentives attached to this theme. Also, there is constant dialogue between the

provincial administration and *CasaClima* since the building industry is important for private stakeholders and for mitigation and adaptation to climate change.

According to the civil society interviewee (IntBZ_04) **the existence of many sectoral plans also involves many assessors**: the water plan involves electricity, water supply, health of citizens, fish, rivers, so it involves a lot of administrative bodies, and of course they have to find a balance and a compromise. This type of coordination requires an internal governance where one or more functionaries are the reference persons for sustainable development (IntBZ_07). They have a monthly and bimonthly meetings organized by the Consultant for Sustainability at the Europe, Innovation, Research and Communication Department in order to coordinate among cross-cutting issues. The role of the Consultant, in this sense, can be defined as “moderator” (IntBZ_07). In addition to these meetings, there are the so-called "summer workshops" where the consultant has meetings and three-hour workshops with about twenty administrative offices, and not only with the manager of sustainability, but also with all managers. Other formalized processes concern the internal stakeholders, such as one with science experts, university, municipalities and citizens.

Another important issue for the horizontal coordination is the **interplay between the water sector and energy** (IntBZ_06). The management of water resources is closely related to energy in this sense, because there is also a whole set of rules for the protection of water bodies that are subject to contentious practices for water use. Usually priority is given to drinking and irrigation. This is evident in the fact that water and hydroelectric originally were two separate offices until the end of 2018. After the merging of the two offices, the name was changed into the “sustainable water management office”. Furthermore, the institutional interviewee added that informal coordination is evident in the context of the preparation of legislative acts or proposals for deliberation. But then this coordination is always expressed in a formal way, and this process is inserted in the texts of the deliberations, so we know what are the administrative offices that were called to give their opinion and what was the outcome of the opinion. However, “it is obvious that before having a formal opinion, there is also a whole series of informal talks or reports preceding or in any case forming part of the scope of the deliberation” (IntBZ_06).

The other institutional stakeholder of space planning confirmed that there is **strong horizontal cooperation between its department, transportation and agriculture** (IntBZ_10) since they are the main actors involved in the sustainability strategy. This dialogue between different departments takes places in the *Giunta*.

Finally, the civil society stakeholder (IntBZ_11) affirmed that, in their opinion, there is not a good coordination among the different provincial administrations. He supported this claim by highlighting the fact that while horizontal coordination is promoted in the Climate Plan and the *Agenzia* tries to be an important coordination point, **however the interviewee did not witness a true engagement among different departments. On the contrary, they should be united in an integrated approach to climate change**. The interviewee (IntBZ_11) further supported this argument by affirming that in regions like Emilia Romagna or Piedmont the administrations have developed integrated databases for energy planning, while in the Province of Bolzano citizens and other stakeholders must ask and compare data coming from a variety of different actors (such as distributors, the *Agenzia*, the municipality office). If this work were done in a coordinated way by a regional or provincial body, the work would be much easier, and all data collection would also be more transparent. Another interesting aspect that prevents a real coordination is **the conflict of interests between different councillors (*assessorati*)**, for example with regard to the use of soils (e.g., agriculture v. spatial planning or hydroelectric). However, the interviewee IntBZ_08 expressed that the **governance model in this aspect is rather top-down**, because the sectoral experts have the necessary knowledge to understand implications in terms of funding, or other measures that can be opposed from important local stakeholders. In fact, the interviewee IntBZ_08 thinks that “What remains of the climate plan at

the level of measures, is always a compromise, because there will always be conflicts of objectives or interests, sometimes even within the provincial administration, but especially when all external stakeholders are involved in the decision-making progress”.

1.2.2. COORDINATION (VERTICAL)

The significance of the EU and international legislation and policy

Since the Bolzano is an Autonomous Province, it can directly transpose EU legislation in the territory. This aspect makes the EU and Bolzano legislation directly connected, as evidenced by the interviews. The political institutional interviewee (IntBZ_02) has the perception that **EU policies are not directly addressed in the political debate, they are rather a matter for more technical /legislative procedures**, especially for what regards agriculture, tenders and public procurement (*appalti*).

The institutional interviewee from the **water sector** (IntBZ_06) affirmed that the European directives have been gradually implemented both by national legislation and also by the provincial administration of Bolzano, for example regarding the **water charges**. In this sense, the **polluter pays principle** has been applied so that the calculation of the water charge has been revolutionized and, for the first time, it is taken into account not only the quantities of water that are utilized, but also the period during the year when the water has been utilized. Those who use the water for a longer period (even using the same amount of water) will pay a greater amount than those who instead make a more limited use in time. The other principle that has been applied with the latest regulations of last year is that of the coverage of costs, so the funds that are collected through water charges of non-hydroelectric concessions, will cover the costs for the upgrading of water courses and, in part, the optimization of irrigation systems. As far as the water sector is concerned, there has certainly been a great deal in the introduction of the EU directives, such as the Water Directive, which, in any case, has given importance to the sustainability compared to the previous legislation and which, gradually, was then acquired by national and provincial legislation.

According to the institutional spatial planning stakeholder (IntBZ_07), both the 2015 Paris Agreement and the 17 SDGs have been a milestone. At the Provincial level, the program of the legislature 2018-23, was introduced by the premise that “the *Giunta* is committed to the 17 SDGs...”. This close relationship between EU and international objectives is also due to the fact that the Autonomous Province, in certain areas, can **directly transpose the European directives**, and this obviously allows us to do so with a certain autonomy and in order to take into account the best possible peculiarities of our territory (IntBZ_08). But in this aspect it is indispensable to have a dialogue with national institutions or local stakeholders at the provincial level.

Finally, the civil society stakeholder (IntBZ_11) has noted that there is an [office](#) at the provincial level that is in charge of dealing with the EU directives and policies, and therefore an **institutional coordination** that works at the vertical level, especially when it comes to the attraction of EU funding for initiatives that deal with sustainability and climate change.

Conflicts between the national State and the Autonomous Province

The technical expert (IntBZ_03) shared the impression that national legislation, “since we are an Autonomous province, is always applied in a somewhat ‘autonomous’ way”. The Autonomous Province’s policies sometimes seems more advanced compared to national policies on climate change and environment. Certainly, in some areas this can be considered true because of the cooperation with countries on the northern borders, such as Austria [see section on cross border cooperation] but

sometimes, according to IntBZ_03, this feature is just apparent and it is not indicative of a true commitment to environmental policies.

The institutional interviewee of the water sector (IntBZ_06) affirmed that **the State has sometimes challenged some provincial laws**, parts of laws or even articles of provincial rules which were found to go against national law [but more research is needed to check if this has happened with regard to environmental laws].

The institutional interviewee of the energy sector (IntBZ_08) believes that the provincial institutions have an excellent relationship with the various levels of administration and with the State, so as to create the regulatory and legislative framework that serves for the implementation of all measures. However, the interviewee did not want to hide that **sometimes the administration of the Province is not fully happy with the national laws**, because sometimes they are too complicated.⁸

Cross-border cooperation

There are cooperation mechanisms in place between **the Autonomous Province and Austria** for what regards environmental protection (IntBZ_04). Such measures concern motorway transit and train rails. There is also the **Euregio** initiative which also coordinates tourism policies. However, the main problem is the heavy traffic in the Brennero motorway, insofar as 2.200.000 trucks go back and forth through the motorway every year, resulting in heavy pollution of valleys. The initiatives related to the cross-border cooperation are also present in the [Stage A folders](#), in the section “cross-cutting”.

1.2.3. LEADERSHIP

Political Leadership

The main political actor for the integration of climate change policy is the **Giunta Provinciale** (Provincial Government) (IntBZ_04). The President of the *Giunta*, together with other colleagues (the councillors) sets the priorities for the entire legislature, and then are constantly monitored, revised and adapted, especially in the weekly meetings of the Giunta. This is the core from where decisions are made, altogether with the regulatory level with the Provincial Council. Until a few years ago, climate change was the prerogative of a single party, while now almost all parties recognise the importance of policies for sustainability and, undertake to improve the quality of the environment and people’s lives in this regard (IntBZ_10).

The situation of the Autonomous province of Bolzano is quite peculiar, since the same party has been governing in the last 50-60 years (IntBZ_02; IntBZ_04). Therefore, the political programme of such party can be directly found on their website. The institutional interviewee (IntBZ_02) affirmed that at the moment, the Environment department (*Assessorato all’Ambiente*) is held by a member of the League party (Lega), whose party “is known for not being environmentalist”. They remarked also the fact that “in addition, here there is a **power stratification**. Since the [political] power is in the hands of the “Germans”, then give an *assessorato* in the hands of leader belonging to the Italian linguistic group is automatically weakening that department. This is the statement of reality, in fact many think that the spatial planning department is also the environmental *assessore*, but it is not. The *assessore* has not yet proposed a meaningful act to the Council, but this does not mean everything of course. I

⁸ The interviewee asserted that national laws are “beautiful from the academic-formal point of view... but of difficult implementation”. For example, the 110% bonus, “super-generous, super interesting and super complex”, needed two simplification decrees to make this initiative applicable. They concluded that “In this context perhaps the province could be much more flexible and much more streamlined at the provincial level, because perhaps we are even closer to full implementation, insofar the feedback that comes back from the field is immediate”.

see that the Governor himself takes lot of initiatives in the environmental sector. But he's also a neoliberal, so he is a bit on a double track. He receives the people of the Fridays for Future, he meets the associations, and it is also he who speaks in every talk of sustainability, so that our young people are fascinated, and at the same time disgusted, because they hear these statements, but they never see the facts. The founder of the Green Party, Langer, opened the debate around climate change and environmental issues”.

Important stakeholders at the administrative and inhouse level for climate change integration

Several stakeholders, when asked about administrative leadership for what regards climate change (IntBZ_01; IntBZ_02; IntBZ_03), affirmed that the main actor in this sense is the *Agenzia Provinciale per l'Ambiente e la tutela del Clima*. They evidenced that this office recently changed its denomination (including also “climate protection”) and this fact is very significative (IntBZ_01). Another important non-administrative actor is the inhouse society **CasaClima**, as a powerful agent of change in the energy and emissions sector. [to simplify, the political power is strictly connected to inhouse societies because these lasts are financed by public bodies]. CasaClima organizes a fair every year where they present information to private individuals around the importance of adopting a CasaClima certification for houses and buildings. At the fair, there is also an award ceremony (IntBZ_08).

Other stakeholders that were mentioned during the interviews are **Klaus Egger**, the Consultant for Sustainability at the Europe, Innovation, Research and Communication Department of the Province [public administration] (IntBZ_07), **Hans Glauber** [ecologist] (IntBZ_05), who was not in the public administration but is the founder of the Ökoinstitut, which is a private entity however had an important role in the organization of the “Dobbiaco talks” that fostered the integration of environmental issues at all levels in the Province. He also played an important role in creating the basis for CasaClima, and he created an open dialogue with political actors (IntBZ_05). **Flavio Ruffini**, the director of the *Agenzia*, has been mentioned as key stakeholder for the integration of climate change policies (IntBZ_03). At the same time, it has been highlighted that the cooperation between administration and the scientific research sector is important (IntBZ_03).

1.2.4. PARTICIPATION

Overview of participatory practices

The institutional interviewee (IntBZ_10) stated that “culturally, South Tyrol has always been characterized by a great attention to the territory with the participation of citizens”.

The first interviewee (IntBZ_01) rightfully affirmed that **participation means more than a mere slogan**, but an actual involvement and information. This is true for the new Climate Plan, which is now open to comments through an online procedure available on the *Agenzia*'s website.

More than one interviewed institutional stakeholder (IntBZ_02) affirmed that participation of citizens in decision making of climate change and environmental matters is much better realized at the level of municipalities, because they are felt “closer” by the population since they operate at the local level. In fact, at the level of municipality there is a direct involvement and participation of citizens within the Piano di Azione per l'Energia Sostenibile e il Clima (PAESC) (IntBZ_03). At the municipality level there is strong commitment and involvement of private stakeholders since they begin of the realization of the climate plan (IntBZ_03).

The IntBZ_03 affirmed that environmental associations are very active in the Province of Bolzano and at the municipality level, and the interviewee referred in particular to Fridays for Future and [Rete dell'Alto Adige per la Sostenibilità](#). Citizens have always been very active when an environmental conflict arose (for example, regarding the construction of the airport and the Val Pusteria Road). However, the interviewee registered a drop in attention in environmental matters when a problem seems to have been resolved. The civil society interviewee (IntBZ_04) provided an interesting description of the Fridays for Future. According to the interviewee (IntBZ_04): “Fridays for Future are something special: they don't tell you what to do! While we, historical environmentalists, were trying to provide solutions such as ‘no incinerator, but there are other systems instead of incinerators’, we studied them and proposed them... [...]. Fridays for Future does not make proposals, they just say ‘we are the future, you have to do something!’, and I think this is also very correct: you have the scientists, the technicians, etc., you have to do something, but this something must be serious and incisive”.

The institutional interviewee (IntBZ_07) asserted that there are **two different participation processes that will take place starting in 2022**: 1. “participation mix” which concerns the existing stakeholders; 2. Participation process with citizens and population. This last process is realized through a web site for information and workshops, plus a static tool for the collection of citizens' opinions. With regard to the effectiveness of participation processes regarding the Climate Plan, the interviewee answered: “You have to evaluate and understand whether the opinion is only of an individual or it represents the thought of many. What I know from the experience of the previous climate plan is: what is easy to integrate, is integrated without evaluating how many people really have that opinion... and when it becomes problematic, you have to start to assess how many people have that opinion. For this reason, it is important that the population is part of certain networks because then it is no longer just the opinion of an individual, but that of network”.

The institutional interviewee of IntBZ_12 underlined the important function of participation in the definition of the Climate Plan: “the climate plan process is participatory because we want choices to be shared and also known. The political will is to involve as much as possible of the population in the implementation of these measures. Unfortunately - or fortunately - we are living two momentous occasions: the pandemic and climate change. But even the pandemic shows how important it is that strategies are shared in order to avoid a social rift. This phase of consultation is followed by other phases of direct meetings with stakeholders. What I do know is that then all the contributions collected will be analyzed by a committee with political and scientific actors. In the end, the final decision is taken by the *Giunta*. I do not write the criteria, but in my opinion some may be a criterion of feasibility even at the level of economic resources, but not by doing so I am only assumptions. It is also important to provide the policy with an estimate of the financial resources needed to achieve the objective that is being set. At the moment, many financial and even human resources are being distracted by the ongoing pandemic”.

Finally, the civil society interviewee (IntBZ_11) talked about the organization *Patto per il Futuro* which was created also with the view to involve citizens with a broader spectrum of information [compared to the instruments already available]. He affirmed: “We plan to set up a new body, along the lines of what is happening in Austria, where binding advisory bodies have been set up. What we want to say via the initiative *Patto per il Futuro* is that participation is good, but it depends on how it is done: it is not enough to make a public presentation, we must also initiate procedures that make it binding”.

Sectoral participatory processes

According to an institutional interviewee (IntBZ_02), the new **law on spatial planning**, which entered into force in 2017, provides some **mechanisms for participation**. This is due to the fact that

spatial planning measures have a consequence on the organization of the territory, and hence require an involvement of the population.

With regard to water measures (IntBZ_06), the institutional interviewee stated that such measures are enshrined in **sectoral plans**, such as the plan on water protection at the provincial level, as well as the water management plan, which is a plan that is drawn up at the level of basin authorities. In such cases the final plan is subject to the publication of the draft plan and, after a process of about 6 months, the plan is made public and comments are possible from all stakeholders (private or public authorities). This applies however only to the plans of a “certain importance”, plans that can run for five/seven years, and then are adjusted as soon as this period of validity is over. As for the legislation - made through laws and resolutions - there is no path of participation of civil society (generally). “The provincial administration proposes the resolution in the form it considers most appropriate, but then the resolution is approved by a political body that is the provincial government, which - of course - has within it the ability to discuss this proposal with the stakeholders it represents, because obviously it is the *Giunta* that, at the political level, decides whether the proposal made by a sectoral office (also from a technical point of view) can be good or not, and certainly, from the political point of view, there is a confrontation with the relevant stakeholders... but not directly with civil society as far as I know.” (IntBZ_06).

In the transportation sector, for the development of the bus timetable, in 2020 it was created a platform for citizens to submit their requests and observations (IntBZ_05).

Online instruments and tools of participation

Please refer to [Klimaland](#).

Highlighted criticalities

The civil society interviewee, with regard to the theme of participation, stated: “**I don’t know if civil society can influence these decisions** [climate change plans etc] - I don’t think so, because in my experience we’ve never been able to get anything out of public administrations - so the leadership tends to work alone. Let me give you an example, since we are talking about participation, also it is relevant this issue here: last year a group with provincial funding was born whose name translated means ‘pact for the future’ which is a network in South Tyrol seeking to push the 17 sustainable development objectives. This group has now reached over a hundred associations that participate in this thing, and when it was born at the beginning there was an online meeting (because we were in full Covid period) which was also attended by the president of the Province who told us clearly ‘do whatever you want, do whatever you think, look for incredible solutions... but remember that then we decide!’. The decisions are made there [at the administration level], [...] this is the consideration that there is about civil society, or to the fact that civil society can provide some indications; whenever we could give guidance on anything (the last is the Water Park project) we were not considered, now have the problem that at the Water Park the aquifer has invaded the spaces (we told them they were too close to the aquifer)... But they needed to have 800 parking lots, and to have 800 parking lots they had to go down [in the underground] with three floors, now they’re inside the aquifer... but the decision was made there” (IntBZ_04).

The institutional/political stakeholder (IntBZ_02) stated that “**The concept of participation is not rooted here.** [in order to understand why] It is necessary to know that a party has ruled here for eighty years and often the participation of citizens is misunderstood as ‘sharing [opinions] within the party’. One thing that we did [the political party of the interviewee] five years ago we proposed a law for direct democracy and participation. Another colleague and I were new to the party, and we initiate a first participatory process. So, we asked, ‘how come in cities there is no participation?’ and one person answered ‘how come there is not! Just enter the committee [of the political party] and participate’.

There I understood how participation is here: if you participate in the party then you participate! This is to understand how it works, because then when you have an evening of participation in reality it is an informative evening: come, see the slides, this is the law... and then the presenter asks at 10 o'clock at night 'there are comments, there are questions?'. And this was the evening of participation. [...] but you have to know [what participation means], otherwise you misunderstand it with a PowerPoint with questions”.

Finally, the civil society interviewee IntBZ_11 highlighted some similar critical problems with regard to participation: “if you ask me if institutions want to promote participation, both on the climate level and the sustainability strategy, I tell you that it has to be verified. Some look at the Fridays For Future [as a positive example of participation] ... but in fact my perception is that **especially on the structural choices, young people are not involved, valued and/ or informed.** Maybe Fridays for Future asks for a target like: zero emissions and zero environmental impact... but then in fact they don't know how to get there, because they are often not within the technical-structural choices that make decisions for the territory. When I hear a young man saying that in South Tyrol we produce twice the energy we consume, I stay a bit speechless, because the energy we produce is not only mine or yours, but the energy we produce can also go to the other side of Italy! Evidently there is a lack of information and involvement also from this point of view... and there are no structured bodies [that aim at promoting effective participation].”

1.2.5. INFORMATION

Nature of the existing information mechanisms and processes

Generally, and from what emerged from the interviews, **information and participation are strongly interrelated.** Sometimes interviewees were answering questions related to participation with processes related to information, and vice versa. It could be assumed this is because only when citizens are well informed – on climate change, in this case – they can meaningfully participate in the decision-making of environmental and climate plans. But even the fact that the stakeholders were not able to make a clear distinction between the two processes is something that can be reflected upon.

The interviews evidenced that most communication and information can be found **online**, especially in the past two years because of the Covid pandemic.

The Klimaland website already mentioned above in the report, is one of the major tools where information on the climate plan is provided and where citizens can participate in the policy process (IntBZ_11).

The most important information provider with regard to climate change and environment is the *Agenzia* (IntBZ_10; IntBZ_06). The *Agenzia* informs the population through different campaigns, such as the importance of going to work by bike, how to recycle domestic garbage, and also about the importance of buying locally produced food (IntBZ_10). Important communication is made through the webpages of the *Agenzia*, followed by a campaign of information at the provincial level (via social media) which involves (in some cases) also the *Agenzia* in case of particular initiatives (IntBZ_06).

The Sustainable Development strategy [has been officially presented](#) to the public by the *Giunta* and the public administration on 23 July 2021 (IntBZ_07).

Overall availability and transparency of information

The civil society interviewee (IntBZ_04) provided an **example from real facts about the procedure to obtain environmental information from public administration**. There is a procedure to ask for information to the *Agenzia*, based on a form that must be filled in by the person who is interested in having information. The interviewee asserted that in order to fill this report, “you need to speak the same language of the administration [I assume a technical language]”. They also affirmed that having such information can be difficult because sometimes 1. The administration is scared about giving environmental information because they do not know what citizens will do with the data; 2. They don’t have the information you are looking for (IntBZ_04 made an example of this sort: they wanted to know the level of polluting agents in the air of certain areas, but the public administration provided just aggregate information, so it was impossible to determine the level of pollution of a single area); 3. They reply that information is already available on the website so they do not send information, or some information is kept secret (for example, according to IntBZ_04, health information such as cancer rate in local areas is impossible to have). In general, the procedure to obtain environmental information is not straightforward.

A similar procedure to obtain information has been described by the institutional interviewee of the **water sector** (IntBZ_06). They stated that to access the environmental data it is necessary to fill in a form that is present in the web pages of the *Agenzia* and it must then be submitted to the administrative office of the environment which then forwards it to the office interested in the application for those specific data. The data are then processed and sent back in compliance with the privacy rules to applicants. Many environmental data are present in the geobrowser of the province that are systems that show the provincial system on which offices can upload information that describes the quality of water, the land registry of sources etc. The interviewee added that “Obviously, the request for information by the citizen must be justified, but generally, yes, environmental data are public data.”⁹ According to the civil society interviewee (IntBZ_11), what is missing at the information level is an “energy facilitator”, an officer who helps non-technical people to deal with the situation of energy efficiency and climate mitigation.

Communication strategy(ies): in person and online

As mentioned above in this report, the *Agenzia* is the main channel through which environmental information is made available.

For what regards the water sector, a general communication to the public is made by the *Agenzia* webpage, then an information campaign is made at the provincial sector that sometimes involves the participation of the *Agenzia*.

For what regards the transportation sector, the institutional interviewee of this sector (IntBZ_05) confirmed that their communication strategy works in conjunction with other actors, for example electric cars producers. They have created in various places in South Tyrol the opportunity to test these cars. They are currently participating in a European project where we raise awareness with **the hashtag #mobilitygreen**, and they are creating various initiatives and challenges, such as “bike to work”. The interviewee added that for the elaboration of the provincial plan on the cycling mobility, they have invited many associations and other stakeholders to participate in some workshops (in this case online because of Covid) in order to contribute to the establishment of the initiative, to give suggestions.

⁹ In Italy, the request must be justified by an “environmental interest”.

The technical expert of IntBZ_03, asserted that their office has promoted several **campaigns on the CasaClima certificate**, for example through dedicated workshops both for citizens and technical experts, but the participation level is not very high.

The Ökoinstitut (IntBZ_02) is doing a lot in terms of information since it works for the initiative ComuneClima. The interviewee also affirmed that a lot has to be done with regard to the **transparency of food production chains**. The Green party, in conjunction with the opposition party, has proposed a law on the transparency of animal derived food information in school cafeterias, which was recently approved. Now the challenge will be to obtain the same information transparency standard in restaurants.

The institutional interviewee of the energy sector (IntBZ_08) reported that a [CO2 calculator online](#) is available, by which people can understand the ecological impact of their actions and lifestyle. The respondent also stated that much information is available on the Klimaland website, that is a good example of a communication strategy that wishes to bring information to citizens. Nowadays the web is the main source of environmental information, since the “informative evenings” organized by ComuneClima that were happening at the municipalities level have been cancelled because of the pandemic (IntBZ_08). Finally, the interviewee highlighted the fact that an information desk for municipalities and public administrations was inaugurated in March 2020, which provides in a single location all information services regarding technical advice, incentives and related energy saving information.

Under 30 as a target group

With regard to information campaigns for under-30 citizens, it has been argued that governmental institutions do meet youngsters from Fridays for Future, as already expressed elsewhere in this report (IntBZ_09).

Information campaigns on climate change and the environment are also provided in schools (IntBZ_02; IntBZ_08). In particular, CasaClima offers the initiative “**ScuolaClima**”, through which they wish to involve young people and their families about the importance of having a sustainable lifestyle, and provide them with theoretical and educational tools around energy saving, mobility, and sustainable food (IntBZ_03).

The civil society interviewee (IntBZ_04) asserted that they do not know about any informational campaign on environment and climate change, apart from official press releases.

1.2.6 FUNDING¹⁰

The analysis of the provincial public expenditure on climate change cannot be separated from an analysis of the division of competences, given the instrumental nature of the former in relation to the latter. Put differently, public expenditure reflects the political dimension of subnational autonomy. In practice it is predominantly affected by the exercise of the administrative function. A major problem in this respect is the fact that climate change policies are integrated within different sectoral policies in which climate change is in some cases a direct goal, while in others it is an indirect consequence of the exercise of activities aimed at satisfying other primary interests. The same dynamic is reflected on the expenditure side (IntBZ_01, IntBZ_05, IntBZ_06, IntBZ_07).

As a rule, provincial resources are distributed among the various administrative subdivisions (*ripartizioni*); among these, the ones with the most direct link to the fight against climate change are **the provincial Agency for environment and climate protection** (hereinafter Environment Agency), and the civil protection (*protezione civile*) which is responsible for dealing with catastrophic events, e.g., danger zone plans (IntBZ_01). However, **there are many other administrative subdivisions/provincial agencies that in the exercise of their functions indirectly intersect climate change**. Landscape planning and protection, energy, and public transports are all sectors of

¹⁰ This section has been authored by Alice Valdesalici.

relevance in this respect (IntBZ_01, IntBZ_05, IntBZ_07). The same applies to the Agency Casa Clima and the Green Mobility initiative: climate protection is not their priority, but this is achieved through the implementation of policies within their respective competences (IntBZ_03, IntBZ_05). Because of this **fragmentation**, it is not possible to give a clear account either of the total expenditure for climate protection, or of its evolution over time. Not surprisingly, respondents disagree when answering the question about the evolution of the resources over time. Some even have no idea at all. Overall, it emerges that **the most common measures are grants to individuals or enterprises, and tax benefits**. If the rule is that the expenditure is covered also in this **field through the general provincial resources** in the amount yearly determined by the provincial executive, **water charges are in this sense an exception**. Pursuant to law 10/2019, from 2020 onwards the funds from water charges are earmarked to improve the quality of watercourses (half of them) and to optimize water installations (the other half). All in all, these can be considered adaptation measures to combat the effects of climate change. The total amount obviously depends on the revenue collected, which from 2023 on are estimated to amount between EUR 3 and 4 million per year (IntBZ_06).

Over the last ten years, **the Environment Agency has allocated an average of 10 million per year, divided between renewable energy sources, district heating and energy efficiency**. The budget has remained fairly stable over time thanks to the attention shown by politicians to these issues (IntBZ_12). However, as mentioned above, **there are also other non-quantifiable resources**, such as subsidies in the transport sector (e.g., electric car bonus or other mobility bonuses).

The funds managed by the Environment Agency are transfers from the provincial budget. The priorities and the amount of the transfers to the Agency are defined by the provincial Executive after consultation with all sectoral departments. The resources are then distributed among the various offices/sectors of the Agency and from here they are then partly used for operating expenses and partly allocated to individuals and businesses on the basis of criteria and objectives set by the Executive (IntBZ_12). The Agency has its own budget that shall be either published on the institutional website or made available upon request.

The interviews have also revealed that **one of the most heavily funded sectors is public transport**. **Energy is another area** in which the Province invests a lot. In particular, many biomasses and district heating plants have been financed. Only Bolzano uses the incinerator, while all other municipalities use biomass (though mostly imported). This also shows a certain attention to climate (IntBZ_04).

Other sectors such as building, agriculture and mobility are also important (IntBZ_07). Examples in this respect are the incentives for heat pumps and photovoltaic that have been increased from 50 to 80%, the electric mobility incentives and the fact that South Tyrolean can combine national and provincial contributions (IntBZ_07). In fact, individuals and companies located in South Tyrol are also entitled to access national subsidies likewise all Italian citizens (IntBZ_12).

Other resources come from the European Union. European funds are managed by the provincial administration and not by the Environment Agency. In relation to these, however, the Environment Agency offers technical advice for the evaluation of projects (IntBZ_12).

The EU has also another role. In this respect it shall be noted that a share of the provincial budget has been allocated to the financing of environmental-related projects for different reasons. On the one hand, on the belief that investing in the environment and consequently in the fight against climate change **is a good investment for the future**, as it can bring advantages not only in terms of the environment but also in terms of employment and health. On the other hand, because of the European Union. First, **European funding requires in most of the cases a co-financing by the receiving authority**, second, because **the province follows the European trend** whereby richer territories tend to spend more on environmental-oriented policies (IntBZ_04). The same shift from environmental protection to climate change strategy has taken place following impulses at the European level. Energy and climate planning are required to member states by the EU and this has a knock-on effect on the provincial level (IntBZ_11)

A few critical issues have emerged from the interviews. These concern the importance, among others, to **keep policies up-to-date** through evaluation tools (IntBZ_01), to introduce **tools for**

assessing whether the economic measures have the desired impact on climate protection (IntBZ_07), and to involve individuals and stakeholders in the **improvement of the procedures for granting incentives or contributions** (IntBZ_05). It has also been stressed the **total lack of investment in environmental protection by the private sector**, which in fact often goes in the opposite direction (IntBZ_02). Finally, what is lacking is an over-arching vision, which could also include the assignment in the budget of **resources specifically targeted to the fight against climate change, or at least a document that gives a holistic view** of it and acknowledges the resources spent on the various measures, so that it would also be easier to assess their impact (IntBZ_11).

1.3. CROSS-CUTTING TENDENCIES

Several stakeholders confirmed that **the integration of climate change policies at the provincial level is not a straightforward process**, and sometimes obstacles prevent a rightful application of such policies. Such obstacles are not only legal, but also political, social and economic.

For example, the technical expert interviewed (IntBZ_03), affirmed that in the realization of climate change policies there are several elements, the political one for example where consent is needed from all the different forces, and reaching a functional compromise is not so simple because **some private interests are not always in line with these objectives**. The interviewee suggested that perhaps the legal development must start simultaneously from the top, with the laws, and from the bottom with the population or the consumers (for example, tourists).¹¹

Another area where obstacles arise concerns the relationship between the laws at the national level, and the competencies of the Autonomous Province. This aspect emerged in IntBZ_08, which showed that in those areas where the Autonomous province of Bolzano has primary competences, however, **it is always necessary to be careful to be in line with state legislation and of course also with the principles of the European framework**, and this requires a constant effort. Another example are tax allowances and incentives at national level are always incentives where national requirements must be met.

This **clash in national and provincial matters** is also evident in the sector of the photovoltaic, insofar as the territories which should be dedicated to this purpose on the one hand clash with the interests of agriculture stakeholders, or on the other hand cause speculation whereas the government prescribes to use unproductive areas for photovoltaic installation, and then the Province labels as “unproductive” territories that were, originally, productive (IntBZ_09).

There are also **competing interests at the EU level and at the provincial level when it comes to food labelling**, regarding the origin of raw ingredients. The EU regulation is much more permissive, while citizens at the provincial level ask political parties to intervene regarding the food labelling (IntBZ_02).¹²

¹¹ For example, regarding tourists, the interviewee made this example: tourists notice that if there is too much traffic in the streets is a great disadvantage, and therefore they ask the possibility of reaching both hotels and places that they want to visit by sustainable transport. In other cases, tourist would like an environment that is not only sustainable on paper but that can be experienced. Many ask for this authenticity, which is not just a label or a promise but a fact that can be noticed in person (Int_3).

¹² This is not directly related to climate change, however it is well known that intensive farming is one of the major causes of polluting agents in the atmosphere. In this sense, the origin of raw materials in meat-based food comes into play when we talk about climate change.

Finally, the civil society stakeholder (IntBZ_04) affirmed that **the climate change policies available at present are not generally incisive enough, and changes are happening in a way that is too slow.** According to this interviewee we will not be able to contain the global warming below 2 degrees Celsius, the interests are too big and too deep-rooted, even in the mentality of the province and municipalities: here the interests are smaller, here we do not have large vehicle industries... but we have many small interests that force us to limit our work, which results in a very slow process when it comes to climate change policy integration at the Provincial level.

2. TRENTO

Expert-Interviews data in the Autonomous Province of Trento (IT):

<p>Number of conducted interviews: 11 Institutional/Administration: 7 Civil Society: 3 Technical expertise: 1</p>
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TRENTO INTERVIEWS - INTERVIEWEE PROFILES

INTERVIEW-CODE (extended)	INTERVIEW-CODE (short in text)	TYPE
IntTN_01_Administration_Transport	IntTN_01	Institutional
IntTN_02_Technical expert_Spatial Planning	IntTN_02	Institutional
IntTN_03_Trento_Civil Society_Transport	IntTN_03	Civil society
IntTN_04_Trento_Political_Cross-cutting	IntTN_04	Institutional
IntTN_05_Administration_Energy	IntTN_05	Institutional
IntTN_06_Trento_Civil Society_Cross-cutting	IntTN_06	Civil society
IntTN_07_Trento_Administration_Cross-cutting	IntTN_07	Institutional
IntTN_08_Trento_Administration_Water	IntTN_08	Institutional
IntTN_09_Trento_Administration_Spatial Planning	IntTN_09	Institutional
IntTN_10_Trento_Civil Society_Cross-cutting	IntTN_10	Civil society
IntTN_11_Trento_Political_Cross-cutting	IntTN_11	Institutional

Glossary used in this report:

Name	Description	Website
<i>Giunta Provinciale</i>	See Bolzano report	http://www.giunta.provincia.tn.it/
<i>Assessore/Assessorato</i>	See Bolzano report	
<i>Agenzia per la tutela dell'ambiente e del clima</i>	APPA is an organizational structure of the Autonomous Province of Trento - created on the model of the regional agencies and the Agency of the Autonomous Province of Bolzano - endowed with organizational, administrative, technical and accounting autonomy. It responds to the need to ensure the presence of autonomous technical bodies throughout the national territory. Starting from 2020, the Agency has also acquired new competences and skills in the field of climate	http://www.appa.provincia.tn.it/

	change, urban waste and the 2030 Agenda for sustainable development.	
<i>Agenzia provinciale per le risorse idriche e l'energia</i>	APRIE is the agency in charge of the regulation and government of policies and strategies inherent to water and energy at the Provincial level. In terms of climate change, it is responsible for the planning of mitigation measures.	http://www.energia.provincia.tn.it/
<i>Strategia provinciale per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile</i>	SproSS is the Provincial strategy for sustainable development. It identifies 20 provincial sustainability objectives that represent the heart of the strategy. They are grouped into 5 areas and indicate the paths to follow in order to build a sustainable Trentino.	https://agenda2030.provincia.tn.it/Trentino-2030/SproSS
<i>Strategia Provinciale di Mitigazione e Adattamento ai Cambiamenti Climatici</i>	The Strategy is the reference tool to guide the administrative action of the Province to contain the ongoing warming and counteract the negative impacts of climate change. The action develops in two directions: that of mitigation, aimed at progressively reducing emissions of greenhouse gases, and that of adaptation, which aims to decrease the vulnerability of natural systems, such as forests and ecosystems, and socio-economic ones.	
<i>Conferenza Stato-Regioni</i>	The State-Regions Conference is the collegial seat useful that promotes cooperation between the activities of the State and that of the Regions and Autonomous Provinces. It usually meets every two weeks. It represents the privileged forum for political negotiations between central and regional administrations.	https://www.statoregioni.it/it/

2.1. SECTORAL OVERVIEWS

2.1.1. TRANSPORT

Main initiatives and strategies mentioned during the interview:

- The development of transport and of cycle lanes and cycle routes - 2012
- Piano Provinciale per la Mobilità Elettrica, Provincial Plan for Electric Mobility – 2015
- Legge provinciale 6/2017: Law on sustainable mobility
- PEAP (Piano Energetico Ambientale Provinciale) - 2021

Overview¹³

In the transport sector no plans are developed on the Italian national scale. State law, from the legislative decree n. 422/1997 onwards, has been more concerned with oversight of the bodies entrusted with providing public services than with questions of performance. At best, these were dealt with in relation to the most vulnerable categories of users (i.e. disabled individuals). There is, therefore, no normative structure that establishes the objectives that must be achieved. These fall instead under the umbrella of mobility plans and the **regulations of the individual regional or autonomous provinces' administrations**. Law n. 6/2017 (Law on sustainable mobility of the Provincia Autonoma di Trento: hereafter PAT) is to some extent an exception, in that it stipulates the types of objectives that are normally established in non-normative documents. With this law, an attempt was made to develop a middle ground between ideal standards and a genuine mobility plan. The law details priorities that are dealt with in non-normative documents in other regions. This has its benefits: i.e. it establishes development guidelines for a sustainable transport network. However, there is also a drawback: the demanding thresholds for sustainable transport risk becoming an aspiration, as it would be difficult to sanction those who do not respect the regulations. In relation to the Law on sustainable mobility (*Legge sulla Mobilità Sostenibile* in Italian), it is also interesting to note the existence of a legislation proposed by a citizen's committee, which developed from below, and which was fundamental in developing the final version of the law (for more details, see the 'Participation' section).

According to the accounts of all of those interviewed, **the transport sector is that which has undergone the greatest number of difficulties** (at least among those sectors studied in the project) in effectively integrating the fight against climate change into its action priorities. Interviewees from the provincial administration (both administrative and political figures), attribute this first and foremost to a **lack of funding and investment**. There was a gradual decrease in financing, mostly following the economic crisis of 2008 and in particular after 2010. This lack of investment can be interpreted in a negative sense (less investment leads to fewer possibilities to implement effective initiatives), but also in a partially positive sense: the fact that there is less money available made it essential to **rationalise, forcing administrations to envisage a panorama of public mobility that was not dependent on structural investments**. Positive examples of this approach were mentioned by political and administrative interviewees, such as the improvement works undertaken on the Valsugana and Trento-Malè lines, and the regulation of the traffic flow on the **Brenner Tunnel**: in all of these examples, significant improvements were achieved with few resources. This is also recognised by interviewees from civil society, who also agree that Trentino is at the forefront when it comes to the development of cycle trails and cycle tourism (e.g. the Val di Sole cycle trail). However, these interviewees, in particular IntTN_06 and IntTN_08, are more critical when it comes to the results that have been achieved in the transport sector as a whole, and lay the blame not only on a lack of funding but also a lack of political vision. According to IntTN_06, for example, public

¹³ <http://www.trasporti.provincia.tn.it/>

transport in Trentino is excellent when compared with the rest of Italy, however it is still somewhat lacking when compared with the transport system in the Autonomous Province of Bolzano.

The above mentioned difficulties should also be analysed considering a more general aspect: the fact that transport sector is more related to air pollution than to climate change (even if the two are strictly interrelated: e.g.: fossil fuels). An important contribution, mentioned for example in Int_7, is represented by the Air quality provincial plan 2018.

It is also interesting to note that these shortcomings are also recognised by the administrators themselves, unlike other sectors where it is more common for negative impressions to be expressed by members of civil society. Indeed, in some cases the situation is the exact opposite of that found in the other two sectors: Energy&Water and Spatial Planning. For example, one civil society interviewee (IntTN_10) recognized that the PAT has introduced quite a bit of legislation in recent years, in particular on **wider scale tourism** (e.g. the Adamello Brenta Park). The same interviewee also noted that this process has slowed in recent years, particular as far as some tourism mobility projects that were started but never concluded are concerned. Particular reference was made here to mobility on the mountain passes of the Dolomites, which is a problem in the summer and is clearly related to climate change.

In spite of the fact that the transport sector is that which has had the greatest problems in recent years, it is also the **sector that the PAT is focussing on the most in its attempts to reduce its climate impact in the coming years**. In fact, it must be underlined that, as stated by IntTN_05, the 5% difference that will raise the PAT's greenhouse gas emissions target for 2050 from a 50% to a 55% reduction, will mainly be achieved in the transport sector, specifically by encouraging the use of bicycles, public transport and shared transport. (All of these measures are contained in the PEAP – the energetic and environmental provincial plan: see next section). In addition to the obvious links with the energy sector, there is also an important link to spatial planning sector: adopting these measures will entail a radical change in how both the city and the province itself are conceived.

As is the case in other sectors, the **stimulus provided by the European Union** is described as being fundamental: according to one important political figure (IntTN_04), this is especially the case in relation to the construction of the Brenner Tunnel, which aims to reduce road traffic by shifting it to rail. On the other hand, IntTN_08 claims that the Brenner Tunnel will lead to a significant lack of funding for other works that he considers more important, and in particular for the transport links for small municipalities. According to a number of civil society interviewees, funding should be better allocated and made available more for small-scale works rather than major infrastructure projects. In contrast, IntTN_04 argues that for those with political responsibility the primary objective is to improve the tunnel as this will indirectly make it possible to achieve the objectives of larger scale plans and strategies, such as PEAP and Agenda 2030 (see next sections for details on these plans). The administrative and political interviewees also state that ancillary works are essential: in the city of Trento one million euros have already been invested in the construction of a bypass, which will be followed by routing the train line underground, while plans are also being developed for the Munich-Riva del Garda line.

Many interviewees (especially political figures and administrative staff) expressed a hope that the situation will improve thanks to funding provided by the Italian **Recovery Plan** (PNRR). On the contrary, civil society interviewees feared that such funding could be directed towards projects that would have a negative effect on the climate and to air quality more specifically.

In many of the interviews it was also noted that the **PAT is characterised by particular geographical challenges**, as it is 80% mountainous which makes **rail transport less efficient than**

road transport across large parts of the region. This does not mean that rail should be abandoned, but that more thought should be invested in deciding where exactly to construct new lines. What is more, as was underlined by a number of administrators, it is impossible to rely on profits from transport alone without significant levels of public funding. In spite of this, the rail network has doubled the number of passengers carried each year between 2005 and 2020, mainly due to the introduction of more rational and better performing models. What is mainly lacking is funding on a provincial level (the purchase of new trains, for example, falls on the provincial budget), as well as State funding.

A great deal of emphasis is placed on **change at the individual level and on the development of sustainable transport practices by citizens themselves** in an approach that is championed by administrators on the one hand as a means of increasing social innovation, while on the other hand it is criticised by members of civil society organisations as an attempt by politics to reduce its responsibilities and offload them onto citizens. IntTN_10 in particular refers to “degrowth” and to the fact that it is necessary to limit new construction as part of a wider discussion on limiting consumption: “the incentives linked to the green economy are a bit vague. Relying on things such as electric cars, wind turbines etc. has its limits”. Without specifically mentioning degrowth, IntTN_03 and IntTN_06 also raise similar issues in relation to the creation of an alternative development model, especially in relation to transport.

The budget of the transport department amounts to 150 million euro a year in management fund, 100 million euro to ensure the functioning of public transport (trains, buses, school buses, etc.), 50 million for construction, energy efficiency, electric transport, and bonuses.

2.1.2. ENERGY AND WATER

ENERGY

Main sectoral initiatives and strategies mentioned during the interview:

- Provincial law 10/2010, the so-called Legge Clima - 2010.
- Piano Provinciale per la Mobilità Elettrica, Provincial Plan for Electric Mobility - 2015
- PEAP 2021-2030 (Piano Energetico Ambientale Provinciale, Energetic and Environmental Provincial Plan) - 2008, 2013, 2021

Overview¹⁴

As was clearly outlined by one of the most important administrative figures involved in the energy sector (IntTN_05), who is also one of the main coordinators of the most recent PEAP (*Piano Energetico Ambientale Provinciale*, i.e. the main document employed by the PAT to regulate the energy sector, also reducing its impacts in terms of climate change), the energy question predates the emergence of climate change and has been a major issue since the 1973 oil crisis. There is a long history of planning in this area, dating back to the 80s and 90s, both at the international and at the local level. **Previously the main focus when discussing energy was on ensuring energy security and the provision of energy in the mountains and valleys.** It is only more recently (from 2010) that there has been a focus on the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. The term **climate change only began to be used after 2010.**

There have been three energy plans since 2005: in 2008, 2013 and 2021. The **PEAP is essentially the document that outlines in general terms the mitigation plans at the provincial level.** The development of the current PEAP began in 2018 with the signing of an accord between the University

¹⁴ <http://www.energia.provincia.tn.it/>

of Trento and the PAT. Subsequently an account of energy consumption for the years 2014-2016 was drawn up; on that basis possible scenarios were developed and in June 2021 the PEAP was approved. The PEAP is composed of 12 principal actions aimed at achieving a 55% reduction in emissions by 2030 (in line with the European Green Deal and new European Climate Law reduction targets). The 12 actions can be divided into three main areas of intervention: reducing energy consumption; identifying an efficient mix of energy sources; interdepartmental measures across various policy sectors. In addition to these general objectives, the PEAP also identifies a number of individual measures, ranging from energy production to making buildings more energy efficient. Previous versions of the document had always included objectives set by the European Commission and the Italian State, and indeed even went so far as to increase those objectives and achieve greater results. The initial draft of the 2021 PEAP, for example, had already set an objective of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 55% by 2030, which was only later introduced by the EU in 2021. On the other hand, as was outlined in one interview, “in Italy, the adoption of European directives related to energy has not taken place in suitable timeframes.... however, fortunately there is the possibility to legislate on a provincial level, skipping the State level and considering the European level directly” (IntTN_05). This holds above all for autonomous regions and provinces, and it is also an element that interviewees from other policy sectors agreed with.

According to the accounts of both experts and administrative staff, **the main driver in the various plans has always been mitigation measures. In the most recent version of the PEAP (2021), there has also been an increase in the number of adaptation measures.** However, as maintained by other interviewees, significant limits and obstacles survive/remain in effectively combatting climate change in the current politics conducted by the PAT: in particular, it was outlined that there is such a “scarce amount of renewable energy, that they only took into consideration solar panels and hydroelectric energy” (IntTN_11).

The previous PEAP, issued in 2013, was written by an external consultancy, and this undoubtedly produced coordination and participation dynamics that were very different from the 2021 PEAP, which was coordinated by APRIE (*Agenzia provinciale per le risorse idriche e l'energia*). In 2013 there was also a certain level of coordination and collaboration, however, this was limited to collecting opinions and observations. In contrast, according to one of the functionaries that personally took part in the **2021 PEAP**, in this latest version there was a **significant level of horizontal coordination between the various structures and departments of the PAT**. In any case, the PEAP is not solely an initiative of the provincial environmental department (*Assessorato* in Italian) and APRIE. There was constant collaboration: from agriculture to forestry, from business to the tourism sector. All of these sectors provided their contributions to achieve the common objective of reducing greenhouse gases emissions.

The 2021 PEAP is, furthermore, unusual when compared to the similar plans developed by other autonomous regions and provinces. It contains a specialist technical report, drawn up by scientific experts (FBK, Unitn, Fondazione Mach), with a dedicated section outlining the various possible scenarios that could be caused by climate issues. Some of these chapters were written by other provincial departments, with APRIE producing the majority. Based on this vertically integrated approach, a selection was made at the interdepartmental level by the heads of various departments. Moreover, the PEAP was produced at a particular time in which many initiatives are taking place, both at a strictly provincial, but also national and international level: the Recovery Plan, Agenda 2030, the Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation Plan, etc (more details on these initiatives in the next sections). As the PEAP had already been launched, it served as a benchmark on each of these themes, thus making it possible to also bring about horizontal coordination in each of these documents.

It must, however, be noted that there was a **lack of effective involvement from civil society associations** in the drawing up of the plan. Both the administrative sources and interviewees from civil society organisations attributed this to negative previous experiences which had led to a certain degree of mistrust and the impression that the parties were involved solely for appearances' sake. Nevertheless, IntTN_05 insisted that many of the observations that had been registered by the civil society associations were taken into account and that in spite of this they declined the opportunity to take part in public discussions on the plan. In their opinion, in this case the mistrust was ill-founded, as the observations were subsequently taken into consideration in an effective manner.

The sector which wastes the largest amount of energy in the PAT is the civil sector (43%): for this reason, according to some interviewees (IntTN_01, IntTN_04), **incentives and reforms do not require a large amount of investment, but rather careful resource management**. In the 2021 PEAP, for example, special measures were introduced in relation to the expansion of natural gas distribution network, electric cars and other similar incentives that do not require a large amount of public investment, but rather a cultural shift. Today a number of direct incentives exist (related to apartment blocks, electric cars, homes) that are organised in a vertical manner in each individual sector. In order for genuine change to come about, there needs to be a greater deal of coordination, as happened in the drafting of the 2021 PEAP. Also in this sector, as well as in transport sector, a **strong insistence is posed on the role of individuals and behavioural changes**.

In recent years it has become increasingly difficult to access finance mechanisms. At the start of the 2000s, grants were the principal financing instrument, however with the draining of provincial budgets there was a shift to financial engineering mechanisms. In the past the autonomous provinces were rich, and there was no need for alternative instruments to support energy efficiency drives: shrinking funds is another point that is shared with the interviews carried out in other policy sectors.

WATER

Main sectoral initiatives mentioned during the interviews:

- Piano di gestione generale dell'utilizzazione delle acque pubbliche - 2006
- Piano Tutela delle Acque (currently being updated; it will contain measurement guidelines that will make it possible to estimate the various scenarios brought about by climate change)

Overview

The Plan for the General Management and the Use of Public Water (*Piano di gestione generale dell'utilizzazione delle acque pubbliche*) was launched in 2006. The plan is organised along district lines. In Trentino there are two districts: one in which the water drains into the Po, and another in which it drains into the Adige and subsequently the Adriatic. According to IntTN_08, it is a plan that is largely characterised by the logic of the 2000s, when climate change was beginning to be discussed, but not to the extent that it is today. **Within the general Plan there are useful guidelines for the fight against climate change**. A good example of this is **water rationing**, especially for those sectors that consume the most water, in particular the agricultural sector.

In relation to the management of water it also emerged that there was a technical problem linked to the differing approaches taken by the Department of Civil Protection and APPA (*Agenzia Provinciale per la Protezione dell'Ambiente*). The two bodies have different competences and monitor water for different applications/reasons: flood risk management and water quality management. There has still been no agreement between the two bodies on coordinating their work. One functionary, who is an expert in the field of water management, claimed that "we are not receiving the data as we should.... The issues, unfortunately, have spread to all levels. There should be a complete change of

personnel at a certain level, otherwise things will not improve. It is essential that whoever is in charge makes a clear decision on what to do” (IntTN_08).

The European Commission explicitly requires that climate change be considered in water management plans, as seen for example in the Floods Directive (2007/60/EC). In this case, as is also the case for the energy sector and in general for the other sectors examined here, **the legislative autonomy of a province such as PAT is greatly appreciated** as it allows the avoidance of possible delays at the State level (although this is not of great importance in this sector, where the contribution made by the State is instead considered to be positive). Also when speaking of the water sector, interviewees say that Trentino should be the benchmark against which the rest of Italy (and not only Italy) is measured, both because of its legislative autonomy and because of its geographic characteristics. Indeed, it is the legislative freedom enjoyed by the PAT in particular that means that the State has little responsibility when things do not work in an efficient manner: it is more correct to consider the provincial level when examining both positive and negative elements of management. That being said, the State has put into action the Reservoir Plan (*Piano Invasi* in Italian), which is aimed at completing the construction of reservoirs designed to reduce the threat of both flooding as well as droughts. Furthermore, the State has also financed significant projects to improve the condition and management of aqueducts.

The water expert interviewed (IntTN_08) also maintained that there is a **problem with the roles undertaken by the public sector and the private sector**. According to him, the public sector should provide better regulation, while allowing the private sector freer rein to intervene in water management. It would be necessary, for example, to **change the manner in which the public sector is involved in setting rates for the sewage system and drinking water**: these rates are kept low level in order to avoid public resentment, yet this is problematic for the proper functioning of the water system and the public finances. What is more, the interviewee argues that it is necessary to widen the catchment areas of the water management bodies, as it is not efficient for the management of water to be entrusted to individual small municipalities.

As with the other sectors examined, in this case too public participation is considered to be largely ineffective, difficult to implement, and more a case of window dressing than genuine collaboration. On the other hand, in this case there is a perception that the level of economic investment by the PAT has been adequate.

2.1.3. SPATIAL PLANNING

Main sectoral initiatives and strategies mentioned during the interview:

- PUP (Urban Provincial Plan) - 2008
- So-called Legge per il governo del territorio - 2015
- Carta di Sintesi della pericolosità del territorio (Summary Map of Territorial Risk) - 2018

Overview¹⁵

There is no State law on territorial governance. As in the other examples here, this is a topic that is primarily the responsibility of the regions and the Autonomous Provinces. Nevertheless, in recent years the State (within the frame of European guidelines) has been working to introduce a number of measures aimed at directing the legislatures of the regions and autonomous provinces to reduce land consumption and pay attention to resource conservation. Furthermore, in this sector there are other

¹⁵ http://www.urbanistica.provincia.tn.it/pianificazione/pianificazione_territoriale/

important factors that must be considered, such as the municipal administrations that draw up regulatory plans as well as the role of mountain communities.

In this sector, the most important point of reference is the **Urban Provincial Plan** (*Piano Urbanistico Provinciale*: hereafter PUP), which was approved in 2008 and is still in force today. As outlined by a member of the administration that has worked for many years on this plan (IntTN_09), it contains a **number of flexible elements that make it possible to incorporate subsequent updates**. Due to this, it is still quite up-to-date and capable of responding to the needs of the PAT. A technical expert, who has collaborated with the PAT, defined it as “a plan that is centred on the landscape as it is understood by the 2000 European Landscape Convention, which states that landscape is everything that a population perceives of its living environment” (IntTN_02).

The Plan originated in 2004, also thanks to the impetus provided by European directives. It is based on the concept of sustainable development, as well as responsible subsidiarity and the principles of territorial competitiveness. In addition to the comprehensive framework of the Plan, which is aimed at adding value to the resources of the PAT, there is also a theme that has been incorporated for the first time and which IntTN_09 was particularly interested in stressing: i.e. compensation for agricultural lands that are the subject to transformations. Thus for the first time a sort of limit has been introduced, essentially pre-empting calculations about land consumption that will only come about in the future.

In addition to its stand-alone value, the PUP foreshadowed the **Summary Map of Territorial Hazards** (*Carta di Sintesi della pericolosità del territorio*), which entered into force in 2018, and which has a central role in questions relating to climate change. The *Carta di Sintesi della pericolosità del territorio* is the result of a great deal of collaborative work, which lasted throughout the decade from 2008 to 2018 and which involved an interdepartmental working group which was responsible for the development of the map. **The composition of this working group varied depending on the composition of the various departments during each legislature**. While the makeup of the departments changed over time, this did not influence the efficiency of the work undertaken, as it was always clear that the main objective of the working group was to draw up the document. Moreover, the Map is a work that is **constantly evolving**, with annual updates aimed at resolving possible critical issues. This means that there must always be active coordination between the various bodies. International protocols have been adopted for identifying hazards and identifying how such hazards might play out in the political realm. As mentioned by IntTN_09 and also pointed to by IntTN_02 (an expert technician in the planning sector), it was a significant amount of work based on surveys and on-the-ground implementation, and (unlike in the past) the need to find the right balance between ever more precise mapping tools and the right scale of application on a territorial level.

Subsequently, Law n. 15/2015 (the so called *Legge per il governo del territorio*), recalibrated the PUP, adopting some of its elements. All of the planning objectives and the guidance on building transformations, for example, were adopted and readapted, introducing on one hand specific rules related to land consumption and a series of incentives aimed at salvaging housing stocks, and on the other disincentivising new construction through a rise in construction taxes. Furthermore, **a number of measures for improving the energy efficiency of buildings were identified**. In this fashion, an attempt was made to utilise measures specifically related to construction to develop an economy that is aimed at the renovation and reuse of land and buildings.

While positive elements were mainly highlighted in the interviews with technical experts and members of the administration (aside from the political administration) who were themselves involved in the development of the documents under consideration, a number of criticisms were raised in the interviews with individuals from the world of politics (IntTN_11) and civil society (IntTN_03 e IntTN_10). For example, it emerged that the network of protected areas within the

territory of Trentino should be extended, as they are not currently sufficient to ensure the preservation of the province's natural heritage. It was also highlighted that there is a lack of attention paid to biodiversity, which would require initiatives to be undertaken to ensure that forests and woods do not become dominated by single species of trees. Lastly, there were calls to increase the amounts of green areas in the cities, by intervening in a systematic and structural fashion both in the centres and the suburbs. Similar interventions could mitigate the increasing temperatures and the urban heat islands, ensuring better thermal comfort to the inhabitants, than with absorbing CO₂ (as only a minimal amount of CO₂ would be absorbed).

2.2. DIMENSIONS OF INTEGRATION

2.2.1. COORDINATION (HORIZONTAL)

Common objectives and common strategies on climate-change integration

As mentioned by IntTN_04, and confirmed in other interviews with administrative figures (IntTN_05, IntTN_07) and members of civil society (IntTN_06), **for a long time there was a lack of a clear political strategy/mandate on the theme of the fight against climate change at the provincial level**, as a result of which there was also a lack of coordination between the responsible bodies.

The responsibility for coordination was initially entrusted to the Department of Civil Protection, and only recently assigned to APPA, with a particular remit of developing the future “Strategy for mitigation and adaptation to climate change” (*Strategia provinciale di mitigazione e adattamento ai cambiamenti climatici*).

In relation to the normative context of the PAT on climate, the PAT has adopted a specific law, “*Il Trentino per la protezione del clima*” (L.P. 9 marzo 2010, n. 5), which was subsequently substituted by the *Legge sulla Valutazione d’Impatto Ambientale* (L.P. 17 settembre 2013, n.19), art.23 “*Strategie e interventi della Provincia per fronteggiare il cambiamento climatico*”. In summary this law:

- defines specific objectives to be achieved in the medium and long term to reduce dependence on non-renewable energy sources, protect biodiversity and increase biomass (particularly forestry), in order to increase the capacity for absorbing CO₂ and other greenhouse gases of ecosystems;
- directs activities and provincial planning and design instruments towards achieving energy autonomy by 2050, drawing on the contribution of renewable sources within the region, and aims at achieving a “Zero Emission Trentino”;
- establishes a “Fund for the promotion of sustainable development and the fight against climate change”.

Moreover, as mentioned above, the *Strategia provinciale di mitigazione e adattamento ai cambiamenti climatici* is currently being developed. This strategy should represent the future blueprint to guide provincial administrative actions in identifying the measures to be integrated in to the planning and programming of various policy sectors in a coherent and coordinated fashion. This strategy is based on the scoping paper *Trentino Clima 2021-2023* - a work programme that is coordinated by APPA, whose contents were shared with interested bodies with the aim of defining and adopting future strategies: the entities forming the *Tavolo provinciale di coordinamento e di*

azione sui cambiamenti climatici (Provincial working group on coordination and action on climate change). The document received preliminary approval at the end of 2020, was evaluated by the research bodies of the provincial territory, and then was finally approved in early August 2021.

Finally, the *Strategia provinciale di Sviluppo Sostenibile – SproSS – Agenda 2030* (particularly objective 13 “The Fight against Climate Change”), adopted in October 2021, represents the overarching framework within which the *Strategia provinciale di mitigazione e adattamento ai cambiamenti climatici* lies.

The existing coordination mechanisms and their viability

There are a number of organs that are specifically tasked with improving the inter-departmental coordination between the various sectors of the PAT inherently related to climate change. The most important of these are:

- the *Osservatorio Trentino sul clima* (Programme Agreement signed in 2010 between the various provincial structures and territorial bodies, in place from 2010 to 2015 and subsequently renewed until 2016), which had the task of coordinating monitoring activity, research and communication related to the climate and climate change in Trentino.
- The *Tavolo provinciale di coordinamento e di azione sui cambiamenti climatici*, a provincial working group on coordination and action on climate change, that is supposed to coordinate the provincial bodies in the identification of appropriate mitigation and adaptation approaches and the development of a comprehensive strategy to propose to the Provincial Government. This body replaced the *Osservatorio Trentino sul clima* in 2016. Its members include APPA (as coordinators), the Department of Territory, Environment, Energy and Cooperation, APRI, the Department of Civil Protection, Forestry and Fauna, the Department of Education and Culture, The Department of Agriculture, the Department of Economic Development, Research and Employment, The Department of Health and Social Services, The Department of Infrastructure and Transport. When decisions need to be taken (e.g. in the case of *Trentino Clima 2021-2023*) the working group discusses the matter and produces a report which is then provided to the head of each individual department, who is the final decision-maker.

Aside from the abovementioned activities, all interviewees, albeit with different emphases and tones, consider that the actions carried out to date are not sufficient and that it will be necessary to ramp up activity in the coming years. The **identification of the APPA as coordinator of policies related to climate themes is generally seen as a positive step**, as long as this is put into action in a more effective manner than in the past.

Climate-coordination unit and coordination of climate-change mainstreaming

As was particularly highlighted by interviewees IntTN_04 and IntTN_07, from its foundation in 2010, the *Osservatorio Trentino Clima* played an important consultative role for the Provincial Government on all questions related to climate change, including investment needs and their priorities in relation to both research and implementation of interventions that were considered necessary. As mentioned above, the *Osservatorio* was initially coordinated in an informal manner by the Department of Civil Protection, before being assigned to **APPA**, which in a wider sense has become the **body within the PAT that is tasked with questions related to climate change**.

In recent years interdepartmental coordination has been implemented in a serious fashion: this is one of the most striking impressions that is evident from the interviews with figures from the political and administrative sector. **Mobility, Energy&Water and Spatial Planning now fall under the auspices**

of the Environmental Department, although it must be clarified that transport is in fact directly controlled by the president of the PAT. Furthermore, since October 2020, the head of the Transport Department has also assumed responsibilities in relation to land, environment and energy, and thus has an overview of the policies implemented at provincial level. According to IntTN_01, this figure has also taken measures to promote joint approaches to **avoid risks around dispersed efforts**. Also in this example, as underlined above in relation to other aspects, the scarcity of resources was identified as both a positive and a negative factor, in that it forced administrators to avoid any initiatives that did not strictly fall under the overarching plan.

In the case of some sectoral plans, the opportunity was taken to experiment with new forms of coordination and the more general strategies described above. In particular, the new PEAP (see above for more details) was mentioned by a number of interviewees, and not only those involved in the energy sector, as a significant moment in terms of the coordination between the various sectors and departments of the PAT. Moreover, a number of other initiatives, such as the Plan on air quality (2018) drawn up by APPA, saw a high level of interdepartmental involvement. This also represents an interesting case, as it involves measures that has to do with energy and transport (as well as with other sectors).

In addition there is also informal coordination via continuous exchanges (also via email) between the various departments of the PAT. Once again the PEAP embodies the best example of this as it was a collegiate piece of work, with chapters written by individuals from various departments: both IntTN_04 and IntTN_01 stressed how important the working group meetings were, while at the same time indicating that at times it is not necessary to have a working group since daily communication between colleagues in different departments functioned well. The same can be said for the *Spross* and the *Strategia di mitigazione adattamento ai cambiamenti climatici*. This improvement in communication is to a large extent thanks to improvements in technology, initially with the introduction of email and subsequently with the increased use of video calls.

Also in terms of interdepartmental horizontal coordination, although to a lesser extent than was seen in relation to public participation (see below), the interviewees from civil society were less optimistic in their views than representatives from the administration and the political field. IntTN_10, for example, argues that “the transport sector should communicate with the tourism sector. Instead what happens is that they create cliques and the sector with the strongest manager comes out on top”. An interviewee from the provincial administration (IntTN_05), while less pessimistic, also admits that there is a mentality that is quite hierarchical and vertical, an opinion that was confirmed by an expert technician who has collaborated with the PAT for many years on the topic of spatial planning (IntTN_02).

2.2.2. COORDINATION (VERTICAL)

The significance of the EU legislation and policy

The importance of the transnational level, and in particular the European level, was evident in the narratives of all interviewees, from technical experts and administrative figures to politicians and civil society representatives. Initially, reference was made to initiatives dating back a number of years, such as the Habitat Directive and the Natura 2000 network. More recent advances were however mentioned most often, from the publication of the **Fourth Report on “Climate Change 2007” by the IPCC** (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change), which outlined a clear connection between climate change and human activity. **From this point onwards, climate change became of fundamental interest also in Trentino.** A process was launched which led to the drawing up of an

initial analysis of the effects of climate change that were already taking place in Trentino and those that posed a threat in the future, as well as an evaluation of the sectors that were at greatest risk due to such effects. The results of this work were brought together in a publication entitled “*Previsioni e conseguenze dei cambiamenti climatici in Trentino*” (2008).

A further moment that was recognised as significant by many of the interviewees was the signing of the **Paris Climate accord in 2015** by the Parties of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change: following this important event in global climate governance, there was a significant rise in awareness of climate issues in the international community, as well as in the public discourse, even on a provincial level. Currently the scientific community is arguing that the measures laid out following the Paris Accord are not sufficient and is urging the international community to make significant changes. This is one of the reasons for which **over the past number of years there has been a shift from this being a topic that was almost exclusively focused on mitigating the effects of climate change** (e.g. the reduction of greenhouse gasses) **to one which also considers the potential of adaptation** (reducing risk, offsetting negative impacts, increasing resilience, exploiting or benefitting from positive impacts). On the other hand, a number of laws, such as Law n.10/2010, the L.P. 17/2013 and subsequently the PEAP, have long established objectives that go beyond those set by Europe.

Nevertheless, in spite of the importance of the European guidelines, the **PAT has its own peculiarities when it comes to local frameworks for managing specific situations**. This is a further element underlined in many of the interviews, especially those with individuals from the administrative and political sectors. While Europe is undoubtedly an indispensable reference point, there are local peculiarities in terms of policy making that are the result of the autonomy of the PAT and its **ability to legislate in an autonomous fashion in certain policy areas**.

The national level

The national level is generally considered **less important than the transnational level** and, in particular, the European level. In some cases, a number of interviewees recognised the fact that the State has had to implement a number of standards set by the European Union. While there is a widespread perception that the Italian State is either neutral or indeed causes blockages when it comes to provincial legislation, it is interesting to note that generally speaking the respondents did not consider the State to be a significant obstacle, apart from a number of situations linked to excesses of **bureaucracy and formality**, and because it is considered to produce **too much legislation**. This opinion is particularly held by political figures, but less so by members of the provincial administration and even less so by members of civil society. Indeed, what is criticised at a national level is not the excess of regulation, but the **lack of dynamism**. A specific example outlined in one interview is related to the approval of a provincial law on hydroelectrical permits (“concessioni” in Italian): an interviewee (IntTN_01) expressed his amazement at seeing how an incentive aimed at streamlining and improving the efficiency of hydraulic resources as well as investing in renewable energy communities and energy self-sufficiency was blocked by burdensome national bureaucracy.

A number of interviews with technical experts or administrative staff highlighted a general rigidity within Italian administration, which was also felt at a local level. As mentioned by one interviewee, “those of us who work in public administration feel the TAR (*Tribunale Amministrativo Regionale*, Regional Administrative Courthouse), the judiciary, and the court of auditors are all breathing down our necks. This is the problem of the Italian administration. In other countries they look more at the results, while in Italy it is considered very risky to move outside of consolidated procedures” (IntTN_02).

In addition to these observations, it must be stressed (as was mentioned in several interviews) that **Italy lags behind in terms of climate change adaptation policies**. Two relevant documents exist in relation to the national scale in terms of mitigation: the *Piano Nazionale Integrato Energia e Clima* (P.N.I.E.C.), which outlines the route towards decarbonization between 2021 and 2030, and the *Strategia Italiana di Lungo Termine sulla Riduzione delle Emissioni dei Gas a Effetto Serra* (published in 2021). On the other hand, Italy is still waiting to implement the *Piano Nazionale di Adattamento ai Cambiamenti Climatici*. For this reason, many regions and autonomous provinces, including the PAT, have been taking steps independently: from this perspective, many interviewees mention both the **unique geographic characteristics of Trentino**, as well as the possibility that the region would/will **place itself at the forefront in terms of climate change adaptation policies** and as a model for other Italian regions.

In a number of specific cases, however, State regulation was held up as a positive aspect as it helped to iron out a number of issues at local level. In the case of Law n. 11/2007, for example, the Parks Plan was erroneously placed within the *Piano territoriale di comunità*. According to one interviewee, “fortunately the national legislation intervened to straighten out this issue in which the Parks Plan, which involves various regions, had been placed under the auspices of a local planning framework, something that would have been politically disastrous: it would have meant that the Parks Plan would have to be adapted according to local decisions”. A similar case was highlighted in the case of the Parco dello Stelvio.

Intergovernmental mechanisms of coordination

There are a number of very formal coordination mechanisms, at various levels of government, which were mentioned by the interviewees: the most important are the **State-Regions Thematic Commissions** (*Commissioni Tematiche Stato-Regione*), which is a body that issues technical guidelines. Another important body, cited in particular by IntTN_07, is the national System of Environmental Protection (*Sistema Nazionale della Protezione dell’Ambiente*)¹⁶, coordinated by ISPRA (Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale)¹⁷, which brings together all of the regional and provincial environmental agencies in Italy. This is a predominantly technical coordination body. It is responsible for defining the indicators of climate change, which can then be used to develop strategies and policies to take action.¹⁸ There are also more political coordination bodies, however, none of the interviewees went into a great deal of detail in discussions on these.

The interviewees more or less unanimously stressed the importance of the role played by the European Union, as well as that of the Italian State in adopting the guidelines and directives issued by Europe. No other mechanisms were specifically mentioned. A number of interviewees did mention working groups, especially interdepartmental working groups as opposed to intergovernmental ones.

The ability of the PAT to exercise independent control in certain areas has allowed it to gain certain advantages, not necessarily in an economic sense, but at least in regards to planning. This has allowed it to put itself in a better position compared to other Italian regions. This aspect was stressed across all sectors, but particularly in relation to the energy sector (IntTN_05).

¹⁶ <https://www.snpambiente.it/>

¹⁷ <https://www.isprambiente.gov.it/it>

¹⁸ They also publish very relevant technical guidelines, useful for policy makers and administrative offices.

Cross-border cooperation

Participation in transnational networks and projects has **reduced in recent years**. This is blamed by a number of interviewees on the constant **reduction in financial and particularly human resources dedicated to these activities**. This finding is observed across all sectors studied. There has been a particular drop off in the number of applications for European funding calls. Nevertheless, there are a number of **networks in which the PAT, or at least some of its departments, is involved**, and this represents significant added value. A number of the names mentioned in the interviews include ERRIN, Fedarene, Covenant of Mayors¹⁹, EUSALP, Convenzione delle Alpi and EUREGIO.

In addition to this, a number of informal, **grassroots links emerged in the interviews with members of civil society**. For example, a number of cities (Graz, Tallin and the French city of Hasselt) are seen as examples for the proposed law by popular initiative that led to the current Law on Sustainable Mobility. In both Tallin and Hasselt in particular, the decision was taken to construct a large bypass to help the flow of traffic, but this required enormous levels of financing. The citizens committees proposed investing the money in public transport instead, and particularly in rail transport. It was found that by adopting this approach it was also possible to provide free public transport. This is not, therefore, a cross border initiative per se, but rather a case in which inspiration was drawn from other cases internationally. It must be said that Trentino is considered by many of the interviewees across all sectors and civil society as the finest example of a testing ground for cutting edge approaches.

It is particularly relevant to note the **relationship with bordering regions within the Alps**. An example mentioned by a number of interviewees and particularly outlined by IntTN_07, is the EUSALP, which brings together many coordination bodies. APRIE, for example, is a member of the Action Group on energy, Fondazione Mach is a member of that related to ecological networks, the Department of Civil Protection and APPA form part of the group working on risks related to natural events.

2.2.3. LEADERSHIP

Political Leadership

As mentioned above, the **PAT climate objectives have long been above the standards set by Europe**. Examples of this include the objective to reduce emissions to 50% of 1990 levels by 2030 (according to the 2013 Law, now -55% according to the new PEAP), and to achieve energy autonomy and reduce emissions to 10% of 1990 levels by 2050. Nevertheless, according to many interviewees (across all sectors and representing different types of respondents), political interest has increased in recent years due to the fact that public opinion increasingly considers climate change to be an important issue and it has become a sensitive political topic. An important role has undoubtedly been played by the **natural events that have taken place in the province which have attracted the attention of both politicians and civil society**. The most important serious event is clearly **Storm Adrian** (also known as Storm Vaia in Italy, 2018). In stressing the shock caused by this event, IntTN_04 underlined a number of nevertheless “positive” effects, such as the fact that there was less damage caused in Trentino than in neighboring regions. One of the main reasons for this was the actions that had been undertaken by the provincial administration, as well as the experience of previous disasters in the province such as the **Val di Stava Disaster** (1985). Following that event Trentino developed a policy of prevention and today 50 million euros of public resources are spent every year in improving the land and the environment. The opinion of members of civil society on

¹⁹ This was mentioned in some interview, but it is supposed to be only for municipalities.

the Storm Adrian event are less positive. IntTN_03, for example, argues that an event such as Storm Adrian “should have made us reflect further. Even in this case, a region like ours which has one of the biggest budgets, was found to be ill prepared and the disaster was managed in a chaotic fashion”.

Aside from these local events, the imposition of European directives has been seen as a turning point, especially the target for a 40% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions and the subsequent Green Deal targets issued at the end of 2019. More generally, **big summits, and specifically the Paris Accord of 2015, were cited as fundamental moments in the integration of the fight against climate change** into provincial policy and in the development of a greater interest among the political leadership. This was evident in many interviews, across all sectors and all profiles of respondents.

As discussed above in relation to interdepartmental coordination, the transport, energy&water and spatial planning sectors all fall under the ambit of the Environmental Department, although public transport remains the responsibility of the president of the PAT. This was not the case in the past, and in the accounts of the political and administrative respondents this represents a major step forward. Even the interviewees from civil society admit that this may be a positive move, however, they maintain that it is important to closely examine the policies that are developed.

One of the aspects that results from this concentration of leadership is that over the years there has been a shift in focus from almost solely considering approaches to mitigate climate change to a greater level attention paid to the aspect of adaptation. The *Legge Clima* of 2010, in particular, was very much focussed on mitigation, and on the urgent need to reduce greenhouse emissions. In terms of mitigation, the reference point is the PEAP, which is linked to this law. Adaptation as an approach, however, has a much more recent history. Many sectoral plans have had to budget for issues relating to climate change adaptation. It is often **difficult to find a specific correlation between the politics of adaptation and any particular references to climate change**: this point emerged both in the interview with a key figure on the provincial level in relation to the climate issue (IntTN_07) as well as in interviews with various experts from individual sectors (IntTN_05, IntTN_09).

There is a **high level of agreement that centralised coordination is important, even among members of civil society**, however, some lacunae were highlighted in relation to the genuine desire of the political leadership to effectively tackle climate issues. IntTN_03, for example, maintained that “there are perhaps some individual initiatives, however, we are suffering from the lack of a big picture, of a roadmap. What is needed is an approach that would make Trentino a strategic hub and not just a border region”. This opinion is shared in substance by IntTN_06: “it is not new laws that are needed. The laws already exist, however, some of them lack implementation guidelines which means that they are not applied. While the law on sustainable transport may not have been exactly what we had called for, only 30% of it has been applied: if everything that was written in the law had been carried out, we would be in a much better place. It is a problem of political will and vision”.

In some interviews there was a clear expression of hope that a specific political authority (an *assessorato* in Italian) would be set up to tackle climate change, arguing that it was necessary to have a standard with which every policy set by the PAT could be measured in terms of its impact on the climate. Another common criticism, mostly expressed by respondents from civil society, is the perceived provincialism and the tendency to be overly influenced by the approaches of bordering regions (especially Veneto). Even in this case the role of Europe is considered a positive aspect, due to the fact that aside from the merits of any policy, it helps the province to look at challenges with a less localised and more international approach, feeding into the idea that Trentino (due to its geographic and climatic characteristics) has the potential to play a consequential role even on a global scale.

A specific issue that emerged mainly in the interviews with political figures, or administrative figures close to the political sector (IntTN_04 e IntTN_01), is the **acceleration of decision processes**. This has become an issue because increasingly it is necessary to deal with ever larger amounts of money (Recovery Plan, The Winter Olympic Games, etc.): these types of initiatives require large amounts of legislation. Often this clashes with the more wide ranging and structural plans developed within the province.

It should be stressed that a number of the respondents from civil society argued that there is a lack of political leadership that is worthy of the term. IntTN_06, for example, states that there has been a lack of knowledge in the various political administrations that have alternated over the years of the approaches taken. This lack of awareness, in particular with reference to mitigation, is linked to a lack of an overarching vision, and, possibly, to a lack of intention to move away from a paradigm dominated by growth (IntTN_10). Other interviewees, for example an expert technician who was less critical of the provincial administration and the various successive governments, admits that there is a lack of an overarching vision, adding that “if you want to find any trace of integration, you have to look for fragments; I don’t believe that its possible now to find any sort of coherent framework”.

A number of leadership figures of the past were identified by name in some of the interviews, in particular Alberto Pacher, Roberto Bombarda, Walter Micheli.

Administrative Leadership

From an administrative/technical perspective, the equivalent of the concentration of power in the Environmental Department is linked to the **identification of an agency within the same department which serves as a reference point for climate issues: APPA**.

Administrative responsibilities, in particular, are divided between two main agencies: APPA (coordination, technical activities aimed at raising awareness, strategy development, communication, education and information, representation at a national and international level) and APRIE (responsible for the planning of mitigation measures). According to IntTN_07 it would be even better if a single body were identified that could take care of all of these responsibilities. Having two agencies that form part of the same department is somewhat of an anomaly, which could be done away with in favour of a new and more efficient coordination.

Having entrusted the responsibility of tackling climate change to APPA was an important step as it recognised the importance of the environment. In the past, these responsibilities were more widely spread; bringing them under the auspices of APPA has a significant strategic advantage. Generally speaking, this change is appreciated by the various respondents, irrespective of their various sectors and roles. As IntTN_07 states, “this allowed for things to speed up. Instruments that existed already were greatly improved, such as the task force for coordination on climate change. This is not to say that there had not been coordination between the departments. Indeed it worked quite well. However, there had not been this strong connection with the political level”.

Another important point that was mentioned in a number of interviews (IntTN_01, IntTN_08) is the fact that the performance of the administration has improved thanks to a high level of turnover and a **reduction in the average age of functionaries**. Also in this case, **lack of finance** has driven virtuous processes to identify more effective approaches.

Relationship between the political and administrative level

The leadership is a **combination of the political leadership and the administrative leadership**. This, according to the account of an important manager within the PAT (IntTN_01), has taken place “by inertia”, meaning that it is to some extent the result of the development of the climatic and environmental crisis. In addition to this generally held belief, the importance of the link between the political and administrative levels is very much linked to the close rapport between the Environmental Department and the individual agencies, particularly APPA in relation to coordination, but also APRIE in some circumstances.

The influence of civil society

The influence of civil society is more often described as effective by figures outside of civil society itself. A number of organisations were mentioned by name, such as SAT, Legambiente, and a number of citizen’s committees. In various interviews with political and administrative figures, the inclusion of civil society in the policy making process is described as one of the major successes and improvements achieved in recent years. On a formal level, there has been the foundation of the Provincial Forum for Climate Changes (*Forum Provinciale per i Cambiamenti Climatici*, coordinated by APPA).

In contrast, the **representatives of civil society, especially associations and citizen’s committees, denounce either the lack of genuine involvement** (see the final paragraph of the following section) or the under-appreciation of certain themes. The latter, for example, is the case for a process cited in a number of interviews and discussed in more detail in some of them, i.e. the *Legge sulla Mobilità Sostenibile* and in particular the popular initiative for the law created by citizens and proposed by a number of organisations within the territory who drew up the document as part of a grassroots process. The participatory process is outlined in the following section, however, it should be underlined here that the major issue lay in the fact that the main demands and proposals from civil society were not reflected in the final output of the law. Indeed, the law was essentially approved in the form that it was proposed by the citizen movement, but some of the main points - among the most important ones - were eliminated, namely those relating to finance (a rise in the annual budget of the PAT for the transport sector from 3% to 5%, free public transport, all financed by public taxes) and to participation (the foundation of a citizen’s assembly, drawn by lots, to discuss policy issues). Moreover, although this law has been approved, it is generally overlooked by most parties, at least according to IntTN_06 e IntTN_10.

One hope expressed in many of the interviews was that awareness of **climate change issues could be extended to “ordinary people”, especially through activities carried out in schools**. In this sense, public initiatives are considered important. According to the majority of the respondents, the PAT has been very effective in putting this in place in recent years; even more, a considerable proportion of interviewees (especially political figures) underlined the central role played by specific initiatives (IntTN_01 e IntTN_04). Beyond this, while there is a critical view of the political leadership in this regard, there is simultaneously a positive view in relation to the possible role that could be assumed by citizens and by associations/committees, which is expressed in clear terms by IntTN_06: “citizens are more open to change than the political class, therefore the proposals made from the grassroots level have always been braver than those of politicians”.

Other interviewees, in particular a technical expert who collaborates with the PAT, underlined how civil society can also represent an obstacle. An example of this is the inherent opposition of some citizens, professional categories or associations to the installation of insulation cladding or solar panels in the historical city centre of Trento (IntTN_02). Even more classic examples are those

referred to as ‘nimbyism’, mentioned by a number of the administrative figures (IntTN_05 e IntTN_09), which can stall the implementation of effective initiatives that form part of the environmental and climate plans.

2.2.4. PARTICIPATION

Mandatory consultation and *ad hoc* participation processes

According to the interviews with members of the administration, there are procedures which allow citizens to request information on the policies aimed at tackling climate change. They mainly require the **citizens to refer to communal or provincial councillors, who then act as intermediaries, as part of their institutional work, in the dialogue with the governing bodies**: this can include inquiries, consultations, motions, and draft laws in the case of provincial and regional councils. Citizens can also undertake signature collections and petitions on specific environmental issues, which can in some fashion be linked to climate change. In some cases, these also reach the institutional level.

Moreover, the already mentioned *Forum provinciale per i cambiamenti climatici* was also created, coordinated by APPA. This is a **space for dialogue that is open to the participation of all groups in Trentino** that are involved in promoting scientific, cultural, information, awareness, training and education initiatives on topics related to climate change.

In outlining the origins of the *Forum provinciale per i cambiamenti climatici*, IntTN_07 underlined the fact that this was originally created as a response to a certain disinterest in the topic in the administration, or at the very least an inability to identify effective action plans. The interviewee recalled the importance of the fact that Trento had hosted the national conference of the *Società Italiana delle Scienze per il Clima* in 2019. Alongside the event, a number of educational events aimed at citizens were organised throughout the province. This is where the idea to ‘formalise’ this arena to exchange ideas was born, all the while maintaining its grassroots nature and its awareness raising activities.

Currently, participants in the Forum include APPA, Meteotrentino, Servizio Sviluppo Sostenibile e Aree Protette per la PAT, Fondazione Mach, Università di Trento, Fondazione B.Kessler, MUSE, SAT – Comitato glaciologico, Fondazione Museo Civico Rovereto, Parco Naturale Adamello Brenta, TSM Step, Climate KIC, Comune di Trento, Associazione Trento Film Festival e Associazione Viraçao&Jangada.

It should also be mentioned the existence of a specific authority dedicate to local participation at the provincial level, namely the *Autorità per la partecipazione locale*.²⁰ This is not an organ dedicated to climate issues, but a central organ for local participation more broadly. No matter the various attempts to organize an interview with the Authority, this resulted impossible.

Participatory processes for the development of sectoral strategy-documents

The provincial scientific and research bodies have been involved in the scientific studies that have laid the basis of many provincial plans. They are also involved in the *Comitato Scientifico del Tavolo*

²⁰ The Authority for local participation is the body to which the Provincial Law of 16 June 2006, n. 3 entrusts the task of promoting the participation of citizens and local authorities in the construction processes of territorial policies. Website: <https://apl.provincia.tn.it/>

provinciale di coordinamento e di azione sui Cambiamenti Climatici (Unitn - DICAM, Fem, Fbk, Muse, Hit).

A specific example of participation referred to by a number of interviewees (e.g. IntTN_04) is that of the *Stati Generali della Montagna* (held in Spring 2019), which was called by the PAT specifically following the Adrian Storm disaster. It involved the coming together of mountain communities, administrators, economic interests, voluntary associations and average citizens. As outlined by IntTN_09, an attempt was made on the occasion to understand and to share the issues faced by the region in a transversal manner. Aided by the involvement of university research institutes, this made it possible to produce a number of important documents. The results of the *Stati Generali* were subsequently incorporated into the PEAP.

Another extremely relevant example cited by numerous respondents from civil society (IntTN_03, IntTN_06, IntTN_10), was the **citizens' initiative for drawing up a law on sustainable mobility**. The draft law contained 22 articles and was the product of a long process that started in 2014, which was also developed by drawing on experiences in foreign contexts and positive regulations introduced in other municipalities. Once it had been drafted, the document was sent to the Environment Commission (in Italian: Commissione Ambiente), which should have discussed it prior to sending it to the Provincial Council in 2017. The whole process was clearly recalled by IntTN_06 and most importantly IntTN_10. Almost 5,000 signatures were collected, far exceeding the requisite 2,500. Initially also a number of trade unions took part in the process, but in the long term the main participants were Mountain Wilderness, Legambiente, WWF and other smaller organisations. The proposal passed through all of the formal administrative and legislative steps, which is an indication of how well it was written, and it even received commendations from a number of administrative figures and provincial councillors. When it came to the stage for it to be approved, it was proposed to discuss the matter with the provincial administration, which was at the time preparing its own plan, with the aim of finding a common approach. Once again according to interviewee IntTN_10, there was a constant dialogue with the administration. However, one of the complicating factors was the fact that many of the meetings were scheduled for the morning, making it difficult for many citizens and committees to take part. As reminded above, even if the participatory process was generally positive, the final outcome was only partially positive, as two of the milestones of the citizens' initiative (rise in the annual budget of the PAT for the transport sector and the creation of a citizens' assembly) were rejected.

Another very relevant participation process discussed in some interviews (in particular IntTN_04 and IntTN_07) is the one that conducted to the SproSS (Strategia provinciale per lo Sviluppo Sostenibile). A very precise and effective summary of this process is provided at this [link](#) (where also useful information on the outcomes of this strategy can be found and consulted).

Online instruments and tools of participation

Technological tools were widely cited as a means by which interdepartmental coordination was facilitated (as well as vertical coordination between different levels of government), but rarely in relation to the involvement of the population and civil society in general. This was also the case following the outbreak of the **Covid-19** pandemic, with the mass implementation of video calls and working from home. Covid-19 may have effected change through the increase in remote working, and not solely in terms of impacts (i.e. reducing the strain on the transport system), but also in terms of the **possibilities that remote connections provide to effectively increase the number of participants in an activity**.

Furthermore, political figures and figures in between from politics and administration stated that they had communicated with citizens through the use of messaging systems such as Whatsapp: “the administration reduced the distance between itself and the citizens, this administration comes from a culture of public rallies, of direct interaction with the stakeholders and the people”. This impression was not always shared by representatives from civil society: some interviewees referenced the fact that direct requests addressed to administrative functionaries often go unanswered (IntTN_03).

With regard to the use of online tools for participation, it can be said that they are employed, but it must be underlined that there are more limits than opportunities, in that it is undoubtedly preferable to organise participatory events in presence if possible.

There is a PAT platform aimed at encouraging citizen participation ([IoRacconto](#)), but it is mainly used in relation to the health services. The interviewees, especially those from civil society, hoped that the same could be done in relation to the fight against climate change.

Highlighted criticalities of participatory processes

The main criticality stressed in various interviews is linked to the fact that **consultation is often reduced to a formality**, mere consultation, thus becoming delivery of information as opposed to a genuine participatory process.

A point that was largely shared by respondents from civil society (IntTN_06) as well as from the provincial administration (IntTN_05), is the fact that **associations at the local level are badly organised**, and this means that in relation to certain macro-themes (like an environmental energy plan) they are unable to intervene in an effective manner. They are sometimes able to do so in relation to sectoral plans or individual initiatives, as opposed to more sweeping documents such as the PEAP or the *Strategia di mitigazione e adattamento ai cambiamenti climatici* (see previous sections for details on these documents).

Many interviewees from civil society condemned the **distance between citizens and elected politicians caused by the many administrative levels**, such as the mountain communities, the province, the municipalities, etc. Even assuming that there was a desire to involve citizens (something about which the representatives from the organisations were sceptical), the problem is that politicians do not reply to everyone with the same speed and availability, instead only doing so with certain preferred categories. Moreover, as underlined by IntTN_03, this type of participation can be carried out in a society that is informed and aware of the importance of climate issues at a collective level. If citizens could deliver constructive proposals in a collective manner this would be a positive development, whereas currently direct contact between politicians and citizens is mainly used for private issues.

2.2.5. INFORMATION

Nature of the existing information mechanisms and processes

These are **mainly voluntary information mechanisms**, primarily linked to the desire to inform citizens about the issues related to climate change, and eventually to communicate future initiatives taken by the provincial administration in relation to individual measures or in terms of individual sectors. **Other sources of information are related to the presence of legislative, normative and planning documents on the PAT website** (see below).

One of the formal mechanisms that is available is the *Forum*, mentioned above, which not only has the function of bringing together grassroots bodies, but also has the role of informing the general population about issues relating to climate change.

IntTN_06 also made reference to the festival [*Fa' la cosa giusta*](#), stating that it would have been helpful if there had been a greater deal of coordination on the part of the PAT and if the initiative had been better advertised.

Availability and transparency of information on climate-policy

In general terms, **availability and transparency of information is not a theme on which the respondents had particularly developed opinions**. It is considered neither as a particular strength nor as a weakness. This opinion was shared across the whole sample. IntTN_10 made particular reference to this topic, stating that “if a person wants to take a moment and think about the topic, between communications issued by the PAT, newspaper articles and other sources, they can find the information. But people have to start doing a bit of the leg work themselves. I don't think that the right approach is to delegate things to others. I criticise politics, but then I also think that it's important to get involved personally. Sometimes there is not a huge amount of transparency, but many of us have the wherewithal to study, to interpret and to be a bit autonomous mentally”.

Communication strategy(ies)

There is **no shared strategy on a communication level**, but there should be. Insofar as any strategy exists, this is applied to single themes, not in a general sense. There is an awareness in the administration that this strategy must be improved and implemented.

According to various interviewees, at the moment every sector essentially acts alone. Communications are aligned with the general objectives set by the PAT in relation to climate change, but these communications are far from being communication strategies coordinated in a precise and strategic manner.

Under 30s as a target group

According to a central figure at the political level (IntTN_04), young people can have an influence on decision makers, in addition to influencing the daily habits and housekeeping practices of their relatives. It is for this reason that **individual awareness activities must be implemented first and foremost in schools**. According to the respondents, young people are more attuned to climate issues than other generations. Nevertheless, in some cases (especially in the interviews with political and administrative figures), attention was drawn to successful initiatives that had already been put in place. This impression was not shared by the interviewees from civil society.

At the end of 2019 a [specific channel](#) related to schools was opened up within the Agenda 2030, with a specific focus on the goals relating to greenhouse gases emissions. With the outbreak of Covid-19, this was transformed into a number of webinars with university students and a number of events in high schools.

Another initiative that is relevant to this topic was described by IntTN_07, and is linked to the engagement offerings for teachers and students. The PAT has created a brochure and a dedicate web

platform²¹ coordinated by APPA in which all of the engagement offerings of the various *Forum* members are outlined. This meant that in September teachers were able to select their preferred engagement activity for their students.

While engagement initiatives in the schools exist, they must be improved according to many interviewees. Direct engagement with students as well as training for teachers on these topics needs to be increased, as they are generally very lacking and often only connect with some individuals who are particularly interested in the theme. It must be noted that a number of the respondents made reference to the **mobilisations for climate justice**, particularly **Fridays for Future**, as important engines of change (an element that was especially emphasised by IntTN_11).

Finally, young people themselves have organised activities specifically dedicated to climate change and aimed at their peers. One of the many examples mentioned by IntTN_11 is the **Trento Film Festival**, in which 40 young people between 15 and 29 years old undertook a [programme](#) that ended with them developing a document containing recommendations addressed to politicians, businesses, associations, and the media. The document was specifically presented to two Council members of the PAT, two Council members of the Trento municipality and even to the Italian minister for the ecological transition – Roberto Cingolani – during the COP26 in Glasgow.

Online tools, social media campaigns and best-practices platforms

There is a reference website run by the province named Climatrentino (<http://www.climatrentino.it/>). On the website, users can find various educational and informative documents, which have been drawn up thanks to funding from the province and in collaboration with the various provincial scientific bodies (Universities, FEM, FBK, MUSE):

- First publication “*Previsioni e conseguenze dei cambiamenti climatici in Trentino*” (2008)
- Temperature and precipitation report “*Analisi di serie di temperatura e precipitazione in Trentino nel periodo 1958-2010*” (2012)
- Climate Map of Trentino (presented at a conference organised in 2017 by the *Osservatorio* entitled “*Dalle temperature ai ghiacciai: la ricerca racconta la storia di un clima che cambia*”; the map has its own dedicated site)
- Conferences
- “*A scuola per il clima – Proposte di educazione ambientale sull’emergenza dei cambiamenti climatici*” – 2020/2021 academic year (to be repeated in 2021/2022); curated educational engagement activities for schools in the province (Forum: APPA, CCI, FBK, Museo Civico di Rovereto, MUSE, Parco Adamello Brenta, Parco Paneveggio, TSM – STEP, Trento Film Festival, Ass. Viracao&Jangada).²²

Furthermore, on the website one can find a range of digital materials (which correspond to the printed documents), such as brochures and other information aids used over the years to raise awareness of the theme of climate change and to increase the understanding of the wider public.

IntTN_06 cites [La parola ai cittadini](#) as a possible instrument of direct democracy. Also in this case, however, it must be stressed that it must take the form of genuine engagement and not simple window dressing.

²¹ <https://educazioneambientale.provincia.tn.it/Catalogo-del-sistema-provinciale>

²² All documents available on the website mentioned above.

2.2.6. FUNDING²³

The only financial instrument specifically linked to climate change is the *Fondo sul Clima* (which subsequently became the *Fondo per lo sviluppo sostenibile e la lotta ai cambiamenti climatici*) which was established with the law in 2010 (*Il Trentino per la protezione del clima*). A large proportion of resources from this fund have been used over the years to finance initiatives such as the *Tavolo provinciale di coordinamento e di azione sui Cambiamenti Climatici* and the *Osservatorio Trentino*.

A general element that emerged from all the interviews relates to the **reductions in public financing** and in particular the funds available to the provincial administration. This reduction is the result of larger scale economic issues, and especially the economic crisis of 2008.

There is **no specific target for financing on climate change**, but certain themes (such as land transformations/modifications and land use) are closely linked to climate change. Spending is tied to particular themes, as it might be tied in turn to budget headings. There are arrangements that make it possible to earmark well-determined tax revenues directly for certain sectors. Conversely the rule is that taxes and other revenues are included in the PAT budget and then the PAT decides how to distribute them to the individual sectors and authorities. This is the general rule in public finances.

What can be drawn from the budget of the Province is the amount of expenditure in the function - territorial government (before 2016) and in the mission 09 - sustainable development and protection of land and environment (from 2016 onwards). Under this heading the expenditure for the administration and operation of activities and services related to the protection of the environment and the territory, natural resources, biodiversity (including sewage treatment plants) are included. Mission 09 gives evidence of the core expenditure in environment, i.e., whether it represents the prevailing interest. Nevertheless, there are other policies in other sectors with related expenditure that contribute to mitigating climate change. The CPT database is of interest because it allows for comparison between the two provinces, and also with the other regions. The database regionalises expenditure, including that of the State in the various regions. Of interest is the environment function no. 14, which contains data distributed on three levels: state, provincial and local.

The DEFP and NADEFP also contain useful information. They are drawn up on seven strategic areas, including the environment, and there is a link between missions and programmes, but it is not so straightforward. The NADEFP at the end of the strategic area description contains a reference to the provincial budget, thus linking policies and resources in a clearer way.

The table below outlines the funding earmarked solely for climate change up to 2015 (1,831,200 Euro):

ANNO	FONDO CAMBIAMENTO CLIMATICO SPESE C/C - DIRETTE cap. 803560
2010	600.000,00
2011	350.000,00
2012	351.200,00
2013	140.000,00
2014	70.000,00
2015	320.000,00

²³ Parts of this section has been authored by Alice Valdesalici, Eurac Research.

Since 2016, funds have been merged into the *Fondo unico sviluppo sostenibile e la lotta ai cambiamenti climatici*.

ANNO	FONDO SVILUPPO SOSTENIBILE SPESE C/C - DIRETTE cap. 803550-001	FONDO SVILUPPO SOSTENIBILE SPESE C/C - CONTRIBUTI cap. 803550-002
2010	973.000,00	2.614.960,00
2011	695.000,00	1.696.400,00
2012	1.300.315,00	1.948.000,00
2013	547.000,00	820.000,00
2014	273.500,00	410.000,00
2015	323.000,00	50.000,00
2016	230.000,00	70.000,00
2017	165.000,00	210.538,00
2018	225.500,00	1.177.571,50
2019	120.000,00	1.000.000,00
2020	225.200,00	770.600,00
2021	150.000,00	601.600,00

Aggregated data according to type of spending in the *Fondo sul Clima* from 2010-2015 (available only for the period 2010-2015):

- Events/conferences/communication/studies and experiments: 359,152 euro
- Research activity carried out as part of programme agreements with other bodies: 646,000 euro
- Projects carried out by provincial bodies with the aid of the *Fondo sul Clima*: 320,736 euro

Overall total for 2010-2015: 1,325,888 euro.

As has been mentioned a number of times, at the end of 2020 responsibility for action on climate change was transferred to APPA. Under this framework, 130,000 euros were designated for the budget of APPA for 2021 (with 150,000 euros forecast for 2022 and 2023) in order to aid the implementation of the work programme *Trentino Clima 2021-2023*.

2.3. CROSS-CUTTING TENDENCIES

A number of interviewees, across all sectors, admitted that it is **difficult to find a direct relationship between initiatives in the individual sectors and the fight against climate change**. In some cases, the relationship might not be clearly evident, but it does exist. However, it is difficult to make an assessment of all of the measures and the extent to which they have been linked to climate change, particularly because some initiatives may not have been labelled as such.

Another common trend that emerged in many interviews is undoubtedly that related to the **lack of financing on themes related to climate change**, and more generally a decrease in the funding available to carry out this type of initiative.

In light of the two preceding general observations, it is interesting to note that many interviewees across all sectors agree on the **difficulty in getting such diverse sectors to work together**, especially on themes that are as complex as climate change (the sample also expressed itself fairly unanimously on the complexity of the theme).

In addition to these issues raised by many of the interviewees, a number of positive elements were also shared across the sectors: first of all, the **increasing awareness of climate change emerges as a common theme**. Some interviewees especially emphasised the increased awareness within the wider public, while others focussed on improvements in the administration and amongst political figures.

On the basis of this greater awareness, there was a desire for a greater level of **investment in cultural events aimed at modifying/changing lifestyle habits and behaviors from below**. The role of single individuals was also considered central by all respondents, as part of a wider discussion on the cultural change within society. Given the centrality of this issue, some interviewees did underline that this should not equate with less commitment and work by politicians and institutions, and that it does not reduce the responsibility of industries and markets.

The last observation is also linked to another theme that emerged in many of the interviews, i.e. that the greatest obstacle to the implementation of effective initiatives in the fight against climate change is represented by the **economic interests of a number of production sectors, as well as the private interests of a number of categories of citizens** who tend to be more concerned with their own interests than the benefits to wider society.

In terms of coordination, there is general **appreciation across all sectors that responsibility has been concentrated under the control of certain political and administrative figures**. While it is true that a number of interviewees criticised the lack of a clear political vision in relation to the fight against climate change, there is wide praise for the identification of an environmental department as those with jurisdiction on climate issues (indeed some even called for the creation of a Climate Change Authority), as well as of an agency within this Department (APPA) which acts as an administrative point of reference. Both of these measures are seen as very positive steps.

Finally, the **role of Europe has been described as fundamental**, both with regard to the content outlined in its directives, as well as the guiding role that it plays for the PAT, which has allowed it to free itself (somewhat) from its provincial outlook. The awareness of the particularities present in Trentino, as well as of the impact that global climate change could have on a local level and of the necessity of addressing the challenges of mitigation and, especially, adaptation at the local level, is also a common theme underlined by many interviewees.

3. TYROL

Expert-Interviews data in Tyrol (AT):

Number of conducted interviews: 8 Institutional/Administration: 6 Civil Society: 2
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TYROL INTERVIEWS - INTERVIEWEE PROFILES

INTERVIEW-CODE (extended)	INTERVIEW-CODE (short in text)	TYPE
Int_01_Tyrol_Administration_Transport	IntT_01	Institutional
Int_02_Tyrol_Administration_Energy	IntT_02	Institutional
Int_03_Tyrol_Administration_Spatial Planning	IntT_03	Institutional
Int_04_Tyrol_Civil Society_Cross-cutting	IntT_04	Civil Society
Int_05_Tyrol_Administration_Water	IntT_05	Institutional
Int_06_Tyrol_Civil Society_Energy	IntT_06	Civil Society
Int_07_Tyrol_Administration_Cross-cutting	IntT_07	Institutional
Int_08_Tyrol_Tyrol_Administration_Funding	IntT_08	Institutional

Glossary used in this report:

Name	Description	Website
Peripheral agents	Entities differently linked to the administration either directly, by means of public participation and or controlling interests, or indirectly, by mean of funding and financing of climate relevant projects, which are relevant in the climate-change policy cycle. The interviews showed a systematic outsourcing of information and awareness-building initiatives as well as coordination tasks.	n/a
<i>Energie Tirol</i>	A non-profit association and independent consulting agency of Land Tyrol developing projects and concepts in the fields of energy, environmental education, mobility, climate protection, sustainable economy and lifestyle for public and private customers.	https://www.energie-tirol.at/

<p>Conference of State Climate Representatives/Landesklimaschutzreferentenkonferenz</p>	<p>State Councillors responsible for climate protection of all Länder and the Federal Minister for Agriculture Regions and Tourism meet regularly to discuss key climate protection issues and approve resolutions and guidelines. This body developed from the Conference of State Representatives <i>Landesumweltreferentenkonferenz (LURK)</i>, as it was necessary to specifically tackle climate protection.</p>	<p>https://www.land-oberoesterreich.gv.at/187365.htm</p>
<p><i>Querschnittsmaterie</i></p>	<p>Cross-cutting subject-matter falling in different competence fields of both Bund and the Länder, corresponding to a number of competences in legislation and in the implementation of laws by state governments and state administration.</p>	<p>n/a</p>
<p>Sustainability and climate coordination unit and climate coordinator</p>	<p>Administrative organizational units specifically entrusted with the facilitation and coordination of sustainable development processes at departmental level, as well as cyclic reporting on the development in the sectoral climate-change integration.</p>	<p>https://www.tirol.gv.at/landesentwicklung/nachhaltigkeits-und-klimakoordination/</p>
<p>Energy coordination</p>	<p>Organizational unit tasked to coordinate and accompany initiatives and to act as an information-exchange hotspot within the administration in the energy sector</p>	<p>n/a</p>
<p>State or <i>Land</i> level</p>	<p>Herein the terms identify the government, legislative or policy level of <i>Land</i> Tirol, as opposed to the national level of the <i>Bund</i></p>	<p>n/a</p>

3.1. SECTORAL OVERVIEW

3.1.1. TRANSPORT

Main initiatives and strategies mentioned during the interview:

- **Infrastructural measures:**
 - 2008 Development of public transport and S-Bahn in Tyrol
 - Advancement of public transport through the establishment of the VVT²⁴ 10-12 years ago
 - 2016 Tariff-Reform area ticket for 490 EUR
 - 2019/2020 Development of the ÖBB rails

²⁴Verkehrsverbund Tirol

- **Strategies:**

- 2008 mobility program until 2012: first manifestation of climate-change integration in the transport (mobility) sector. The program contains objectives and concrete measures to be implemented until 2012.
- 2013 mobility program until 2020-2011. Note that the Report on the last program²⁵ offers an overview of the implementation of the measures.
- 2016 Bicycle strategy.
- 2021-2022 third mobility program: the new program is currently under processing.

Overview

The transport sector was considered one of the main focus points in the first climate-strategy of the Land of 2015, since it was identified as the main CO₂ emission contributor. The main objective is the improvement of public transport; the keyword: mobility. This segment of the transport sector has been characterized by a shift from a technical to a more societal approach, which is expected to positively impact the sectoral climate-change integration. The freight transport field, in turn, was deemed to be still rather underdeveloped with regards to climate-change integration efforts, due to inherent strong economic interests that characterize the field (IntT_01).

Transport was depicted primarily as a federal subject-matter. The institutional interviewee observed that there are no binding legislative sources at the state level so far, which could otherwise ease the sectoral integration of climate-change. Notoriously the Länder act as indirect administration and direct implementation agents, consequently they would have (limited) space of maneuver, with regard to the financing of climate-relevant projects and the adoption of concrete measures for the development of public transport (IntT_01). It was also noted (IntT_01; IntT_07), that the Bund is rather reluctant to take action in the implementation of specific legislation, given that each legislative initiative would also require a funding of its implementation by the Länder. It should however be noticed that traffic laws adopted at state level could represent a further viable legal source for climate change integration. Indeed, Länder may be able to decide if and how state roads are built and whether, for example, climate compatibility is taken into account at the planning stage. See in this regard the sectoral overview in the report on Vorarlberg.

3.1.2. SPATIAL PLANNING

Main sectoral initiatives and strategies mentioned during the interview:

- Tyrolean spatial development strategy “Zukunftsraum Tirol 2011”
- Raumbild 2030: planning instrument which is not legally binding but self-binding for the administration and represents a point of reference for new zonings and in the argumentation with municipalities (IntT_03).
- Precautionary reservations for land use²⁶, *i.e.* areas protected from development.

Overview

(Regional) spatial planning (“überörtliche Raumplanung”)²⁷, besides being a further “*Querschnittsmaterie*” in the Austrian federalism, notoriously falls within the exclusive competence

²⁵ <https://www.tirol.gv.at/verkehr/publikationen-statistiken/publikationen-verkehr-mobilitaet/#c225976>.

²⁶ <https://www.tirol.gv.at/landesentwicklung/raumordnung/ueberoertlicheraumordnung/raumordnungsprogramme-1/>.

²⁷ Herein the term spatial planning is used as a translation for the terms “Raumordnung” and “Raumplanung”.

of the Länder²⁸ with respect to both legislation and execution. This leads to consider information exchange frameworks between Länder particularly relevant, given that each could adopt partially different approaches and solutions (IntT_03).

Conversely, the **local spatial planning** ("*örtliche Raumplanung*") was defined as a task for municipalities, as Autonomous administrative units, to be carried out within their own responsibility, subject to supervision by the regional planning authorities and in line with spatial planning at state level (art. 118 (3) no 9 Austrian Constitution). This requires further coordination and information efforts and could lead to discrepancies in the implementation, also of climate-relevant measures (IntT_03; IntT_04).

The institutional respondent of this sector identified 2005 as the milestone in the sectoral climate-change integration in Tyrol. The 2005 amendment of the Tyrolean spatial planning law of 1994 integrated open-space reservations in the planning concepts and required municipalities to adapt the local spatial planning concepts accordingly.

According to the interviewee, a critical reorganization of the existing building land zonings would be highly desirable to rectify previous misclassifications, also in view of a more climate-friendly spatial planning. However, this option would not be practicable, as it would lead to an infringement of the private property rights of the landowners. Hence, the existing building land classifications would almost be unalterable (IntT_03).²⁹ Regardless of this highlighted criticality, the institutional respondent observed a twofold positive development in the sector over the past 15 years. First, the zoning process of new areas shifted from the designation of undeveloped areas as building land to the preservation of certain areas from development. Secondly, there would be a recognizable tendency to invest in the improvement of the existing building land towards more ecologically viable and energy-efficient settlement areas (IntT_03).

The institutional respondent of this sector deemed that the instruments provided by the state laws are adequate, since the spatial planning law has been progressively incorporating climate-change and rather highlighted difficulties in the implementation of the latter.

3.1.3. ENERGY AND WATER

ENERGY

Main sectoral initiatives and strategies mentioned during the interview:

- 2008 Energy Strategy until 2020
- 2014 Energy-Autonomy for Tyrol until 2050
- Building-subsidies changed over time since 2005
- Heating Strategy 2020 until 2040
- 2020 local Heating and Air Conditioning Act introduces ban on fossil heating and fuels in new buildings in the local Heating and Air Conditioning Act and implements severe restrictions in renovations.
- The new Tyrolean Sustainability Strategy 2021

²⁸ As stated by the Constitutional Court in VfSlg 2674/1954.

²⁹ The respondent wanted to hint at the difficulty to modify the existing classifications (due to the existence of private property). He described them as untouchable.

- *Erneuerbaren-Ausbau-Gesetzespaket* (Renewable Expansion Framework): this legislative framework determined an innovation in light of sustainability with the purpose to provide legal instruments for a shift towards renewable energy.

Overview

Central focus point in the climate-change policy in the energy sector is the shift to renewable energies, especially hydro power and photovoltaic. Further focus point is the Austrian heating strategy, which has been jointly developed by the Bund and the Länder and seeks to achieve the replacement of the oil and gas heaters by 2040 (that would imply the exchange of 1.6 Mio. heaters). The institutional respondent highlighted that the Land has a clear-cut space of maneuver in specific fields of the energy sector that fall within the exclusive sphere of influence of the Länder, such as notably the building sector and specifically the housing subsidies (IntT_02). Otherwise a continuous information exchange with the Bund, especially with regard to joint actions is inherent in this sector, especially in respect to subsidies (IntT_02).

Specifically, in the building sector, the subsidy conditions have been successively transformed since 2005 with regard to energy saving in residential buildings and the use of fossil-free heating systems. Since 2009, the subsidy for the renovation of heating systems has been adjusted so that it is no longer dependent on income but is now available to every household (IntT_06).

In the framework of the Energy-Autonomy, a strategy approved by the state government in 2014, the expectation was that the energy demand should decrease by 50% and the renewable energy sources should be expanded by 30%. The program “*Tirol 2050*” was thus initiated as a process of change, where the mobility, building and industry sectors were specifically targeted (IntT_06).

WATER (management)

Main sectoral initiatives mentioned during the interview:

- Urban water resource management (wastewater supply, wastewater purification and groundwater management): There are specific guidelines for subsidies, e.g. for securing water supplies in municipalities, with the focus on preparing for the expected longer dry periods.
- Agricultural hydraulic engineering (irrigation): A new funding guideline is currently being drawn up to ensure that sufficient water is available for agricultural land even in dry periods; always with a view to water-saving measures and the protection of groundwater and surface waters. Climate change is the driving force, being the measures related to the increase in temperature and longer dry periods.
- Hydraulic engineering (flood control and hydropower):
 - Flood control: This field of the water-management sector was deemed to still have little relation to climate change, and to be more linked to the adaptation to floods, which are only partly caused by climate change and are mainly subject to natural fluctuations.
 - Hydropower: The administration developed the so-called hydropower-criteria in 2011, which stipulates that until 2036 in Tyrol an additional 2.8 TWh (terawatt hours) should be generated from hydropower. This criteria catalog provides a certain framework that must also take other issues into account, such as water ecology and environmental protection and should enable a sensible hydropower expansion.
 - Water ecology (preservation of good water conditions): The increase in temperatures in water bodies is a problem that is being addressed directly. As adaptation measures, the administration carries out revitalization and shading measures on water bodies.

- Climate protection bonus: A bonus related to energy generation has been introduced to manifest a positive evaluation of the investments in renewable energy sources.

Overview

It was highlighted that “water” is essentially a federal competency, governed by national laws and also subjected to a number of European directives. The Länder are indirectly involved as agents of federal administration. As a result, in administrative-implementation terms, the authority in respect to legislation, guidelines and funding in many areas of this field is the Bund. A further preliminary differentiation between climate-change mitigation and climate-change adaptation is also inherent to this topic, as the water-management sector is mainly concerned with climate-change adaptation measures. Concrete mitigation measures are limited to the creation of hydropower plants with consequent CO₂ reduction through renewable energy (IntT_05).

The institutional respondent emphasized that there were and are no remarkable obstacles to climate-change integration in the water-management sector. This fact would be connected to the overall shared perception by the addressees of the measures (including the population) that water is inherently a limited resource, on one hand, and to the fact that sectoral measures were devoted to sustainability for years (IntT_05). According to the institutional interviewee, the operative fundamentals of the sector have not changed significantly due to the climate discourse, since sustainability has always been considered when it comes to water (IntT_05).

The federal legal basis was deemed as adequate and providing effective policy-tools also with respect to climate-change integration. In particular, two main instruments in the federal Water Act were considered to be crucial: (1) the Flood Risk Management Plan and (2) the National Water Management Plan. Both plans contain significant chapters on climate change. The current plans were developed in 2015 and are updated every six years. The 2021 plans are currently in the public participation stage of their development process.

3.2. DIMENSIONS OF INTEGRATION

3.2.1. COORDINATION (HORIZONTAL)

Common objectives and common strategy on climate-change integration

The respondents recognized that there are shared objectives between departments in the fight against climate-change and hinted at the overall climate-change/sustainability strategy of Land Tyrol. However, there is a shared institutional concern with regard to the implementation of these shared objectives (IntT_01, IntT_03, IntT_05).

It was further observed that what aggravates the integration of climate-change in sectoral policies is the lack of the necessary structure in the administration, which is not naturally set up to deal with such a large cross-cutting issue (IntT_01; IntT_02). This structural unpreparedness seems to be linked to the process-innovation that climate-change integration could concretely require.

A few interviewees observed that the key point would be the introduction of a climate-change coordination unit at a higher level in the organization-matrix of the administration³⁰, which would be able to impose vertically binding measures for the departments and all further organizational units directly concerned with climate-change (IntT_01; IntT_04). Otherwise, the implementation and success of the climate-integration measures was deemed to rely solely on the willingness of each public officer to adhere (IntT_01).

The existing coordination mechanisms and their viability

The coordination between different departments at state level generally occurs on a project basis at strategic level, in the policy-development phase. Inter-departmental exchange is mostly non-institutionalized and situational, with one or the other department in the framework of previously set paths for coordination for the fulfillment of certain common objectives (IntT_01; IntT_03; IntT_05).

The main coordination mechanisms in the transport sector operate in relation to the sectoral strategies and were developed by *ad hoc* introduced working groups (IntT_01). In the energy sector, the Tyrolean administration responded to the sectoral needs for coordination by introducing the energy-coordination unit: An institutionalized coordination mechanism with the mandate to coordinate and accompany initiatives by different departments or sub-divisions and to act as an information-exchange hotspot within the administration on the energy topic (IntT_02). The institutional respondent in spatial planning observed that an intensification of the horizontal coordination with the transport sector within the administration would be beneficial to overcome discrepancies in the local planning initiatives by municipalities with regards to cycle and pedestrian pathways (IntT_03). Further, a sector-specific synergy between the water and the spatial planning departments was mentioned by the institutional respondent in the water sector. This coordination was specifically linked with climate-change integration with regard to flood protection (and the development plans) and drainage and is characterized by an ongoing exchange for the development of measures implemented under the Tyrolean spatial planning law (IntT_05).

Climate-coordination unit and coordination of climate-change mainstreaming

Climate change integration at sub-national level entails a coordination challenge for the concerned departments, as the institutional respondents confirmed (IntT_01; IntT_02). To face this challenge Land Tyrol introduced the climate coordination (from 2011) and the climate-coordinator, both organizational units specifically entrusted with the facilitation and coordination of sustainable development processes at departmental level. The respondents recognized a central role of this unit in the sectoral mainstreaming of climate-change (IntT_03; IntT_05).

The climate-coordination is also responsible for cyclic reporting on the development in the sectoral climate-change integration. The different departments are requested, in turn, to provide updates on the status of the implementation of the planned sectoral climate-change integration measures, also for the purpose of identifying possible overlaps between units (IntT_03; IntT_05).

³⁰ The department-level was deemed to be the relevant decision-making level (or decision-making unit) in the administration, whereas the levels above are described as administrative structures with relative impact on the decision-making process at departmental level.

Systematization of horizontal coordination

The respondents referred to a planned evolution in terms of institutionalization of a broader coordination between the departments concerned with climate-change mainstreaming, which should occur beyond the policy-development in the implementation phase of the policy-cycle.

The goal of the **new Climate and Sustainability Strategy 2021** is to bundle and systematize coordination between departments at state level (IntT_06; IntT_07). The development of the strategy, as well as the implementation is based on two complementary levels of coordination 1) within the administration and 2) between the administration and political representatives. The core working group, consisting of the climate coordination, the energy coordination and the head of the relevant departments in the administration meets regularly and focuses on priorities, targets and sectoral measures. In parallel, there is a steering group with political representatives and the core group as an operative part of the steering group. In the broader framework of the steering group the priorities are then set. This “governance” system was originally conceived for the development of the Sustainability Strategy in 2019 but will remain as a permanent process (IntT_07). The added value of this mechanism is that it provides for institutionalized coordination between departments and between the political and the administrative leadership with the specific purpose of integrating climate-change at sectoral level. This coordination is further not only limited to the strategic phase of policy-making, but is intended to be activated throughout the whole policy-cycle, also in the implementation (IntT_07).

Outsourcing and implementation agents

Furthermore, the interviewees confirmed that the implementation of certain sectoral climate-change integration measures is **systematically outsourced** by the administration to peripheral entities, differently linked to the Land (such as, for example, Energie Tirol in the energy sector, TIWAG in the water sector, Klimabündnis for awareness and knowledge-building initiatives).

The outsourcing was deemed to be necessary, as the introduction of *ad hoc* organizational structures with new competences and tasks would not be possible, whilst the representation of the necessary outsourcing costs would also prove more convenient from a budgeting perspective (IntT_02). As a result, further coordination efforts are necessary to maintain an overview in the implementation of the climate-integration measures and occur both in institutionalized and informal manner (IntT_02; IntT_04). However, the added value is the increased human resources that are specifically dedicated to coordinate, implement and oversee climate projects (IntT_06; IntT_05).

3.2.2. COORDINATION (VERTICAL)

EU level

The significance of the EU legislation and policy with respect to climate-change integration was unanimously recognized by the respondents (IntT_01; IntT_02; IntT_03). Specifically, the EU has been recognized as the entity able to effectively advance the fight against climate-change, perceived as a global problem, by introducing binding targets both at the state as well as the sub-national level. The turning point in the evolution of the climate-change discourse has been identified with the ratification of the Paris Agreement (IntT_07).

The national level

With regards to the national legislation, a recurring reference was made to the federal Climate-Protection Law, with a critique to the ambivalent enforceability mechanism, which would not effectively bind to the set targets (IntT_01; IntT_07).

Intergovernmental mechanisms of coordination

The Conference of State Climate Representatives (“*Landesklimaschutzreferentenkonferenz*”), which meets yearly, was mentioned as an institutionalized platform of exchange between Bund and Länder. Further, within the framework of the new climate-protection law, there is to be an institutionalized climate cabinet that will then also include representatives of the ministries and states (i.e. political representatives) (IntT_07). The aforementioned Conference is preceded by preparatory work by the competent officers at administrative level, which also represent a framework for knowledge transfer at administrative level.

The respondent in the transport sector observed that the multilateral cross-cutting meetings are normally participated by climate-change coordinators, but that in the area of transport, a working-group would need to be introduced with the specific purpose of setting forth climate protection targets. This group would present the moment in which Land and Bund also discuss the financing of the measures (IntT_01).

In the energy sector, coordination efforts between the Länder and Bund have recently notably focused in the implementation of the heating strategy³¹, which seeks to innovate Austria’s heating system until 2040 in the broader framework of the Austrian pathway towards energy transition (IntT_02). The respondent highlighted that the heating strategy not only represents a viable platform of exchange between Länder and Bund but is also necessary to achieve the simultaneous phase-out from oil and gas of the Länder, especially considering that the involved subject-matters (building sector, heating and water heating systems) fall within the bundle of their exclusive competences (IntT_02). The respondent further highlighted a shift from disputes over competencies to a more systematic exchange and better formats of coordination (IntT_06).

The institutional respondent in the spatial planning sector expressed the need for improvement in the communication with regards to joint actions and favored the Bund to set a coordinated approach to be shared between the Länder in respect to climate-change integration (IntT_03). The interviewee highlighted that having different spatial planning laws at state level enables tackling locally relevant questions effectively but is not necessarily congenial for the fight against climate-change and for achieving the national climate-targets (IntT_03).

Cross-border cooperation

Finally, **cross-border cooperation** was regarded as a propulsive factor in the integration of climate change and reported to work well with regards to public transport, spatial planning and the water sector, and overall in relation to climate-change integration in sectoral policies (IntT_01; IntT_03; IntT_05; IntT_07).

³¹ See: https://www.bmk.gv.at/themen/klima_umwelt/energiewende/waermestrategie.html.

3.2.3. LEADERSHIP

Political Leadership

The political leadership at the state level has been unanimously identified as the propulsive force of climate-change integration in sectoral policies (IntT_01; IntT_02, IntT_03; IntT_04; IntT_06).

The representative of the State Governor Ingrid Felipe, members of the Land Government in the transport Beate Palfrader and Josef Geisler in the energy sector have been identified as key figures in the advancement of the fight against climate-change at state level (IntT_04). The political backing of climate-change has further a clearly recognized direct impact on the content and outlook of the climate-change measures and strategies developed by the administration (IntT_01).

Administrative Leadership

With regard to the leadership at administrative level, there is a shared institutional perception that the main apical departments in the sectors concerned with climate-change actions recognize the urgency of the climate-change integration problematic and take it into account in their main decision-making processes (IntT_01; IntT_02; IntT_03; IntT_05; IntT_07). However, this approach would not be descriptive of the overall mindset in the administrative apparatus and its organizational matrix (IntT_01; IntT_04). A respondent from the civil society noted that issues are recognized in individual discussions, but the administrative officers would often feel relieved of their responsibility to take up the issue of climate-change (IntT_04).

A substantial role has been attributed to the climate-coordination unit within the state administration (IntT_02; IntT_03; IntT_04) and to the energy coordination unit in the energy sector (IntT_06).

In the energy sector, a trend-setting role was also attributed to the Energy Institute, a peripheral entity of the administration (IntT_02; IntT_06).

Relationship between the political and administrative level

The interviewees described the relationship between the political and administrative leadership, with regard to the planning of measures, as typically top-down, but nevertheless characterized by a bidirectional exchange, where the final decision is however always taken at the political level (IntT_05; IntT_02; IntT_04; IntT_07).

Evolution in time

The interviewees report a progressive, but decisive, evolution in the acknowledgment of the urgency of the climate-change problem (IntT_01; IntT_05). This evolution at political level was deemed to have recently culminated in the amendment³² of the state Constitution with the constitutional anchoring of climate protection and sustainability as goals of the Land and in the development of the new reinforced Sustainability Strategy (IntT_06).

At this point in time climate-change has become a shared political objective at state level, irrespective of the political orientation of the governing coalition (IntT_01; IntT_04; IntT_06). Voter behavior has also changed as, in the eyes of an interviewee of the civil society, there would be overall less perceivable resistance when the political, or administrative leadership affirms measures in favor of climate protection (IntT_04).

³² See art. 7.3 of the state Constitution of Tyrol as amended in 2019; LGBl. Nr. 133/2019.

As proof of this shift in the political mind-set at the Land level, a respondent in the civil society mentioned that despite it being easier for politicians to issue subsidies rather than bans, the banning of fossil fuels represents a sign of a dramatic change (IntT_06).

The influence of civil society

The recent social movements by younger citizens (Fridays for future) and the consequent pressure for climate-change related actions by policy-makers were identified as a fundamental factor influencing the leadership both at political and administrative level in addressing the issue on a large scale (IntT_01; IntT_02; IntT_04; IntT_07, IntT_06). For example, a respondent from the civil society affirmed that an encounter between the Fridays for future representatives and the political representatives led to the formulation of a new climate and sustainability strategy (IntT_06).

3.2.4. PARTICIPATION

Overview of participatory practices

Aside from binding participation imposed by law, consisting in mandatory consultations of certain societal parties (e.g. mandatory participation processes pursuant to the Tyrolean spatial planning law or under the Federal Water Act and the Aarhus Convention), a number of voluntary *ad hoc* participatory processes were initiated by the administration in the policy-development phase of strategy-documents (IntT_03; IntT_05; IntT_06).

Participation *per se* was not recognized as a key element in the decision-making cycle. Indeed, the system was described as not being based on direct democracy (IntT_01) and the thematic is still perceived as a rather new topic for the administration (IntT_02).

It was observed that the involvement of stakeholders, and of the population in particular, is instrumental for the acceptance and adherence to sectoral measures, on one hand, and necessary to develop a broad inclusive approach, going beyond the engagement of single public officers, on the other (IntT_01; IntT_02), but is still underdeveloped at state level, where a culture of participation still has yet to be developed (IntT_04).

Sectoral participatory processes

The involvement of stakeholders was also detected in the policy-development of sectoral policies, such as the initiative Tyrol 2050 (IntT_02), the criterion catalogue of 2011 in the water-management sector (IntT_05) and the Lebensraum Tyrol in the spatial planning sector (IntT_03).

The development of the new Sustainability Strategy of the Land Tyrol, adopted on May 25th, 2021, was preceded by structured participation at a consultative level, (i.e. for the purpose of developing recommendations for policy-makers). The participation process entailed: 1) a preliminary online survey, open to the broader civil society (1.4000 responses); 2) stakeholder-workshops with the involvement of the Chamber of Commerce, Chamber of Labour, Fridays for future, “Rad-Lobby” and the broader civil society 3) information and discussion events to present and discuss the interim results 4) public consultation of the draft-strategy. As a result, the administration qualitatively and quantitatively considered and evaluated the responses in the policy-development (IntT_02; IntT_04; IntT_06; IntT_07). An institutional interviewee flagged the intention by the administration to pursue a participatory setting also in the further implementation phase with an annual exchange with civil

society on the progress of the new sustainability strategy, as well as on important thematic areas of the strategy (IntT_07).

Online instruments and tools of participation

Social media and online consultation platforms have been identified as crucial instruments to ensure participation of the younger generations, which should be regarded as the ultimate beneficiaries of the climate-change related efforts by the administration and the politicians (IntT_02; IntT_06). This aspect in the communication would need to be enhanced and further specifically budgeted, as it was identified as a clear obstacle to reach a certain age-range in the population. This aspect was deemed problematic in respect to the involvement in participatory processes and also to the dissemination of information regarding climate-change (IntT_06).

The interviewees did not refer to any specific tools or instruments to effectively measure and evaluate participation at state level.

Highlighted criticalities

A respondent from the civil society mentioned that participatory processes were already conceived 15 to 20 years ago with the problematic outcome that the people engaged would always be the same, whereby the ideas were not ultimately reflected in the decision making (IntT_06). The processes would overall need to be improved and better structured in order to avoid frustration and to bring the participants, expressing their needs, on one hand, and the policy-makers, having to adopt concrete measures, also calculating sectoral technicalities, on the other, closer together in policy-making (IntT_06).

Time resources as well as the need to provide the participants with real feedback by the administration were mentioned as difficulties linked with the execution of participatory processes (IntT_02).

The interviewees recognized the importance of the Fridays for future movement, as a gateway to involve people under 30 in connection to climate-change. Indeed, the political decision to innovate the Sustainability Strategy of Land Tyrol (2021) was deemed to have originated in a meeting between the local responsible political representatives and the local section of the Fridays for future movement (IntT_01; IntT_04; IntT_06; IntT_07).

It should be noted that the conducted interviews in Tyrol revealed an overall predominant focus on the information and communication aspect, considered indirectly as means to provide for involvement, rather than the significant employment of participatory instruments in the decision-making cycle.

3.2.5. INFORMATION

Nature of the existing information mechanisms and processes

The interviews revealed the coexistence of voluntary-based and binding information mechanisms. The voluntary mechanisms are initiated with the underlying purpose of either 1) raising awareness with regards to climate-change measures amongst the relevant stakeholders outside the administration and the public, or 2) disseminating climate-relevant and sector specific information.

As for binding mechanisms, the institutional interviewees mentioned the following legal basis: The Environmental Information Act (*Umweltinformationsgesetz*), the Information Duty Act

(*Auskunftspflichtgesetz*), spatial planning obligatory information proceedings (state spatial planning law) and the National Water Management plan (NGP³³), the Flood Risk Management Plan (HRMP³⁴) under the Federal Water Act (IntT_02; IntT_03; IntT_05). The Information Access Act (*Informationszugangsgesetz*), currently still in approval, was mentioned as a forthcoming relevant source to implement the right to information on constitutional level (IntT_02).

The mentioned binding instruments were reported to be primarily utilized by NGOs rather than the general public (IntT_02), whereas informal non-institutionalized requests for information emerge on a case by case basis. This was deemed to have recently increased and be specifically linked to the now more frequent occurrence of natural extreme events (IntT_05).

Availability and transparency of information on climate-policy

The most relevant information base on climate protection and climate change mitigation measures for the general public is represented by the yearly climate-report developed by the Regional Development Department (and specifically the climate-coordination). The report is a result of the continuative consultation with the departments responsible for the implementation of sectoral measures and is finally adopted and acknowledged by the local government. This report gives an overview on the stage and progress of the sectoral climate-change integration measures. Important developments with specific reference to climate-change integration are further summarized in sectoral monitoring reports in the energy and in the transport sector (IntT_01; IntT_07).

The aforementioned reports are all available on the institutional website of the concerned department. As contact points for information on climate-policy and measures, the interviewees mentioned the sustainability coordination within the administration, the climate alliance (*Klimabündnis*), the Energy Institute and the ZAMG outside the administration (IntT_07; IntT_04).

Overall availability and transparency of information

An overview of the utilized channels for the communication and dissemination of information related to climate-change policies and actions was indicated by the department for public relations in a written answer to our inquiry³⁵. Press releases, sent to a broad media distributor, press conferences, or entries in the newspaper *Tiroler Landeszeitung*, as well as different social media channels (Facebook, Youtube, Instagram, Twitter) were mentioned as instruments used for communicating information by the Land Tirol. In addition, figures, data and facts were deemed to have been published to enable a greater transparency and information dissemination.

Overall, the interviewees shared the assessment that there is an accessible and sufficient amount of information on climate-change, as opposed to a perceived lack of interest by the population, with the notable exception of highly engaged few (IntT_01; IntT_02; IntT_03). A respondent from the civil society observed that the administration generally responds cooperatively and passes on information as a rule, aside from exceptional cases where the information is not available to the public based on internal decisions (IntT_04).

³³ Nationaler Gewässerbewirtschaftungsplan

³⁴ Hochwasserrisikomanagementplan

³⁵ See in shared drive under data gathering, Austria, Tyrol in the cross-cutting folder

Communication strategy(ies)

The institutional respondents hinted to the development of multiple minor sectoral communication strategies, in the framework of the respective umbrella sectoral strategy (such as the mobility program in the transport sector or Tirol 2050 in relation to the energy-autonomy), rather than to the existence of an overall communication strategy for Land Tirol (IntT_01; IntT_06).

According to an institutional respondent, sectoral communication strategies, specifically targeting and addressing those who are concerned and will need to comply with the measures, is more efficient than broader communication. This aspect was highlighted from the information, as well as the knowledge-building standpoint (IntT_01). Vice versa, a non-institutional respondent, mentioned that an overall strategy on communication in Tyrol would be needed to standardize and enhance the availability of information in all sectors (IntT_04).

In relation to broader communication, the website “*Tirol 2050/Tirol Energieautonom*”³⁶ (in the framework of the Energy-Autonomy) was mentioned as the user-friendly tool to bundle climate-change related news, projects and information at state level (IntT_07). The website, operated by the local Energy Institute, commissioned and funded by the Land, represents the central communicative strategic tool chosen by the administration to disseminate information on climate change measures, projects and best-practices (IntT_07). Moreover, “Tirol 2050” was defined as a **marketing measure**, entailing the development of a logo to be used by individuals in connection to energy-autonomy activities (IntT_07).

Climate-change related knowledge and awareness building initiatives

Informative and awareness-raising initiatives with different target groups, with different addresses and stakeholders outside the administration (the general public, enterprises, schools and municipalities), are organized on a project basis in all sectors (IntT_01; IntT_03; IntT_05; IntT_06; IntT_07).

Moreover, there is a clear role of **peripheral entities** (such as the Energy Institute, the Climate-Alliance, TIWAG, *Standortagentur*, the VVT and others) in the implementation of knowledge-building initiatives and dissemination of information with regard to climate-change (IntT_02 IntT_06; IntT_04 IntT_07).

The respondents named various awareness building initiatives, which were and are continuously either conducted directly, funded by the administration or provided in cooperation with peripheral partners: for example the annual TRIGOS prize for sustainable operations in cooperation with the Chamber of Commerce³⁷; the sustainability exhibition “Eco Fair”³⁸; the communal representatives courses on climate-change in cooperation with the Climate-Alliance Tyrol³⁹; information events and initiatives in schools (with more than 300 participating schools in 2019)⁴⁰; ÖKOLOG- Schools in cooperation with the Energy Institute⁴¹ (IntT_06; IntT_07). In this specific regard, see point 3.14 “Awareness-building” in the table of measures of the climate progress report, which offers an overview of the internal and external information initiatives and projects⁴².

³⁶ <https://www.tirol2050.at/>

³⁷ <http://www.trigos.at/trigos/trigosregional/tirol>

³⁸ <https://www.oeko-fair.at/de/>

³⁹ <https://tirol.klimabuendnis.at/gemeinden-angebote/tirol-gemeinsam-in-den-gemeinden-aktiv>

⁴⁰ <https://tirol.klimabuendnis.at/alle-schulstufen>

⁴¹ <https://www.oekolog.at/regionalteams/tirol/>

⁴² <https://www.tirol.gv.at/landesentwicklung/nachhaltigkeits-und-klimakoordination/klimaschutz-und-klimawandelanpassung/grundlagen-und-ziele-der-klimapolitik/tiroler-klimafortschrittsbericht/>

An advantage of the delegation of projects regarding the information of the public to peripheral entities, was reported to be the greater availability of human resources (IntT_06).

A different approach was initiated with the “Double Plus Program⁴³”. The project provided financial help for specific low-income households and introduced climate coaches selected from civil society to ease communication between civil society and the administration (IntT_06).

In the water and spatial planning sectors, the institutional interviewees reported that the respective departments voluntarily initiate and sponsor specific training for majors, in order to harmonize and guide the implementation at municipal level (IntT_03; IntT_05).

Under 30 as a target group

Besides awareness-raising initiatives organized in schools (see above), the interviewees highlighted that there is a generalized difficulty to reach younger individuals under 30 years of age. The attempt to involve u-30 required a shift in the communication tools from traditional media (news-paper and television) to social media such as Facebook and Instagram and led to single social media campaigns on climate-relevant topics (IntT_02; IntT_06).

However, a recent survey within the Tirol 2050 program showed that there is still room for improvement, since people under 30 are 50% less informed about Tyrol’s climate change policy than older generations (IntT_06).

Online tools, social media campaigns and best-practices platforms

A temporary social media campaign (8 weeks), with the title “*Tirol schaut aufs Klima*⁴⁴” was launched in June 2021 with the purpose of informing on climate-change related projects initiatives and topics through short videos and to encourage target groups to engage sharing best-practice examples and tips. The administration plans to further pursue social media campaigns in future to make use of every available governmental communication platform (IntT_07).

The upcoming Platform on Climate Energy Circular Economy (see 4.7 p. 70 of the 2021 Sustainability Strategy) was mentioned as an exchange of information and best practices platform to concretely implement the new sustainability strategy. The target groups are organizations, companies and educational institutions and the administration. The administration could access projects and the platform could also include projects of the administration as best practice (IntT_04).

3.2.6. FUNDING⁴⁵

General interviews

The interviewees mentioned subsidies and funding of climate-change initiatives and projects as a primary measure to pursue the fight against climate change, influencing societal behavior through financial incentives. Especially in the transport sector, where the direct initiatives of the Land, in terms of regulatory framework and policies, are limited and largely influenced by the Bund (IntT_01).

⁴³ <https://www.doppelplus.tirol/de/home/>

⁴⁴ <https://www.tirol.gv.at/landesentwicklung/nachhaltigkeits-und-klimakoordination/tirol-schaut-aufs-klima/>

⁴⁵ Parts of this section has been authored by Mathias Eller, Institut für Föderalismus, Innsbruck.

The financing is however not explicitly reserved for climate-change mitigation or adaptation measures and is often pursued via the funding of measures that indirectly benefit climate-change integration in sectoral policies (IntT_01; IntT_02; IntT_05).

The institutional respondent in the water sector specifically mentioned that new funds earmarked for climate change adaptation measures were introduced in the urban water management field (IntT_05). In the transport sector, there are multiple options to gather funding for climate-relevant projects at EU, national and state level. However, the EU level was considered to be a rather burdensome funding channel, especially with regard to the subsequent accounting requirements (IntT_01).

The institutional respondents have recognized a decisive shift in the public expenditure policy over the years, which was connected to the growing concern to integrate climate-change in sectoral policies. This trend is expected to lead to a further prioritization in the budget area over the next few years (IntT_01; IntT_05).

This tendency is especially evident in the transport sector, where the resources for the public transport sector raised significantly and notably over the years (7-figure increases in recent years, the budget is currently set to 140 Mio. Euro of the 3.5 billion overall budget of the Land). This would represent an indirect climate-change measure, as the goal is to incentivize the use of public transport as means of reducing CO₂ emissions and denote the efforts taken at the state level to fight climate-change in this sector (IntT_01).

The subsidies and funding channels have developed to a point that there are multiple options available on different levels (from the Land, the Bund and the EU), a problematic aspect has become to keep an overview of the “funding landscape” and to obtain the necessary information about the funding possibilities (IntT_01; IntT_02).

Selected expert interview on funding in Tyrol

At the beginning of the interview, the meaning of "climate protection" and "climate change adaptation measures" was discussed. The terms go back to the Paris Climate Agreement. Climate protection measures are understood to be those whose purpose is to bring greenhouse gas emissions to the lowest possible level, while climate change adaptation measures are taken to deal with the unavoidable consequences of climate change in the best possible way. However, the fact that it is not possible to draw a clear line between these terms, but rather that they are intertwined, also makes it difficult to make a statement about how much funding is going into the project's areas of investigation. One would first have to define exactly what "climate measures" are. It is therefore not possible to provide financial data in this depth, because precise indicators in respect of the term "climate protection" are missing.

The European level is a decisive driver for climate policy in the member states and the regions. Since climate protection will continue to have the highest priority in the future, European funds will increase in absolute terms, but it is not possible to determine how the ratio of financial resources will determine which resources are made available by the European, federal and state levels.

From an administrative point of view, the topic of climate protection is located in all specialized departments; in addition, a unit has been created to coordinate the topics of climate protection. The departments have independent budgets and use parts of these budgets for climate protection-relevant projects and funding. Therefore, there is no central "climate budget", but it is found in the budgets of all organizational units. The individual departments submit budget proposals in consultation with the responsible members of the government. After negotiations with the finance officers, it is decided which budgets will be made available to the respective organizational unit. As a last step, the land

parliament has to adopt the budget. There is also no need in Tyrol to create an item designated as a "climate budget".

In Land Tyrol, the recent adoption of the new sustainability and climate strategy has brought a change in the system insofar, as in the future, decisions of the Tyrolean Land government must primarily be examined for their climate compatibility.

The transparency of subsidies plays a decisive role in Tyrol. The funding reports of the respective departments in the Office of the Tyrolean Land Government can be viewed online on the respective institutional homepage.

3.3. CROSS-CUTTING TENDENCIES

Missing binding frameworks, measures and compliance mechanisms

A recurring comment throughout the interviews was that the lack of binding measures and top-down imposed prohibitions, linked with direct sanctions and enforceability mechanisms, appreciably negatively impacts the fight against climate-change. Indeed, despite the increasing proliferation of soft-law instruments such as policies, common strategies, measures targeting behavioral change and long or mid-term goals – which remain the uncontested main instruments in the fight against climate-change – the latter are perceived as not persuasive or inconclusive for the fulfilment of the ambitious climate-change goals (so IntT_01; IntT_02; IntT_04; IntT_07).

The existing sources for climate-change integration stem from EU-level or from the national level. Whereas, the climate-protection law (KSG) in Austria has concretized the targets at a supra-regional level, the consequence mechanism for non-fulfillment remains vague. The EU sources are legally binding for the State; however, their fulfilment requires coordination within the State. Austria's federalism poses a further coordination challenge in this regard (IntT_01; IntT_02).

A partially different perception could be observed in the spatial planning sector. This fact is reasonably due to the presence of planning instruments and tools of binding nature that are provided by law and enacted by regulations. Also, the Länder have significantly differing regulatory powers in this sector, falling within their exclusive sphere of competence (IntT_03; IntT_02).

In the same fashion, but diversely linked with the federal regulatory competencies that govern the sector, the institutional respondent in the water sector highlighted that there is a clear and adequate legal basis for policy implementation. The viability of the mentioned federal framework has been linked to its original conception and subsequent development in coherence with sustainability as a necessary part of the equation (IntT_05).

Federalism, constitutional allocation of competences and climate change integration

According to the interviewees the federalist structure is perceived as an additional coordination burden for climate change-integration. Not only is climate-change an overlapping and trans-sectoral topic, it also requires coordinated actions simultaneously falling within the exclusive competences of either the Bund and/or the Länder (IntT_01; IntT_02; IntT_07; IntT_01). This is especially the case for the transport, energy and water sector, substantially situated in the exclusive sphere of competences of legislation of the Bund, where the Länder prevalently intervene in terms of indirect

administration (i.e. execution), soft-measures and funding. Interestingly, this leads to partially different results.

In the transport sector, the perception is that the Bund limits the options for integration, leaving the Länder with a limited space of maneuver in respect to the funding and the adoption of concrete measures. Further, the adoption of a regulatory framework (by the Bund) necessarily leads to the question of its financing (IntT_01; IntT_04; IntT_05). In the water (management) sector, the Bund offers clear regulations and legal instruments that serve the purpose of pursuing climate-change integration goals. The interviewee connected this with the nature of the subject-matter. Water has always been perceived as a limited natural resource and hence the adaptation to climate change was long considered an aspect to be included already in the law-making process (IntT_05). The energy sector is also characterized by federal competencies, however the Länder are able to take initiative in their clear-cut sphere of competences with regards to the building and heating subject-matter (IntT_02; IntT_06; IntT_01).

Spatial planning is traditionally considered an exclusive competence of the Länder based on Art. 15 of the Constitution. The institutional respondents expressed their content with the instruments provided by law and highlighted that the Tyrolean spatial planning laws have been progressively incorporating climate-change, despite there being no legislatively declared purpose to integrate climate-change (IntT_03).

The interviewees mentioned that the Land managed to achieve better results in the fight against climate-change, by integrating it in the legal framework and binding instruments, in fields where it holds the legislative exclusive competence. This was especially the case in the building sector with the adaptation of the Tyrolean Building Act (“*Bauordnung*”) and the Tyrolean Housing Subsidies Act (IntT_02; IntT_07).

Structural aspects, overlapping and climate-change

Climate-change is a cross-cutting issue which poses coordination-challenges for the administration. Normally, each *Landesrat* and each department would be concerned with certain institutionalized topics. Inversely, climate change requires a coordinated approach, which would request process innovation for the administration and continuous exchange between policy-makers in the policy-development and implementation phase (IntT_01; IntT_04).

The existing coordination mechanisms, specifically addressing climate-change mainstreaming within the administration, enable the coordination unit and the climate-coordinator to maintain an overview over the implementation of the sectoral integration and to engage in intense bidirectional exchange with the single departments, but not to concretely impact implementation of the measures. Moreover, inter-departmental coordination mechanisms between the responsible units, specifically dedicated to climate change integration, are currently not in place.

The underpinning goal of the new sustainability strategy (2021) was reported to be the positioning of climate-change and as a cross-cutting issue within the administration, to overcome the aforementioned coordination-challenges (IntT_04; IntT_07).

A culture of participation under development

It should be noted that the conducted interviews in Tyrol revealed an overall predominant focus on the information and communication aspect of climate-change. Aside from mandatory consultation mechanisms, the interviewees mentioned the initiation of single processes in the policy-development

phase. The respondents referred to an added value of citizen involvement for the overall acceptability of voluntary-based measures and expressed the intention to further focus on this aspect.

Fridays for Future as a catalyst of climate-change integration

Multiple interviewees emphasized the centrality of the Fridays for Future movement in the advancement of the fight against climate-change at state level, as a result of the pressure generated by the movement on policy-makers (IntT_01; IntT_04; IntT_06_civil; IntT_07). The local sections of the movement were depicted as stakeholders in the climate-change discourse and representatives of a younger section of the population (under 30). The movement was hence specifically addressed to enhance the acceptability of the measures, advance information on climate-change and to involve younger individuals (IntT_04; IntT_06; IntT_07).

4. VORARLBERG

Expert-Interviews data in Vorarlberg (AT):

Number of conducted interviews: 8 Institutional/Administration: 5 Civil Society: 3
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BOLZANO INTERVIEWS - INTERVIEWEE PROFILES

INTERVIEW-CODE (extended)	INTERVIEW-CODE (short in text)	TYPE
IntV_01_Vorarlberg_Civil Society_Energy	IntV_01	Civil Society
IntV_02_Vorarlberg Administration_Spatial Planning	IntV_02	Institutional
IntV_03_Vorarlberg Administration_Cross-cutting	IntV_03	Institutional
IntV_04_Vorarlberg_Civil Society_Cross-cutting	IntV_04	Civil Society
IntV_05_Vorarlberg Administration_Transport	IntV_05	Institutional
IntV_06_Vorarlberg Administration_Energy	IntV_06	Institutional
IntV_07_Vorarlberg_Civil Society_Cross-cutting	IntV_07	Civil Society
IntV_08_Vorarlberg Administration_Funding	IntV_08	Institutional

Glossary used in this report:

Name	Description	Website
Peripheral agents	Entities differently linked to the administration either directly, by means of public participation and or controlling interests, or indirectly, by mean of funding and financing of climate relevant projects, which are relevant in the climate-change policy cycle. The interviews showed a systematic outsourcing of information and awareness-building initiatives as well as coordination tasks.	n/a
Energy and Climate Protection Unit	Administrative unit within the General Economic Affairs Department with the task to coordinate and accompany climate-change integration efforts in the departments at state level	https://vorarlberg.at/-/abteilung-allgemeine-wirtschaftsan-gelegenheiten
Landesrat	Member of the state government (Landesregierung), responsible for specific pre-established subject-matters and head of	n/a

	administrative hierarchical matrix related to the field of competence.	
Bürgerrat	Participatory tool by which approximately 10 to 15 selected by sortition are involved in deliberative processes on specific topics and develop solutions and collective recommendations, presented in successive citizen-café, to be evaluated by policymakers, who, in turn, are expected to provide feedback in the framework of so-called resonance groups.	https://vorarlberg.at/-/b%C3%BCrgererrat-klimate-zukunft
Energy Institute	Non-profit association with focus on energy, climate and sustainability related questions with the subject-matter responsible <i>Landesrat</i> as chairman. The institute engages in consultancy, serves as information hotspot for policy-makers and the general public and plays a central role in the coordination of the energy and climate plan of the Land.	https://www.energieinstitut.at/
State or Land level	Herein the terms identify the government, legislative or policy level of <i>Land Vorarlberg</i> , as opposed to the national level of the <i>Bund</i> .	n/a

4.1. SECTORAL OVERVIEW

4.1.1. TRANSPORT

Main initiatives and strategies mentioned during the interview:

- Mobility Concept (strategy) 2006
- Mobility Concept (strategy) 2019
- Sub-sectoral strategies:
 - Bicycle Strategy
 - E-Mobility Strategy
- Air-quality Plan based on § 9a IG-Luft (2018)
- Freight transport concept (currently under development)
- Energy-Autonomy (2009) and Energy-Autonomy + (2021) with focus on the mobility action field.

Overview⁴⁶

The institutional respondent highlighted the centrality of sectoral strategic programs and the predominance of soft-law instruments. The 1st mobility program, adopted in 2006, was deemed to have had an initial impact on the sectoral policy integration, despite lacking an explicit reference to

⁴⁶ <https://vorarlberg.at/mobilitaet-verkehr>

climate-change. The successive 2019 mobility concept was deemed to be the most crucial instrument, encompassing all sectors of mobility and entailing an overall strategy explicitly focusing on climate-change and identifying sectoral integration objectives and measures. The administration recently responded to the much anticipated need for developing a climate-conscious freight transport concept, by initiating a policy-development process (currently still ongoing and to be concluded at the end of 2021), involving the relevant stakeholders and external experts in the field, which will be concluded at the end of 2021⁴⁷.

The newly introduced Energy-Autonomy + strategy (2021) entails sectoral measures on mobility developed in cooperation with the responsible department in the transport sector (IntV_05 transport). Strong framework conditions, in terms of transport policy, could be established at federal level (for example by setting the pricing for motorized individual transport), whereas Länder would only have a limited impact in fields where the Bund holds the exclusive legislative competence. Alternatively, mobility would be addressed in other fields of Länder exclusive regulatory competence, such as spatial planning and the building sector, or, limitedly with regard to state and municipal roads, in the Land Roads Act (*Straßengesetz*) (IntV_05 transport). It should be noted that the Vorarlberger Land Roads Act foresees a mandatory environment-compatibility of road corridors for new road-projects at state level (art. 9) and for road and pathways concepts at municipal level (art. 17). The law has been recently amended to enhance the involvement of stakeholders and of the population in the framework of the environmental impact assessment (Art. 10 Vorarlberger Land Roads Act [LGBI.Nr. 10/2021](#)).

The mobility-coordination, an organizational unit specifically tasked with coordinating the efforts for a shift to sustainable mobility and specifically engaging for this purpose with municipalities in the framework of so called “*Gemeindeplattformen*”, has been introduced as a sectoral measure in connection with the fight against change-mitigation⁴⁸.

4.1.2. ENERGY AND WATER

Main initiatives and strategies mentioned during the interview:

- “*Energieautonomie 2050*” (2009);
- 101 “*Elterntaugliche Maßnahmen*” (2012): concrete measures to cover the implementation of the Energy concept until 2030.
- “*Energieautonomie +*” (2021): new climate-strategy of the Land with sectoral measures for the period between 2021 and 2030.
- “*E-5-Gemeinde*” Land program⁴⁹: 50 e-5 municipalities in Land Vorarlberg are committed to contribute to the achievement of energy autonomy in Vorarlberg.
- EU-directives (EU-building directives⁵⁰ - falling within the exclusive competence of the Länder and the Energy-efficiency directive⁵¹ - implemented in the Federal Energy Efficiency Act)
- The building regulation of Vorarlberg which integrated climate-change aspects.

Overview

⁴⁷ For more information see: <https://vorarlberg.at/-/gueterverkehrskonzept-vorarlberg>

⁴⁸ <https://vorarlberg.at/-/vorarlberg-mobil-koordinationsstelle-fuer-mobilitaetsmanagement>

⁴⁹ https://vorarlberg.at/-/raumplanung-und-baurecht?article_id=99100

⁵⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/energy/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/energy-performance-buildings-directive_en

⁵¹ https://ec.europa.eu/energy/topics/energy-efficiency/targets-directive-and-rules/energy-efficiency-directive_en

In Vorarlberg the climate-change discourse initiated in the energy sector, which is characterized by a long-lasting tradition of climate-change integration in policymaking, in terms of shifting to renewable energy and energy-saving measures (IntV_01; IntV_06). The institutional respondent of the sector highlighted that Vorarlberg initially and primarily facilitates climate-change with subsidies, promoting the conversion to renewable energy sources.

The milestone in the sector was identified in the adoption of the first energy-program of the Land, *i.e.* the *Energiezukunft Vorarlberg* (then *Energieautonomie*), developed in 2009 as a result of the 2007 unanimous resolution of the Vorarlberger Landtag⁵². The program specifically tackled greenhouse gas emissions linked to energy production (fuels, heating oils, natural gas). Progressively the CO₂ emission developed from a background to a central theme in the program (IntV_06). In 2012, the name was changed from *Energiezukunft* to *Energieautonomie*. As a complementary tool for policy-implementation, 101 measures were developed in 2012 by a group of experts, divided in four working groups on the topics of renewable energy, industry and commerce, buildings, mobility and spatial planning (IntV_01; IntV_06).

The newly developed “*Energieautonomie +*” (2021) represents a broader strategy, which also covers non-energy related emissions generated in Land Vorarlberg and was regarded as the common reference for climate-change integration in sectoral policies (IntV_06; IntV_02; IntV_07).

4.1.3. SPATIAL PLANNING

Main initiatives and strategies mentioned during the interview:

- “*Energieautonomie 2050*” (2009).
- Climate-Adaptation Strategy 2015 with sectoral measures and the yearly climate-adaptation plans (with sectoral actions).
- “*Raumbild 2030*” (2019) first spatial planning strategy of Land Vorarlberg. The strategy specifically tackles climate-change mitigation and adaptation.
- Mobility Concept (2019) coordinated in its development with the “Raumbild” strategy.
- 2019 amendment of the spatial planning law Vorarlberg⁵³, pursuant to which development plans for municipalities became mandatory and will need to be approved by 31. December 2022.

Overview⁵⁴

The institutional respondent indicated 2005 as the starting point for the sectoral climate-change integration. Major flood events were identified as a trigger for the funding of protective measures in the water management sector and for the planning of hazard zones in spatial planning.

Recent developments were highlighted in supra-local spatial planning, with regard to climate-change adaptation and specifically in connection with open space planning. These developments led to the identification of additional tasks for the department and to the attribution of the related responsibilities to a dedicated public officer within the department, specifically dealing with climate-change integration (IntV_02).

⁵² Beilage 34/2007 “Energiezukunft Vorarlberg”

⁵³ LGBl. Nr. 4/2019 (art. 10 and art. 29a).

⁵⁴ For an overview of the division of competences with regard to spatial planning see note on the sectoral overview for Tyrol.

The institutional respondent highlighted that the spatial planning sector, falling within the exclusive competence of the Länder, provides effective legal instruments that can be utilized for climate adaptation and climate protection purposes. However, a sectoral criticality is connected with local spatial planning, a prerogative of municipalities, where the Land is bound to have a relative impact in the implementation, with regards to the rejection of local concepts that are not conforming with the spatial planning law, or the introduction of limitations for the achievement of supra-local spatial planning objectives through state spatial plans (“*Landesraumpläne*”). Hence, efforts to sensitize local spatial planning officers towards a unified implementation of the measures are undertaken in the area of counselling, awareness-raising and in the joint implementation of projects by the administration itself and through peripheral agents, such as the Energy Institute⁵⁵ (IntV_02). The respondent further highlighted that the available binding instruments, in particular the state spatial plans, could be, but were not yet, further utilized for achieving climate-change integration goals also with regard to energy-planning (IntV_02).

4.2. DIMENSIONS OF INTEGRATION

4.2.1. COORDINATION (HORIZONTAL)

Common objectives and common strategy on climate-change integration

The interviewees referred to the climate-adaptation strategy of the Land, specifically addressing sectoral climate-change adaptation. The strategy is yearly updated with an action plan, entailing general sectoral objectives for each period (last update: 2021-2022⁵⁶). Further, a common reference strategy for climate change mitigation, which now bundles the previously existing umbrella and sectoral strategies into one comprehensive concept, was deemed to be the new *Energieautonomie + (2021)*, developed with the direct involvement of the departments responsible for the sectoral implementation of the measures (IntV_01; IntV_05; IntV_06).

As the respondents of the civil society confirmed, there is a generalized understanding of the importance of the problematic; however, the actions still remain at the strategic level. Indeed, measures would be identified as generic sectoral objectives with no specific concretization of short-time actions (IntV_01; IntV_04).

Despite a generally observable trend towards the integration of climate-change in sectoral policies, a non-institutional respondent highlighted that counter actions are still promoted at state level, such as new climate non-compatible road projects. Especially the spatial planning sector, characterized by land use competition, would still need to make a clear directional turn (IntV_04).

The existing coordination mechanisms and their viability

Horizontal coordination works primarily in relation to established mutual dependencies and on a project and case by case basis (IntV_01; IntV_05; IntV_02). The informal setting has been described as a rule in the inter-departmental exchange, due to the modest size of the administration, which would not require institutionalization *per se*, but was inversely deemed as necessary in relation to the climate-change thematic, due to its overlapping nature (IntV_02; IntV_05; IntV_06). Indeed, sectoral

⁵⁵<https://www.energieinstitut.at/gemeinden/strategie-planung/raeumliche-entwicklungsplanung-energieplanung/>

⁵⁶<https://presse.vorarlberg.at/land/dist/vlk-64365.html>

climate-change integration measures are distributed among several departments, and, within each department, again distributed among various offices, resulting in a complex network between units normally only concerned with their institutionalized tasks (IntV_06).

The coordination between the single departments in respect to climate-change would be rather modest and incidental and occur in the framework of the preexisting informal coordination mechanisms, generally under the umbrella of the “*Energieautonomie*” (IntV_02; IntV_05; IntV_06).

Overlaps between the transport and the spatial planning sectors emerged during the implementation of the first mobility program; the successive concept of 2019 mobility codified that cooperation between the departments should be intensified and the departments jointly developed specific measures (IntV_02; IntV_05).

As for the viability of the mechanisms, the institutional respondents clarified that a formalized coordination mechanism is needed to ensure the existence of a clear framework for cooperation, especially in overlapping thematic such as climate-change integration, however the informal aspect was deemed as coessential for the effectiveness of the actions (IntV_02; IntV_05; IntV_03).

Outsourcing and implementation agents

The administration systematically outsources the implementation of certain measures, especially with regard to awareness building and information, participation of the population and expert support in the execution of climate-relevant projects (IntV_01; IntV_05).

The necessity of outsourcing is linked to the understaffing in the administration, which can be better remedied by employing human resources of peripheral agents of the administration, differently linked to the latter, rather than procuring personnel in the public sector (IntV_01; IntV_05). As a result, the responsible administrative units need to further engage in coordination efforts with the sectoral implementation agents, which occur mostly in informal non-institutionalized manner (IntV_01).

In the transport sector and in the energy sectors, the respondents confirmed the centrality of the VVV (“*Verkehrsverbund Vorarlberg*”) and of the Energy Institute with regards to information and public relations (IntV_01; IntV_05).

Climate-coordination unit and coordination of climate-change mainstreaming

The respondents hinted at the existence of a coordination-unit, the Energy and Climate Protection Unit, located within the General Economic Affairs Department (*Abteilung Allgemeine Wirtschaftsangelegenheiten*). The unit specifically operates to bundle sectoral policy-integration in view of implementing the climate-change goals set at state level (IntV_02; IntV_05).

The institutional respondent in the spatial planning sector mentioned that being spatial planning a cross-cutting issue in itself, a climate-adaptation coordination would adhere with the sectoral specificities, however the coordination office is located in the energy sector, due to the long-established expertise on climate-mitigation of the sector. It was also suggested that detaching the coordination-unit from one of the sectors, would enhance the overall mainstreaming of climate change at sectoral level (IntV_02).

Further, a climate coordinator, specifically managing the climate-adaptation aspect of the problem, has been identified as the key-actor within the administration to support the sectoral mainstreaming (IntV_02; IntV_05).

The climate-coordinator and the coordination unit maintain an overview on the implementation of the sectoral integration and are responsible for cyclic monitoring, also in order to identify critical areas (IntV_06). For these purposes, they engage in regular (bilateral) exchange with the single departments (IntV_02; IntV_03). The point of contact for this exchange might be either the responsible head of the department, or a public officer within the department specifically entrusted with the sectoral climate-change integration (e.g. in the spatial planning sector) (IntV_02; IntV_06). The coordination efforts often result in information, exchange, data collection and playback of the latter, but do not converge in direct influence in the implementation, which remains the responsibility of each unit (IntV_06).

Systematization of horizontal coordination

The need to systematize the coordination between departments and to clearly identify roles and responsibilities led to the innovation of the Energy-Autonomy strategy (now *Energieautonomie* +). As a result, seven sectors are identified with twenty specific fields of action and with a clear reference to the individuals responsible for the decentralized implementation of the sectoral measures (IntV_05).

In the framework of the Energy-Autonomy, a program management group (technical) and a steering committee (participated by members of the local government) ensure that the departments are involved; however, an institutionalized roundtable between departments is still missing (IntV_03). The new energy-autonomy strategy is deemed to establish coordination meetings at the departmental level twice a year for the purpose of discussing the implementation of the sectoral measures in detail (IntV_05).

According to an institutional respondent, the solution of the coordination problem would be the introduction of an additional task for climate-change in each department and the designation of an officer responsible for the latter, so that the topic is specifically targeted within each department concerned with climate-change integration. This coupled with the existing climate-coordination mechanisms (described above) would enhance the overall results (IntV_06).

4.2.2. COORDINATION (VERTICAL)

EU level

The interviewees recognized the importance **of the EU legislation and policy** in providing for a framework for binding measures with respect to sectoral integration (IntV_01; IntV_06; IntV_02; IntV_05; IntV_03). From an international perspective, the Paris Climate Conference was identified as a turning point, from which the EU acted differently, validating the efforts already taken at state level (IntV_03).

The national level

With regards to the national legislation, a recurring reference was made to the federal Climate-Protection Law, currently still characterized by an ambivalent accountability mechanism, which would not effectively bind to meet the set targets (IntV_02; IntV_03).

According to an interviewee, Vorarlberg took early voluntary based initiatives against climate-change at the state level, anticipating the EU and the Bund, however it would not be able to influence the

every-day life of citizens, as EU targets or mandates from the Bund, especially for certain important figures such as CO₂ tax or energy prices (IntV_06).

Intergovernmental mechanisms of coordination

The submission to the EU Commission of the Austrian National Energy and Climate Plan was reported as a fruitful coordination occasion between the Bund and the nine Länder, whereby Vorarlberg was represented in the core working group by the Energy and Climate Protection Coordinator of the Land (IntV_02; IntV_03).

Further, the joint development by Bund and the Länder of bundles of measures for climate-change integration (2013-2014 and 2015-2019) in the context of the national Climate-Protection law⁵⁷ was indicated as a viable coordination platform (IntV_03).

The Conference of State Climate Representatives (*Landesklimaschutzreferentenkonferenz*) was mentioned as a central mechanism of coordination between governments, whereby preparatory work by the competent officers in the context of pre-conferences would be an interesting tool of coordination at administrative level (IntV_06).

The yearly Conference of State Transport Representatives (*Landesverkehrsreferentenkonferenz*) has been identified as a further mechanism by which the federal government and the Länder adopt joint measures and the Bund can be confronted with specific sectoral needs. Further, *ad hoc* specific thematic working groups between Länder and Bund are established to address specific topics (such as public transport, automated driving, rail and park and ride) (IntV_05).

Being spatial planning a Länder-competence, with the result that each Land might adopt different solutions and approaches to comparable problems, platforms of exchange between Länder and between the Bund and the Länder were deemed to be especially relevant for the sector. The ÖROK (Austrian Conference on Spatial Planning) was mentioned as a formal platform of exchange between Bund and Länder and as a source for non-binding (or better self-binding) sectoral measures with a prominent thematization of climate-change. Besides this more institutionalized framework, a further annual conference on spatial planning at administrative level, between the heads of departments of the Länder, would also represent a relevant coordination mechanism. (IntV_02).

4.2.3. LEADERSHIP

Political Leadership

Again, the political leadership at the state level has been identified as the propulsive force in the fight against climate-change and specifically with regard to the setting of priorities in sectoral policies (IntV_02; IntV_03; IntV_05; IntV_06).

Specifically, the respondents confirmed that the climate-discourse has been a focus point on the political scene since the ratification of the Kyoto Protocol, as is testified by the constitutional anchoring of climate-protection since 2008 ([LGBl.Nr. 16/2008](#)). Land Vorarlberg was further a forerunner in Austria and approved measures and set targets ahead of time with the first Energy Concept 2009, targeting decarbonization by 2050 (IntV_02).

Roles and responsibilities at the political level in the Land government are clearly divided between the members of the government (*Landesräte*), whereby Johannes Rauch, responsible for energy and

⁵⁷ Art. 3 KSG ([BGBl. I Nr. 106/2011](#)).

climate protection, the former member of the government Erich Schwärzler, Andi Gross, member of the Bundesrat were deemed to have played a key role in setting priorities and shaping sectoral policies in relation to climate-change at state level (IntV_02; IntV_05; IntV_01; IntV_06). When it comes to implementation, it was however flagged that the roles and responsibilities within the administration would be heterogeneous because of the transversal nature of the topic, resulting in a very complex network that necessitates a structured coordination (IntV_06).

The respondents reported a unified approach towards climate-change at political level, irrespective of the political orientation and the targeted constituency (IntV_05; IntV_06).

Mayors connected through the E-5 program on energy-efficiency (composed of 50 mayors corresponding to a representation of 80% of the population) were also deemed to have a concrete impact on political decisions (IntV_01).

Administrative Leadership

At the administrative level, the relatively modest size of the administration would allow the individual officers to determine informally who (i.e. which organizational unit) takes on which responsibilities in specific areas (IntV_05). The new Energy-Autonomy is deemed to have further clarified roles and responsibilities in respect to climate-change at state level (IntV_05).

The interviewees reported that climate-change has developed into a focus point also for the administrative leadership, which would be testified by the ongoing project Mission Zero V⁵⁸- by which the administration is to act as a role-model in the fight against global warming and by the fact that no department reacts to climate-change with disinterest (IntV_02; IntV_06). In particular, the head of the Energy and Climate Protection subdivision was deemed to have a central role in the mainstreaming of climate-change at administrative level (IntV_01).

Relationship between the political and administrative level

The “paths” between politics and administration were described as being relatively short in Vorarlberg, also due to its size. The interplay between administration and the political representatives was depicted as rather collaborative and characterized by bidirectional exchange in terms of technical know-how and political backing of initiatives (IntV_02; IntV_05). However, the decisive influence would always lie at the political level (IntV_04; IntV_06).

The decisive factor for the success of climate-integration policies would be the political involvement from the beginning. Indeed, expert-meetings and initiatives would otherwise represent an end in themselves without the political mandate and at the successive political approval of the output (IntV_03). A cooperation between administration and political representatives was also deemed as necessary for the much-needed introduction of legal sources specifically regulating climate-change at state level (IntV_06).

Evolution in time

The respondents reported that the climate-change discourse has been a focus point for a long time at the Land level in Vorarlberg, hence no distinguishable turning point could be observed (IntV_03; IntV_05). Being a cross-cutting thematic, climate-change has progressively acquired more centrality in each sector developing from a background issue to a focus point (IntV_05).

⁵⁸ <https://www.energieautonomie-vorarlberg.at/de/mzv/>

The recognition of the urgency of the problem at political level, also due to the social pressure exercised by the Fridays for Future movement, recently culminated in the declaration of the **state of climate-emergency** in Vorarlberg, a resolution unanimously approved by the local government in 2019 (IntV_06). The state of emergency abstractly entails a preventive check and review on new laws, regulations, and directives for grants in terms of climate-change adaptation and mitigation (IntV_02; IntV_03). The declaration represents a political statement but is deemed to have concrete application. According to an institutional respondent a recent amendment to the Vorarlberger Electricity Industry Act could be passed by emergency resolution on the basis of the climateemergency status (IntV_05). However, contra-directional tendencies to promote climate-damaging projects and initiatives were reported by a respondent in the civil society, who hinted at the necessity of a definitive turn in policy-making (IntV_04).

The influence of civil society

Recent social movements by younger citizens (Fridays for Future), and the consequent pressure on policy-makers, both at political and administrative level, were identified as a fundamental factor influencing the leadership both at political and administrative level in addressing the issue on a large scale (IntV_01; IntV_02; IntV_05).

The environmental activist and head of the Nature Protection Association in Vorarlberg, Hildegard Breiner was also identified as a figure of impact in the development of the climate-change discourse at state level (IntV_01).

The Energy Institute, as implementation agent of the *Energieautonomie* was also deemed as holding a concrete influence in the development of the climate-change discourse at state level (IntV_04).

4.2.4. PARTICIPATION

Overview of participatory practices

Aside from binding mandatory consultation of stakeholders and mechanisms of citizen involvement provided for by the law (e.g. in Art. 16 of the Vorarlberger Roads Act), the respondents highlighted a fairly established practice of voluntary-based participation, characterized by an interplay between the activation of *Bürgergerate* (citizen's councils) at both state and municipal level, stakeholder and expert workshops, as well as *e-participation* in all analysed sectors (IntV_01; IntV_02; IntV_03; IntV_05; IntV_06).

Citizens councils represent a participatory tool by which approximately 10 to 15 selected by sortition are involved in deliberative processes on specific topics and develop solutions and collective recommendations, presented in successive citizen-café, to be evaluated by policymakers, who, in turn, are expected to provide feedback in the framework of so-called resonance groups (IntV_02; IntV_05).

For the purpose of establishing and furthering deliberative processes in decision-making at state level, Land Vorarlberg introduced (in 1999) an organizational unit, the Office for Voluntary Engagement and Participation⁵⁹, specifically entrusted with initiating, supporting and coordinating participatory processes within the administration and in municipalities (VInt 03_cross-cutting). The growing significance attributed to participation at State level would also be testified by the constitutional

⁵⁹ <https://vorarlberg.at/-/buero-fuer-zukunftsfragen-aufgaben-und-leistungen>

anchoring of participation (See Art. 1(4) of the Vorarlberg Constitutions as amended in 2013 [LGBL.Nr. 14/2013](#)).

This process can be either initiated directly by the Land (*i.e.* the interested policymakers), or “from below” by citizens themselves by means of petitions (IntV_05; IntV_03). This was notably the case in connection with climate-change, where citizens collected 1.000 signatures to stimulate the initiation of a citizen council on the climate-future of Vorarlberg. The 12th citizen council in Vorarlberg consequently took place in 2019 and its results were presented in the framework of a successive citizens’ café ⁶⁰(IntV_03).

In general, the design of sectoral citizen participation was deemed to vary from process to process, also depending on the technicality of the concerned topic (see below).

Sectoral participatory processes

In the transport sector, specifically in the area of mobility, a citizen council was initiated by the administration in connection with the development of mobility-concept 2019. Further, the development of the freight transport concept was preceded by the involvement of selected stakeholders (IntV_05).

In the spatial planning sector, the sectoral strategy “*Raumbild 2030*” was also the result of a broader participatory process of stakeholders and the civil society, which resulted in multiple recommendations for action, some of which were deemed to be difficult to implement⁶¹ (IntV_02). In the energy sector, a broad participatory process was launched in 2007 in connection with the development of the energy concept, with 10 workshops and the engagement of about 100 experts, followed by regional citizen councils⁶² and citizens’ cafes in the first phase of the Energy-Autonomy (IntV_07). The implementation of the program is further regularly monitored through yearly consultation of the stakeholders, also with the involvement of sectoral experts (IntV_06).

The development of the new Energieautonomie + strategy (2021) was also preceded by workshops with experts, representatives of NGOs and stakeholders from civil society and by online consultation process on the online participation platform “*Vorarlberg Mitdenken*”⁶³ (IntV_03; IntV_07). The statements were collected, clustered and evaluated, also by the steering committee of the program, and integrated in the outline of the final paper (IntV_07).

Online instruments, tools and networks of participation

The interviewees highlighted the recurring use of online tools of e-cooperation and digital participation at state and also municipal level, recently further intensified with the covid mandated social distancing (IntV_01; IntV_05; IntV_02).

A central tool in the digitalization of participation of Land Vorarlberg is the interactive digital tool “*Vorarlberg Mitdenken*” (IntV_01; IntV_05). Land Vorarlberg also favors the advancement of deliberative processes by sponsoring informative events on participatory practices in the framework of the so-called long night of participation (“LaNaP”)⁶⁴.

⁶⁰ <https://vorarlberg.at/-/b%C3%BCrgerrat-klima-zukunft>

⁶¹ <https://vorarlberg.at/-/raumbild-prozess>

⁶² <https://www.buergerrat.net/at/vorarlberg/regionaler-buergerrat/energiezukunft-2050/>

⁶³ <https://vorarlberg.at/-/online-beteiligung-in-vorarlberg>

⁶⁴ <https://www.langenachtderpartizipation.at/>

In the spatial planning sector, a guideline for digital participation was recently (2020) developed by the spatial planning department in cooperation with the Office for Voluntary Engagement and Participation, to guide participatory processes at Land and municipal level in times of social-distancing (IntV_02)⁶⁵.

An interviewee mentioned that an “impact matrix” was developed in the framework of the *Energieautonomie* and in connection with an EU-project in order to evaluate the effectiveness of communication measures related to climate-change on their addressees and to detect the levels of participation. The underlying purpose of the initiative was to understand how targeted individuals and groups could be effectively moved to action⁶⁶. The result was that the effectiveness of the employed tools is more difficult to evaluate with regard to the analysed communication aspects, whereas a quantitative evaluation of participatory processes would be easier (IntV_07).

Highlighted criticalities of participatory processes

It was highlighted that in participative processes all stakeholders, holding contrasting interests, need to be convened for the acceptability of the measures (e.g. chamber of commerce and NGOs and the broader civil society). The different interests would also need to be balanced and this has been reported to be especially challenging in major cross-cutting issues such as climate change (VInt 07_civil society).

An institutional respondent further connected a criticality with expectations. Participatory processes would need to be better structured and preceded by a clarification of the actual space of influence of the civil society and of the concrete limits to the discretion of the administration in the decision-making process. Further informative events to vehiculate an understanding of the technicalities of the specific issue at hand would avoid the successive frustration of both participants and policy makers (IntV_06).

A further point to improve in participation was deemed to be meaningful feedback. Indeed, the participants need to be sufficiently informed not only on the results, but also on the rationale behind the exclusion of their requests (IntV_07).

4.2.5. INFORMATION

Nature of the information mechanisms

The interviews again revealed the coexistence of voluntary-based and binding information mechanisms. The voluntary mechanisms are initiated with the underlying purpose of either 1) raising awareness with regards to climate-change measures amongst the relevant stakeholders outside the administration and the public, or 2) disseminating climate-relevant and sector specific information. The Vorarlberger Environmental Information Act (*Umweltinformationsgesetz*), was mentioned as the legal basis at state level to obtain climate-relevant information, but its effectiveness was also doubted by a respondent from the civil society (IntV_04).

Availability and transparency of information on climate-policy

⁶⁵ <https://vorarlberg.at/-/raumwechsel>

⁶⁶ <https://www.probieramol.at/>

The most relevant information base on climate change mitigation measures for the general public is represented by the website linked to the *Energieautonomie* +⁶⁷, operated by the Land in cooperation with the Energy Institute Vorarlberg. The website bundles all climate-change related news, projects and information, and the main policy-documents are directly available for download (IntV_07; IntV_05). The *Klimawandelanpassung - Infoportal*⁶⁸ was also mentioned as a source of information for climate-relevant information with regards to climate-change adaptation (IntV_03).

Overall, the interviewees shared the assessment that there is an accessible and sufficient amount of information on climate-change.

Communication strategy(ies)

The respondents specified that the *Energieautonomie* entails communication objectives, which could be regarded as the overall communication strategy of Land Vorarlberg in respect to energy, climate change and climate protection (IntV_06; IntV_07). The implementation of the communication objectives is pursued by the Land in cooperation with the Energy Institute (IntV_05; IntV_07).

Climate-change related knowledge and awareness building initiatives

Informative and awareness-raising initiatives with different target groups and stakeholders outside the administration (the general public, enterprises, schools and municipalities) are organized on a project basis in all sectors (IntV_06; IntV_02; IntV_05). Moreover, there is a clear role of **peripheral entities** (such as the Energy Institute, the Climate-Alliance and the VVV) in the implementation of knowledge-building initiatives and dissemination of information (IntV_01; IntV_05).

The respondents named various awareness building initiatives, which were and are continuously either conducted directly, funded by the administration or provided in cooperation with peripheral partners (such as the Energy Institute or the Climate Alliance Vorarlberg): for example the E5-municipality program⁶⁹; the course on climate-change for communal representatives⁷⁰; information events and initiatives in schools⁷¹; the Ökoprofit program⁷² and the ‘*Energieautonomie begreifen*’-program⁷³ (IntV_01; IntV_07).

The E5-municipalities program was specifically mentioned by the respondents of the administration as a support platform for the implementation of climate change measures in municipalities (IntV_01; IntV_03; IntV_06). The program also contains a communication and advertising strategy and a guideline for public relations⁷⁴ (IntV_01).

In the transport sector, the “*Gemeindeplattform*”⁷⁵ operated by the mobility coordination unit represents a viable platform for exchange and joint action between the administration and municipalities (IntV_05). The VVV⁷⁶ was further engaged in creating an umbrella strategy for sustainable mobility under the “V-Mobil”.

⁶⁷ <https://www.energieautonomie-vorarlberg.at/de/>

⁶⁸ <https://vorarlberg.at/-/klimawandelanpassung-infoportal-vorarlberg>

⁶⁹ <https://www.energieinstitut.at/gemeinden/das-e5-landesprogramm/e5-gemeinden-in-vorarlberg/>

⁷⁰ <https://www.klimabuendnis.at/aktuelles/klimaschutzlehrgang-2021>

⁷¹ <https://www.energieinstitut.at/bildung/fuer-kindergaerten-und-schulen/>

⁷² <https://vorarlberg.at/-/oekoprofit-vorarlberg-zertifikat-fuer-betriebliches-umweltmanagement>

⁷³ <https://www.energieautonomie-vorarlberg.at/de/energieautonomie-begreifen-von-klein-auf>

⁷⁴ https://www.energieinstitut.at/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/e5-Leitfaden_%C3%96ffentlichkeitsarbeit-f%C3%BCr-e5-Gemeinden_web.pdf

⁷⁵ <https://vorarlberg.at/-/vorarlberg-mobil-gemeindeplattform>

⁷⁶ <https://www.vmobil.at/>

Under 30 as a target group

Besides awareness-raising initiatives organized in schools (see above), the interviewees highlighted that there is a generalized difficulty to reach younger individuals under 30 years of age (IntV_03; IntV_07). Specifically, the Land would encounter difficulties to position itself and its thematic on social media and to awake interest in the younger generation (IntV_06).

The efforts to reach this target group would involve advertising and communication campaigns on social media such as Facebook and Instagram (IntV_03). However, a shift from traditional media to social media would not necessarily signify an increased engagement of the younger generation if the subjects are affecting their lifestyle directly (IntV_07).

The interviewees recognized the importance of the Fridays for Future movement and considered them as a gateway to involve people under 30 in connection to climate-change (IntV_06; IntV_07).

4.2.6. FUNDING⁷⁷

General interviews

The interviewees generally confirmed a development in the expenditure policy at state level towards an increase of available funding of climate-relevant initiatives. Indeed, the respondents mentioned subsidies and funding of climate-change initiatives and projects as a measure to pursue the fight against climate change in all sectoral policies (IntV_02; IntV_03; IntV_05; IntV_06). The financing is, however, not necessarily explicitly reserved for climate-change mitigation or adaptation measures (IntV_02). Accordingly, each department has to implement the integration-measures within their budget (IntV_02; IntV_03).

In the transport sector, funding is shared between different governmental levels: The Bund, the Land and the Municipality. Most significantly, the Land funds the realization of bike paths, whereby the Land offers a 70% subsidy and the concerned municipality executes the project. Further, the EU Covid-Recovery plan is expected to positively impact the shift towards sustainable mobility (IntV_05).

The institutional respondent in the transport sector highlighted a continuous budget increase at the state and the federal level with regards to public transport. This tendency was not specifically linked to climate-change but was deemed to have indirectly advanced the sectoral efforts of integration (IntV_05).

A respondent from the civil society, actively engaged in knowledge-building initiatives linked to climate-change, expressed the need to increase the budget for social media campaigns and marketing around climate-change measures, also with regard to the available options for funding climate-relevant initiatives. The administration, however, would partly be of the opinion that no marketing is needed and that offering subsidies is sufficient (IntV_01).

⁷⁷ Parts of this section has been authored by Mathias Eller, Institut für Föderalismus, Innsbruck.

Selected expert interview on funding in Vorarlberg

First of all, the interview raised the legitimate question of which funding can be subsumed under the term "climate change", as the latter can be interpreted either restrictively (e.g. pure climate protection projects) or extensively (e.g. projects that do not only pursue climate protection interests). For example, in the area of public transport, measures are regularly taken that contribute to climate protection, but nevertheless also take other public interests into account.

In Vorarlberg state administration - if one includes public transport – approximately 65 million euros are invested per year, of which approximately 40 million euros are allotted to “public transport” and 25 million euros to energy subsidies (e.g. housing subsidies; air pollution control measures, etc.). The latter are financed by Land Vorarlberg, partly also co-financed by the federal government and the EU. In local public transport, climate measures are largely financed by Land Vorarlberg itself, which is also supplemented by corresponding federal funds.

The majority of fundings are standardized funding programmes (e.g. exchange of heating systems). In the case of newer projects, some of these are also project-related fundings. Few projects in the area of climate protection are "newly invented", but existing ones are continuously adapted and expanded (e.g. the entire bus fleet in Vorarlberg is to be electrified).

The source of legislation in many cases is European law. It is the motor for measures that are ultimately implemented at the level of the member states and the regions, including Vorarlberg. There is a legal basis for every funding (government decision or law), and the funding guidelines are publicly accessible. In addition, the subsidies are recorded in the transparency database, and conclusions about the current funding policy (measures and scope) can also be drawn from the state's accountability report.

The use of fundings in Vorarlberg is tied to certain conditions, some of which also exceed EU standards. The administrative procedure with regard to funding is extremely heterogeneous and also depends on the funding provider (this may or may not be the Land alone). In some cases, compliance with the requirements is only checked by the Land, and sometimes also by external agencies that do not belong to the state's administration.

Climate projects will play an even more important role in the Vorarlberg state administration in the future. The pressure to become active in this area is constantly increasing, and the policy at state level is therefore also challenged.

4.3. CROSS-CUTTING TENDENCIES

Missing binding frameworks, but established tradition of climate-change policy integration

The existing legal sources for climate-change integration stem from EU-level or from the national level, whereas no legal sources specifically regulate climate-change at state level (IntV_03).

The interviewees confirmed an increasing proliferation of soft-law instruments such as strategic policies, measures targeting behavioral change, especially through subsidies, and long or mid-term goals, which remain the uncontested main instruments in the fight against climate-change at state level. The most effective instrument would however be the law (IntV_06).

Provided that push and pull measures and top-down imposed prohibitions were recognized as the most efficient means for the fight against climate-change (IntV_04; IntV_06), the interviewees tendentially expressed their content with regards to the instruments available to integrate climate-change in sectoral policies (IntV_02; IntV_05). This would reasonably be linked with the fact that Vorarlberg has a politically-based historic tradition of climate-change awareness and consequent established policymaking (IntV_01; IntV_02; IntV_03). Concerns were expressed in respect to the implementation of the measures contained in sectoral strategies and other policy-documents (IntV_02; IntV_04; IntV_05).

Federalism, constitutional allocation of competences and climate change integration

The interviewees viewed the discrepancy of competencies, relevant for sectoral integration of climate-change, as an additional coordination challenge directly deriving from the federalist organization of the state and the constitutional allocation of powers (IntV_01; IntV_02; IntV_05).

The interviewees mentioned that the Land managed to achieve better results in the fight against climate-change, by integrating it in the legal framework and binding instruments, in fields where it holds the exclusive legislative competence (IntV_01; IntV_02; IntV_03). Along the same lines, the institutional respondent in the spatial planning, regarded the available legal instruments as satisfactory (IntV_02). This fact is reasonably due to the presence of planning instruments and tools of binding nature that are provided by law and enacted by regulations.

Structural aspects, overlapping and climate-change

Climate-change poses a great coordination challenge for the administration since it represents a cross-cutting problem, which requires to be incorporated into an administration that has developed into a differently institutionalized division of responsibilities (IntV_06; IntV_03).

The existing coordination unit and the climate-coordinator, specifically addressing climate-change mainstreaming within the administration, maintain an overview over the implementation of the sectoral integration, but are not able to concretely influence the implementation of the measures and inter-departmental coordination mechanisms between the responsible units are currently not in place (IntV_03; IntV_06).

The underpinning goal of the new *Energieautonomie+* (2021) was reported to be the positioning of climate-change and as a cross-cutting issue within the administration, to overcome the aforementioned coordination-challenges (IntV_01; IntV_02).

Pronounced engagement in participatory practices

The interviews revealed a fairly established practice of citizen involvement by the administration and the political representatives, as testified by the constitutional anchoring of citizen participation in the state Constitution. The detected tendency is to incorporate participatory instruments for the development of sectoral strategies and for the setting of objectives, aside from limited involvement in the implementation phase of the policy-cycle. The involvement of the population notably occurs through the activation of citizen councils by the administration or by the population itself through petition. This was also the case in connection with climate-change, where the population convened a citizen council for the purpose of outlining the climate-future of Vorarlberg.

Fridays for Future as a catalyst of climate-change integration

The interviewees emphasized the centrality of the Fridays for Future movement in the advancement of the fight against climate-change at state level, as a result of the pressure generated by the movement on policy-makers, which provided the political grounds for further actions at political and administrative level (IntV_01; IntV_02; IntV_03; IntV_07). The interviews revealed a generalized difficulty to reach younger people. Moreover, the social movement was identified as interlocutor/stakeholder in attempts to involve this population group (IntV_03; IntV_07).
